

Agile methods and practices in logistics companies: A
framework to improve competitive sustainability

A theoretical and empirical study

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Abstract

Product complexity characterises the commercial world as technologies evolve rapidly and customer needs and requirements are constantly changing. Digitalisation further accelerates the steady increase in complexity and requires traditional industries such as logistics in particular to expand their products, services and business models, necessitating the optimisation of business processes, reach and performance. Overall, competitive sustainability relies on the ability to adapt and evolve.

This research study discusses how agile methods and practices are used by established logistics companies and logistics start-ups based on insights from the literature and from practice. Four research approaches are used to answer the research questions. First, interviews are undertaken to validate the research need and develop the research questions. Second, a systematic literature review is carried out to identify the current state of the literature. Thirdly, a qualitative Delphi study is conducted to identify which agile methods and practices are used in established logistics companies and logistics start-ups. Fourthly, an international survey to deepen the results of the Delphi study is carried out with a focus on logistics start-ups. Finally, a framework that is based on the experiences of employees of established logistics companies and logistics start-ups is developed. The aim of the framework is to support practitioners in the logistics industry in using agile methods to deal with the increasing complexity of products and processes and adapting to an increasingly digital environment. The framework improves the process of value creation in agile IT projects to meet individual customer requirements in a flexible way.

Statement of Authorship

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this dissertation are original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This dissertation is my own work and contains nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text.

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Note on authorship:

In the above papers, Malena Zielske is the main author, who conducted the research and presented it at the respective conference. The other authors provided supervision.

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List of abbreviations

AFSP	Agile framework for small projects
ASD	Agile software development
B2B	Business to business
B2C	Business to consumer
DSDM	Dynamic systems development method
EMP	Number of employees
FDD	Feature driven development
ICT	Information and communication technology
IT	Information technology
KA	Knowledge areas
LeSS	Large scale scrum
MVP	Minimum viable product
NRB	Nonresponse bias
RQ	Research question
SAFe	Scaled agile framework
SLR	Systematic literature review(s)
SWEBOK	Software engineering body of knowledge
TDD	Test Driven Development
XP	Extreme programming

1. Introduction

Product complexity characterises the business world as technologies evolve quickly and customer needs and requirements change constantly and become ever more extensive (Kagermann, 2015; Rachinger et al., 2019; Tibazarwa, 2021). Digitalisation accelerates the steady increase of complexity even further, and requires traditional industries such as the logistics industry to expand and adjust its products and services. In the context of this study, digitalisation is understood as the development and application of technologies that enable the networking of actors, companies, and customers across all segments of the value chain (Bowersox, Closs and Drayer, 2005; PwC, 2011; Westerman et al., 2011; BMWi, 2014; Bouée and Schaible, 2015). By collecting, analysing, and sharing data, actionable information that facilitates optimisation and (automated) decision-making can be generated. This can add value to business processes, reach, and performance, and enable new products, services, and business models. Logistics companies are enlarging their product range and including software products like platforms and (mobile) applications in their catalogues. The adaptability of digital products has made their creation and modification even more dynamic, which raises the expectations of customers. Customers can be stakeholders, software users, and, in the classic sense, recipients of the product or service. Customers increasingly expect faster realisation of their changing requirements (Dunne et al., 2016; Latos et al., 2017; Schmidt, Weiss and Paetzold, 2018). Overall, it can be stated that digitalisation raises complexity through the extension of existing markets and the addition of software products to product ranges of companies in all industries (Kokkinis and Twigg-Flesner, 2020; Pfister and Lehmann, 2021).

The effects of digitalisation on the logistics industry

The logistics industry is one of the industries most affected by digitalisation: especially in small and medium-sized logistics companies, a lot of work is still done manually and in analogue form (Komus and Kuberg, 2017; Anwar, Henesey and Casalicchio, 2019). Logistics companies, in the context of this study, mainly focus on the management and execution of transport, transshipment and storage of goods, but also on the optimisation of material flows and the overall, cross-company logistics management viz. supply chain management (Göpfert and Seeßle, 2017). Complexity of requirements and technologies increases as logistics companies implement more digital processes and products in order to become digital companies. Digitalisation enables the use of new technologies and data analysis, and facilitates a higher level of automation in the logistics industry. Digital platforms and "Uber-inspired" business models are constantly being established as the idea of sharing resources

becomes more widespread (Hofmann and Osterwalder, 2017; Scheer, 2017). Four main factors are responsible for these changes within the logistics industry: increasing customer expectations, new technologies, redefined collaboration, and new entrants to the market (see Figure 1) (Gawor and Hoberg, 2019).

These four main factors (marked in bold) influence the logistics industry as described below:

- Increasing and continuously **changing customer requirements** together with competition pressures from both existing companies and **new entrants** into the logistics industry force companies to adapt their products and services.
- **Technological advancements** and new services offered by the competition influence the adaptation of products, the resulting business solutions, and **customer requirements**.
- These adaptations redefine the value chain and result in new ways of internal and external business processes and **collaborations**.
- **Technological advancements** allow different forms of collaboration and facilitate existing processes.

The consequences of value chain changes are reflected in the development of new business processes, the utilisation of the ever-increasing availability of timely data and information, and consequently, the adjustment of organisational structures of companies. Logistics companies are shifting towards a more collaborative model: established logistics companies possibly still have to deal with existing tangible resources, while many new entrants only offer services based on intangible resources. Logistics start-ups may therefore be more adept at providing collaborative structures and be able to do so more easily. Overall, competitive sustainability relies on the ability to adapt and evolve (Diaz Lopez and Brandes, 2010; Bonilla et al., 2018). This raises the following questions:

- Can agile methods help?
- Are they being employed by logistics companies?
- What is a successful evolution path for logistics companies?

Figure 1: Main factors responsible for changes within the logistics industry
 Source: Own representation

Logistics start-ups benefit greatly from digitalisation and the resulting changes within the logistics industry. Based on Blank and Dorf start-ups are not a smaller version of a large company but rather: “a temporary organisation in search of a scalable, repeatable, profitable business model.” (Blank and Dorf, 2012, p.XXI). The growing number of logistic start-ups introducing disruptive business models, products and/ or services poses a threat to large, long-standing logistics companies (Kupp, Marval and Borchers, 2017; Urbinati et al., 2018). Logistics start-ups are quicker to benefit from new technological developments as they do not have to adjust their product range, but begin working immediately with the most recent product idea (Dilan and Aydin, 2019). For logistics start-ups, it is easier to use digital technologies to overcome inefficiencies, such as long waiting and transport times, and to reduce costs through the use of support technologies, such as sensors (Duxbury, 2014). Logistics start-ups can build their new business ideas and products directly on a technology stack that is up-to-date, whereas many established logistics companies use as least partially outdated technologies (Wang et al., 2019; Grigoriev and Arkhipov, 2021). In many cases, logistics start-ups have the advantage of focusing only on one innovation and do not have to fulfil needs of already existing customers. Money is no longer earned predominantly with the pure transport, handling and storage of goods, but by offering software solutions for the logistics industry (Barreto, Amaral and Pereira, 2017). IT is becoming a competitive "game changer" as it is enabling speed, flexibility and transparency of logistical processes and products, replacing manual labour (Hofmann and Rüsche, 2017). Overall, digitalisation increases the introduction and expansion of digital products, which results in additional complexity during product development and implementation.

Agile project management to deal with complexity

Digital products are developed in information technology (IT) departments which, just as other departments do, have to deal with increasing complexity (Degtyareva and Korablev, 2021). Agile project management methods and practices are used to deal with complexity where other project management methods, like the so-called “Waterfall approach”, became too rigid (Snowden and Boone, 2007; Stacey and Mowles, 2016). With the Waterfall approach, a fixed plan is followed for several months, whereas in the agile approach, the prioritisation of tasks can be adjusted incrementally (Beck et al., 2001). The Waterfall approach is particularly suitable in environments where the technological and customer requirements are clear from the beginning and change little (Wingo and Tanik, 2015; Stacey and Mowles, 2016). The Stacey matrix illustrates in which situations respective individual project management methods are appropriate: on the x-axis the uncertainty of the technological realisation (What will the solution look like?) is displayed, and on the y-axis, the uncertainty of the requirements (What is the problem?) (see Figure 2). A growing number of employees increases the number of difficulties that could potentially arise in all project situations (see Figure 2 “# people”). In the so-called “**simple**” environment, the problem and solution are understood and can be solved with great certainty and predictability. The **complicated** environment, though, is characterised by more influencing factors that follow linear causality. Agile project management methods are particularly suitable for **complex** environments in which the objective cannot be determined beforehand. The technological realisation is not clearly defined and the requirements can change. Furthermore, these variables interact and influence each other, and no longer follow linear causality. If requirements and technologies are even more uncertain and volatile, agile methods are no longer useful. This is called a **chaotic** environment, and in such environments, structures from the agile approach only slow down the work processes. What is needed here are even shorter iteration cycles than in the complex environment that allow the implementation of experiments.

Figure 2: The Stacey matrix shows when and where which project management methods are appropriate
 Source: Own representation based on (Stacey and Mowles, 2016, Uludag, Harders and Matthes, 2019)

In recent years, the use of agile project management methods and practices which are mainly used in IT departments and IT projects has increased in importance as requirements have tended to evolve more quickly and complexity increases (Singh and Vyas, 2012; Kapyaho and Kauppinen, 2015; Hoda, Salleh and Grundy, 2018). These circumstances can be caused by rapidly changing customer expectations, uncertainties in the business model, complexity of technological decisions, or other evolving external and internal influences (Beck, 2000; Cockburn and Highsmith, 2001). The application of agile project management methods began in software companies but gained acceptance in other industries and in their IT departments, where software is also developed and maintained (Laanti, Salo and Abrahamsson, 2011; Schön, Thomaschewski and Escalona, 2017). Agile methods and practices promise to deliver customer value consistently and in short iterations by adapting and improving the product/ service and the work process incrementally and empirically (Larman and Basili, 2003; Abbas, Gravell and Wills, 2008). Agile methods aim also to learn from customer feedback, to maximise customer value (Sambinelli and Borges, 2019). Since the level of agility of the companies is linked to their interaction with customers, it depends heavily on the mindset of the

employees, the customers, and the organisational structures (Elberzhager et al., 2017). With an open mindset and willingness to improve continuously, agile methods and practices promote the fast implementation of customer-oriented solutions (Beck et al., 2001). As digitalisation and the resulting increase in complexity do not only affect the software industry, the question arises as to whether agile methods can also be applied in industries such as the logistics industry. The question is whether logistics companies have the necessary mindset and organisational structures in place so that they can benefit from the application of agile methods.

IT and agile methods in the logistics industry

IT projects and departments have been relevant in the context of the logistics industry essentially since the advent of office computing. For example, software products can be used to deal with complex logistical processes with a high number of parties involved, but also to share information and documentations to introduce additional controlling mechanisms (Gleissner and Femerling, 2013). At the time of this research more than ever before, the value of IT and software products increases through digitalisation: logistics processes are not only supported by IT to reduce costs, but software products are used to create a competitive advantage (Sohal, Moss and Monash, 2001). As IT and software products become an essential part of the logistics industry, it is more and more important for IT departments and IT projects in logistics companies to react quickly to changing requirements. This is where agile methods and practices have proven to be very helpful (Cockburn and Highsmith, 2001; Cohn, 2009). Flexibility, continuous management of customer requirements, and a high degree of communication and cooperation between disciplines and departments, such as IT, sales and accounting departments, are necessary for the successful utilisation of agile methods. Companies need to bridge the gaps within an organisation and break down isolated functional “silos” where employees concentrate on their tasks in their respective, dedicated departments without keeping an eye on the overall process (Hussaini, 2014). Agile methods aim to create an environment where employees, for example from IT and business departments, work together, and strive for continuous optimisation in order to meet their common goal: increasing customer value (Leppänen, 2013). The success of logistics start-ups and the threat they can pose to established companies could be explained by differences in their organisational structure. Organisational structure in the context of this work includes aspects such as hierarchies, team composition, and cooperation within teams, and with other teams. Logistics start-ups seem to be able to deal well with complex situations such as reacting to rapidly changing customer expectations and business model insecurities (Alizadeh and Jetter, 2019;

Felizola, de Aragão Gomes and Prata de Almeida, 2019). Many established logistics companies, though, seem to face difficulties in such situations as they are often organised in isolated functional “silos” and are more project- than product-focused. Some established logistics companies cannot keep up with logistics start-ups or the speed of innovation within the industry (Beck et al., 2001; Newkirk, 2002; Delfmann et al., 2018). Responsiveness and the way companies can deal with complexity could therefore be related to the organisational structures of logistics start-ups and those of established logistics companies as well as their uses of agile methods (Sommer, Loch and Dong, 2009). To retain market leadership in the future, many logistics companies need to adjust their organisational structures and utilisation of project management approaches to the requirements of constantly evolving markets and technologies.

As discussed above, agile project management methods and practices enable companies to cope faster with changing requirements and allow for a strong focus on customer requirements and fast feedback cycles (Starke, 2020). This poses the question: what organisational requirements have to be met to apply agile methods? What agile methods and practices are used by logistics start-ups, and how do they compare with those used by more established logistics companies? Based on the comparison between start-ups and established logistics companies, it is interesting to assess how the use of agile methods develops over the lifespan of logistics start-ups.

Figure 3: Organisational prerequisites and focus of agile methods

Source: Own representation

Figure 3 summarises the focus of agile methods in dealing with complexity, digitalisation, and the resulting changes for the logistics industry, in addition to the organisational perquisites that must be met. In summary, there are four central aspects that endorse the application of agile methods in the logistics industry:

- For the successful use of agile methods, logistics companies must fulfil a number of requirements. In order to **focus on products** instead of processes or temporary projects, logistics companies need to simplify **cross-functional collaboration** (Chau and Maurer, 2004).
- **Frequent and regular communication**, preferably face-to-face, increases the speed of development and implementation of products (Paasivaara and Lassenius, 2006). **Flat hierarchies** and an organisational culture that promotes transparency and also allows for mistakes advance communication between employees and also with the customer (Paasivaara, Durasiewicz and Lassenius, 2008).
- Digitalisation increases the need for fast responsiveness and the ability to deal with the complexity of logistics companies (Butollo, 2021). The **empirical and iterative approach** of agile methods as well as the **focus on customer value** support logistics companies in dealing with increasing complexity (Larman, 2003).
- Digitalisation enables the development of new products and services such as software and digital platforms that simplify the work of the logistics industry. Agile methods allow **rapid reactions to changes** and facilitate the **continuous management of requirements** (Dingsoyr, Dybå and Moe, 2010; Lundene and Mohagheghi, 2018).

To conclude, this study deals with the use and usability of agile methods in logistics companies. The next section details, after outlining the research gap, exactly which research questions are answered in this study.

1.1. Research gap

Initial research into the literature showed that there is a growing scientific interest in the use of agile methods and their application in companies (Cheng, Jansen and Remmers, 2009; Dingsoeyr, Falessi and Power, 2019; Martínez and López, 2019; Khomyakov, Mirgalimova and Sillitti, 2020). With its origin in the software industry, the use of agile methods is also becoming more and more common in other industries and their IT departments (Conforto et al., 2017; Conforto and Amaral, 2016). Looking at the publications on the logistics industry, there are increasingly more studies on logistics start-ups in general (Rimmer and Kam, 2018; Göpfert and Seeßle, 2019), though as of January 2021, only a few publications could be found on the use of agile methods in software development within established logistics companies (Gunasekaran and Yusuf, 2002; Marlow and Paixão Casaca, 2003; Morlok and Chang, 2004; van Oosterhout, Waarts and van Hillegersberg, 2005; Wang, 2011; Pijpers

et al., 2012; Tuan and Thang, 2013; Dybå and Dingsøy, 2015; Longo and Iazzolino, 2016; Gurahoo and Salisbury, 2018; Bernal et al., 2019; Genzorova, Corejova and Stalmasekova, 2019; Cichosz, Wallenburg and Knemeyer, 2020; Rola and Kuchta, 2020; Dunz, Werth and Breitner, 2020). No study on logistics start-ups and their implementation of agile methods could be found.

Some studies deal with agility in established logistics companies: however, these studies look at other types of agility, such as manufacturing or supply chain agility, but not at agile project management methods (Marlow and Paixão Casaca, 2003; Swafford, Ghosh and Murthy, 2006; Holcomb and Gligor, 2012). It turns out that the existing publications mainly describe the agility of processes. In contrast, agile methods, which are the focus of this study, also include collaboration within the teams and with the customer. The studies of Jurczak and Chang et al. (Jurczak, 2020) support the importance of IT as a competitive advantage for logistics companies. As the interest in and need for IT grows, the need for project management methods, such as agile methods, increases in the logistics industry correspondingly. Furthermore, there are studies that investigate the use of agile methods in start-ups, especially software start-ups (Groenewegen, Langen and Groenewegen, 2012; Daniels, 2014), but thus far no study could be identified that deals with the use of agile methods in logistics start-ups and their IT department and IT projects. Although software start-ups are certainly an interesting comparison to logistics start-ups, the aim of this study is to examine logistics start-ups in particular. The software industry is very innovative compared to the rather conservative logistics industry: logistics start-ups are embedded in an network of other logistics companies and have to deal with the characteristics of the logistics industry (Soosay and Hyland, 2004; Anderson et al., 2011; Kupp, Marval and Borchers, 2017). In general, it can be observed that the number of studies that deal with logistics start-ups is increasing (Göpfert and Seeßle, 2019). But no study on logistics start-ups and their use of agile methods could be identified. The growing number of publications on logistics start-ups validates the importance of the research field of this study.

1.2. Research questions. aim and objectives

The following research questions, which have been developed based on the findings of the interviews, will be addressed (see Section 3.3.1. – Interviews, page 64):

- Research Question 1: What agile methods and practices do established logistics companies and logistics start-ups use?

Agile methods and practices are used by established logistics companies and logistics start-ups in their IT departments and IT projects. The goal is to compare whether established

logistics companies and start-ups use similar agile methods and practices. Based on the findings, it is possible to deduce, for example, which factors influence the selection of agile methods and practices and in which company contexts certain agile methods and practices are used.

- Research Question 2: What benefits do established logistics companies and logistics start-ups realise through the use of agile methods?

The sorts of problems logistics companies seek to solve using agile methods and practices, as these methods promise to generate added value for the customer faster and more effectively, are analysed. In addition, it is considered which improvements logistics companies hope to achieve by using agile methods, since the methods also aim to streamline processes and improve cooperation within software development teams.

- Research Question 3: What difficulties do established logistics companies and logistics start-ups face concerning the adoption of agile methods and practices?

The difficulties established logistics companies as well as logistics start-ups experience introducing and applying agile methods and practices can be of different natures, e.g. difficulties during the agile transformation and with the understanding of agile methods in IT departments or with customers who may expect different approaches than the IT department does. In addition, existing, rather “classical”, processes in logistics companies can prevent agile methods from being used in the best possible ways, thus preventing them from developing to their full potential. Results of this RQ allow a comparison between the challenges faced by established logistics companies to those faced by start-ups.

The focus of this study is on the logistics industry and the IT departments and projects of logistics companies. The main aim of this study is to investigate theoretically and empirically how agile methods and practices can be employed by logistics companies, old and new to develop products and services for a complex and continuously changing business environment. In more detail this study pursues to achieve the objectives listed below and summarised in Figure 4:

- Carry out interviews to validate the need for research and develop the research questions (RQs).
- Perform a systematic literature review (SLR) to determine the current state of the literature in the field of the application of agile methods by logistics start-ups and established logistics companies.

- Conduct a qualitative Delphi study to determine what agile methods and practices are used in established logistics company and logistics start-ups.
- Perform an international survey to deepen the results of the Delphi study focusing on logistics start-ups.
- Describe how agile methods and practices are used by established logistics companies and logistics start-ups based on the findings in the literature and in real-life.
- Create a framework that supports practitioners from logistics start-ups and companies in their use of agile methods and helps them prepare for the introduction and selection of appropriate agile methods and practices.

Research method	Link to RQs	Objectives	Anticipated outcomes
Interviews	Used to develop RQ	Validate the need for research and develop research questions	Practical view on research topic
SLR	Collect data to answer RQ	Determine current state of the literature	Gathered theoretical view
Delphi study		Gather data on the use of agile methods in the logistics industry	Expert knowledge on research topic
Survey		Deepen the results of the Delphi study	Wider perspectives on research topic
Data analysis	Provide consolidated answers to RQ	Compare findings of the conducted studies	Data gathered is analysed
Data consolidation		Create a framework that supports practitioners in their usage of agile methods	Presentation of main findings

Figure 4: Objectives of this study and research methods used
Source: Own representation

1.3. Study significance

Ultimately, various benefits for the logistics sector as well as for people and organisations outside the logistics sector can be gleaned from this study. Within the logistics sector, the study is particularly significant in terms of the experiences of other logistics companies with regard to agile methods, as interested logistics companies and start-ups can learn from them. Through the empirical approach of agile methods, products, services, business models, and processes are constantly questioned and improved. The framework developed in this study supports the continuous scrutiny of the existing ways of work. The adaptability of agile companies and technical advancements enable the rapid implementation of customer requirements, and internal processes can in turn be optimised and made more efficient. Potential benefits of the use of agile methods and practices and the improvement of internal processes could be the reduction of waiting times, the optimal utilisation of transport locations, and the minimisation of transport routes. These potential optimisations could make the logistics industry more sustainable and reduce CO₂ emissions through reducing empty runs, using electric vehicles, or increasing multimodal transport. In the EU, transport produces more than one

quarter of the overall greenhouse gas emissions and is the main reason for air pollution in the cities (European Commission, 2021).

The study of these topics and results presented increase the survivability of both logistics start-ups and established companies: numerous participants of the interviews and the survey confirm that the use of agile methods is necessary to be successful. Furthermore, the results discussed here support the understanding and use of agile methods in a way that raises the overall product quality level of the logistics industry. Customer value increases through frequent and regular communication within the team and with the customer, making the experiences of the participants and understanding their practices particularly beneficial. In summary, the findings of this study can contribute towards potential improvement in competitiveness of companies. The framework offers approaches for logistics companies on how they can apply agile methods, and describes practical experiences with continuous improvement processes, such as those used in Scrum or Kanban. Additionally, agile methods see employees as the most important resource, and the framework encourages logistics companies to design their working environments according to their own needs which increases satisfaction and motivation in addition to productivity of the employees. Outside the industry, customers of the logistics industry could benefit from the faster implementation of their requirements supported by the framework presented here, as well as from innovative and continuously improving products. Furthermore, logistics are a crucial part of globalisation, and the continuous improvement of logistics processes can enhance the globalisation in a sustainable way and help companies to survive in a changing world.

The number of different studies conducted that are consolidated in one multi-method approach and the variety of participants (see Figure 5) ensure a high level of quality. No study that examines the use of agile methods in the logistics industry, including both the literature and practitioner perspectives, has thus far been found. This study collects knowledge in a rather unexplored area and for the first time contrasts the views of a variety of participants in said area with the theories of the literature. The peer-reviewed publication of the results of the studies in several acknowledged scientific journals and conferences confirms the recognition and significance of these studies and approaches within in the scientific community (see list of publications, page V).

Research method	Type of company of interest	Number of sources	Type of source
Case study	12 logistics start-ups	15 participants	Top manager
SLR	Traditional logistics companies and start-ups	15 papers	Conference proceeding, journal article, book chapter, PhD study
Delphi study	14 traditional logistics companies and 15 start-ups	29 participants	Top manager, project manager, agile coach
Survey	95 logistics start-ups	95 participants	Top manager, developer, agile coach

Figure 5: Overview of conducted studies, sources and participants

Source: Own representation

Results from the interviews carried out with employees from twelve logistics start-ups verify the need for agile methods in logistics start-ups, the interest of the employees in the implementation of agile methods, and the relevance of the research topic. The need for the scientific community of studies and methodology in these areas is verified in the SLR through the identification of a research gap. To understand the use of agile methods in the logistics industry overall and in the scientific literature, publications on logistics start-ups and established logistics companies are gathered in the SLR. Based on these results, the agile methods and practices that are used by established logistics companies and logistics start-ups are determined by means of a Delphi study with 29 experts from the field of logistics in Germany, and an international survey with 95 participants from logistics start-ups worldwide. The selection of research methods that build on each other ensures the relevance of the study for practitioners and researchers. Contribution of this study are highlighted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Contribution of this PhD study based on the research questions and the activities

Source: Own representation

Based on the findings of the interviews, SLR, Delphi study and survey, a framework is developed. Such a framework does not yet exist in the research field. It illustrates the use of agile methods in logistics start-ups in addition to the evolution of the start-ups with regard to agile methods: the framework and detailed results are of great value for practitioners and researchers alike. Practitioners can profit from the experiences of other start-ups and use them for their own application of agile methods while researchers learn from the methodology used to address this unexplored research field. In addition, this study lays a foundation for closing the research gap and enables further in-depth research.

1.4. Contribution to knowledge

The contributions of this thesis are interesting for academia and practice. The contribution to research is, on the one hand, the methodological approach, which can also be used as an example for other previously unexplored research areas. In addition, the results confirm the use of agile methods in logistics and provide the basis for future research. The study is also relevant for practitioners; it complements existing theory of IT project management, product design, and development processes

in IT and enables optimisations of existing processes to the new challenges. This can generate decisive competitive advantages.

1.5. Structure of the study

This study is structured into eight chapters, which are summarised in the following:

- **Chapter 2** presents the underlying research design of this study. The methodology, consisting of the interviews, the SLR, the Delphi study, and the survey, are explained in addition to the reasons why, and with what aim the research methods have been chosen. Additionally, the research approaches of the interviews, the SLR, the Delphi study and the survey are described.
- **Chapter 3** illustrates the interviews that are performed to validate the relevance of the research topics. Founders and top managers of twelve logistics companies have been interviewed to explore the need for agility and the value of agile methods for logistics start-ups. Based on the verified need for further research and the interest of the practitioners in the research topic, the research questions are developed and presented in Chapter 4.
- **Chapter 4** presents the theoretical background of this study. Based on a scoping study, definitions and the origins of agile methods and practices are described. To understand the context of the logistics industry, established logistics companies are defined and contrasted with logistics start-ups. Additionally, IT departments and projects in the logistics industry are explained. The second part of chapter 4 presents the data that is collected in the literature on the research topic. Of the 15 publications that are identified, none included views on logistics start-ups. All publications present data on the application of various agile methods in established logistics companies in addition to the benefits and challenges of their application.
- In **Chapter 5**, the Delphi study results are shown. 29 experts from established logistics companies and logistics start-ups are questioned about their implementation of agile methods. Over the course of three complementary rounds, data, including on the benefits and challenges of agile methods, are gathered.
- **Chapter 6** shows the survey results. The survey is used to deepen the findings of the Delphi study. 95 employees of logistics start-ups worldwide provided their views on the three RQs. No noticeable differences between the logistics start-ups from different countries are identified. However, the age of the logistics start-ups causes different views on the use of agile methods.

- In **Chapter 7**, data gathered through the conducted studies is consolidated. Over the evolution of the logistics start-ups different approaches towards the application of agile methods become visible, and a framework on their use is developed. Logistics start-ups of different ages face various challenges and aim to realise diverse benefits.
- **Chapter 8** provides a summary of all results of this study, as well as its contribution to knowledge with regard to practitioners and with regard to researchers, its limitations and an outlook for further research.

2. Methodology

In the previous chapter, the basics and the definitions of the conceptual approach of agile methods and practices as well as of established logistics companies and logistics start-ups have been explained to establish a common understanding. The aim of this chapter is to present the chosen research design more closely to tackle the RQs that are derived based on the findings of the interviews (see Section 3.3.1 - Interviews, page 64). Following a short discussion on the research philosophy, the overall research design is presented, and the used methods of enquiry employed are explained and discussed. In more detail, the following aspects of the methods of enquiry are explained in the methodology chapter:

- Research approach
- Objective
- Data collection
- Data analysis
- Ways to ensure objectivity, validity and reliability

2.1. Research philosophy

Easterby-Smith and Thorpe illustrate three basic points on how philosophy can contribute to the methodology of research (Easterby-Smith and Thorpe, 1994). The first is that research philosophy aids the researcher in his effort to find the right perspective for examining things. In other words, it provides the strategy that the researcher should follow, to gather facts and interpret them. This strategy will also allow the researcher to avoid unnecessary work, in the sense of identifying any limitations of the chosen approach and finally, to identify the methods of enquiry that are fit for purpose.

From the two opposing views that exist, between positivism and post-positivism or interpretivism the example of post-positivism will be followed for the purposes of this research (Malhotra, Nunan and Birks, 2017). The philosophy of positivism does not fit here, as it does not base its results and conclusions on subjective assessments of the study participants. Positivism aims to reach objective conclusions and to explain causal relationships. This is not possible within the framework of this research, as the assessments of experts and study participants are essential due to the research gap. Due to the nature of the survey (Delphi study, interviews), a certain degree of subjective assessments cannot be avoided.

The interpretivist perspective is highly appropriate in the case of business and management research as it recognises the role of humans as social actors and thus their ability to interpret things in a particular way. Social world as in business and management is far too complex to be defined by definite laws as in physical sciences and positivism (Saunders et al., 2019).

The two main approaches when considering a strategy on implementing the above philosophical views is either deductive or inductive or a combination of them (Saunders et al., 2019). Inductive reasoning is a theory building process which starts with observations and seeks to establish generalisations about the phenomenon under investigation. On the other hand, deductive reasoning is a theory building process which starts with an established theory or generalisation and examines the applicability of the theory to specific instances (Hyde, 2000). According to Saunders et al., the inductive approach is more appropriate in cases when the researcher is particularly interested to understand why something is happening, rather than what is happening as in the deductive approach (Saunders et al., 2019).

The realist approach is not conducive to this study. Critical realism recognises the influence and interrelationship between individuals, groups and organisations that are also relevant in the agile context, but realism sees the world as unchanging. This does not fit with the research topic, which deals with the impact of increasing complexity on the logistics industry and resulting changes. More specifically, this study follows the philosophical idea of pragmatism which means acting on the assumption that knowledge is not fixed but has to be constantly questioned and interpreted (Morgan, 2014; Saunders et al., 2019). Shields suggests that “doubt is resolved through critical reasoning and ultimately tested in action” (Shields, 1998, p.197). The research topic, agile methods in logistics companies, is rather unexplored so that it is not possible to build on existing assumptions. Knowledge must first be collected and then questioned from different perspectives. It can be assumed that knowledge will change over the course of the research. On the one hand, unexpected discoveries worth pursuing, and the different perspectives of the participants can also influence the results. In addition, the subjectivity of the researchers must be taken into account when engaged in qualitative research approaches. As the research topic is largely unexplored an inductive approach is chosen to gather data, through several methods of enquiry. A deductive approach is also used, utilising previous results to critically evaluate and enhance the findings. Overall, one can argue that this study employs a mixed methods approach.

2.2. Overall research design

Overall, this study is based on a mixed methods approach. The data of this study is gathered through five different methods of inquiry: a scoping study, interviews, an SLR, a Delphi study and a survey. The aim is to include different perspectives and achieve the research aims presented in the introduction (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Overview of the research design

Source: Own representation

In the first step, a scoping study is performed to establish the focus of this study and develop a fundamental understanding of the research field (see Section 4.1. – Scoping study, page 67). In the next step, explorative interviews are carried out to verify the relevance of the research topics and develop the RQs described below (see Section 3 – Interviews, page 56). All three following research methods, the SLR, the Delphi study and the survey, are used to provide answers to these RQs from different perspectives. In the third step, literature on the identified research topic is collected through an SLR to discover the status of the literature on the use of agile methods in the field of logistics (see Section 4.2. – SLR, page 88). The SLR shows how the research topic fits into the current body of knowledge. In the fourth step, a Delphi study is applied to gather expert perspectives in the rather unexplored research field. The Delphi study allows a multidimensional understanding of the views

of established logistics companies and logistics start-ups on the use of agile methods and practices (see Section 5 – Delphi study, page 103). In the fifth step, a survey is conducted to deepen the results of the Delphi study (see Section 6 – Survey, page 130). In the final step, results of all five research methods are consolidated in one framework that describes the use of agile methods over the age of logistics start-ups (see Section 7 – Framework, page 155).

Together, the selected research methods form a mixed method approach which is chosen for several reasons. Mixed methods approaches that gather, analyse and interpret quantitative and qualitative data on the same research topic became popular in social, behavioural and related science in the last twenty years (Creswell, 1999; Leech and Onwuegbuzie, 2007). Mixed methods approaches are used when one approach, either qualitative or quantitative is not sufficient (Leech and Onwuegbuzie, 2007; Bergman, 2008). In the case of this study, a qualitative inductive research (Interviews and Delphi study) is necessary to gather the views of experts as hardly any theoretical data existed. A quantitative deductive survey follows the Delphi study to deepen and quantify the results. More powerful results can be acquired through the combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). The choice of research methods is influenced by several factors. First and foremost is the research topic. The use of agile methods in logistics companies focuses on processes and cooperation in companies. People and their way of working are strongly in the centre of attention. Therefore, perspectives of practitioners needed to be taken into account and research methods had to be selected that presented their perspectives in an objective and valid manner such as the interviews and the Delphi study. The second factor is the state of research. Depending on how much research has already been done in a research field, there are different starting points for research. The present research field is largely unexplored. Therefore, a qualitative knowledge base has to be formed through explorative approaches such as the interviews and the Delphi study. The results of the explorative studies are deepened and tested quantitatively in the next step through the survey. The third factor is the combination of the individual methods. The results of the individual methods should allow the subsequent methods to deepen the knowledge gathered previously. Especially the combination of the Delphi study and the survey makes it possible to establish a close link. The questionnaires from the Delphi study are used and supplemented in the survey in order to critically evaluate the results of the Delphi study.

2.3. Overview of the explorative interviews

In the scoping study, data is collected to gain a first understanding about the relevance of the research topic. Digital search engines such as Google Scholar, Elsevier and SpringerLink are used for an initial, narrative literature search (see Section 4.1. – Background, page 67). Since it is only a narrative research, the significance is limited. To confirm the need for research from the perspective of practitioners, interviews are conducted with employees of twelve start-ups in 2018 and 2019 (see Section 3 - Interviews, page 56). Twelve semi-structured interviews were performed with 15 employees from logistics start-ups to understand whether agile methods are used in real life and whether these methods create added value. The answers are expanded by information from the start-ups' homepage, brochures and a visit to the start-ups' offices to gain a comprehensive picture of the use of agile methods. The RQs of this PhD study are derived based on the real-life data collected in the interviews in order to make the study and its results as practical and usable as possible for employees of logistics companies. Alternatively, observations could have been used. Observations are easy to conduct, have a high level of accuracy as answers are not distorted by respondents. However, larger correlations cannot always be observed and the method is very time consuming. Since not only the use of agile methods should be questioned, but also the motivation for their use and the challenges, interviews were chosen to ensure a closer exchange with the participants. All subsequent research methods, the SLR, the Delphi study and the survey, aim to find answers from different perspectives for all three RQs.

2.3.1. Research approach of the interviews

In a context of increasing digitalisation and the resulting growing complexity, the discovered lack of research studies covering logistics companies demonstrates the necessity of further research (Holdorf, Roeder and Haasis, 2015). To comprehend the relevance of the research topic, the current application and the benefits of agile methods for logistics start-ups, an exploratory interview approach is chosen. Within the interviews, the focus is on logistic start-ups in order to get a more realistic picture of reality by narrowing down the sample to a small sector. The initial study uses a qualitative research design in the form of an embedded inductive multiple interviews (Eisenhardt, 1989; Ellram, 1996; Voss, Tsiriktsis and Frohlich, 2002; Yin, 2018).

2.3.2. Objective of the interviews

The purpose of these interviews is to collect data on the actual application of agile methods by questioning employees of logistics start-ups and analysing company material in order to gain insights on the following topics and to validate the need for further research:

- Understanding of the interviewees of agility and agile methods
- Application of agile methods and practices
- Impact on the success of the logistics start-ups
- Ways to measure success in logistics start-ups

2.3.3. Selection of participants

To discover the broad understanding of agility of logistics start-ups, logistics start-ups with different business models such as business to business (B2B) and business to customer (B2C), varying number of employees (EMP) and target customers are selected based on ‘purposeful maximal variation’ (Creswell, 1999). The research sample includes twelve logistics start-ups (see Table 4) founded in 2018 or earlier.

The participating start-ups are classified according to so-called foundation stages. In the start-up literature, different approaches can be found to divide the founding process into stages (Pleschak, Sabisch and Wupperfeld, 1994; Kollmann, 2009; Levie and Lichtenstein, 2010). There is no common understanding of the foundation phases of start-ups and not all start-ups pass through all phases successfully (Hanks et al., 1994). Below, Kollmann's model is employed, which divides the start-ups based on the question "What happens to the idea over time" (Kollmann, 2009; Gochermann and Nee, 2019). Its classification of three stages fits well with the agile approach, which focuses on creating value for the customer through the product, i.e. through the idea:

- Early Stage: prototyping of the idea to determine the likelihood of success, development of a business model and preparation of market entry (Kollmann, 2009; Blank and Dorf, 2012).
- Expansion Stage: product launch, realisation of the sales and adaptation to market needs (Kollmann, 2009).
- Later Stage: the company has reliable income, a solid market position and high efficiency in core processes (Kollmann, 2009; Wegner and Koetz, 2016).

The main empirical basis of the cases analysed are expert interviews carried out with company founders and managers. In Table 4, key data of the participants and their companies is summarised.

Table 1: Overview of the participants and their companies of the interviews

Number of start-up	Type of start-up	Role of interviewee	Growth EMP	EMP	Business offering	Stage	Interview length
LS 1	B2B	Board member	200% in 2017 150% in 2018	12	Last Mile delivery with transport bikes	Expansion Stage	92 min
LS 2	B2B	Senior Account Manager	320% in 2017 180% in 2018	140	Digital freight forwarder	Later Stage	62 min
LS 3	B2B/ B2C	CEO	175% in 2018	7	First and Last Mile Delivery	Early Stage	80 min
LS 4	B2B	COO	275% in 2018	11	Logistics Software	Early Stage	57 min
LS 5	B2B/ B2C	CEO	325% in 2018	13	On-Demand Storage/ Warehousing Software/ Consulting	Expansion Stage	65 min
LS 6	B2B	CPO & CMO	125% in 2017 110% in 2018	22	Shipping Service Provider	Later Stage	81 min
LS 7	B2B	CEO	140% in 2017 143% in 2018	10	Logistical process optimisation with augmented reality	Expansion Stage	54 min
LS 8	B2B	CFO	330% in 2018	20	Sensor technol. and software	Expansion Stage	70 min
LS 9	B2B	Marketplace Supply Manager.	171% in 2017 150% in 2018	180	Online freight marketplace	Later Stage	79 min
LS 10	B2B	CBDO	150% in 2018	12	Supply chain financing	Later Stage	78 min
LS 11	B2B	General Manager	200% in 2018 200% in 2019	15	Digital log book	Expansion Stage	72 min
LS 12	B2B	Managing Director	70% in 2018	11	On-Demand Storage/Warehousing	Expansion Stage	47 min

The interviewees are selected to achieve theoretical replication (Boyce and Neale, 2006; Siggelkow, 2007; Yin, 2018), with the aim of covering a wide spread of applied agile methods to enable

generalisability of results. Literal and theoretical replications refer to case selection procedures that focus on predicting outcomes. Literal replication targets similar outcomes, while theoretical replication seeks dissimilar outcomes. In these interviews, similar organisations, but also organisations of different ages, sizes and with different products are selected to achieve literal and theoretical replication.

2.3.4. Data collection

Besides the interviews, published documents and articles are used as additional data sources. The sample consists of a convenience sample of founders and managers from ten German and two non-European logistics start-ups. Firstly, publicly available documentation as well as information from the start-ups' homepage was gathered. To better comprehend the use of agile methods, semi-structured interviews were then carried out with founders and managers of the logistics start-ups. These interviews were conducted by two interviewers in German and English and were held at the start-ups' offices to observe first-hand whether agile artefacts were visibly used. Altogether, twelve interviews were conducted in 2018-19. The interviews comprised four blocks of questions: (1) general information about the interviewee and the company, (2) comprehension of agility, relevancy for logistics start-ups in general and application in the specific logistics start-up, (3) success of the start-up in relation to its implementation of agile methods, and (4) the final conclusion where the interviewees were invited to provide additional information that they thought would be useful for further research. The questionnaire of the interviews can be seen in the appendix (see Appendix A.1., page 214).

2.3.5. Data analysis

To raise the robustness of these interviews, a two-layered analytic techniques was used (Eisenhardt, 1991; Yin, 2018). The first layer concentrates on “[...] priorities for what to analyse and why” (Yin, 2018, p.126). The theoretical basis (see Section 4.1. - Background, page 67) is used within this first layer to gain conceptual orientation and develop descriptions of the different cases. Yin suggests more specific analytical techniques for the second layer, such as logic models, time series analysis, explanations and cross-case analysis. After the interviews with the founders and managers have been completed, the transcription took place. To guarantee the quality of the transcription, the transcripts are verified by the interview partners. Subsequently, the data analysis is carried out by extracting the relevant information from the interview and sorting it by codes (Escobar-Sarmiento and Linares-Vasquez, 2012; Yin, 2018). Finally, the results of the cases are compared in a cross case analysis.

Based on Yin, the results of each case is tabulated in a uniform way to compare them and make juxtapositions visible (Yin, 2018).

The interviews had an average length of 70 min (median 71 min) and are transcribed. To triangulate and enrich the interviews, case-specific documents consisting of internal presentations and public announcements are analysed.

2.3.6. Objectivity, validity and reliability

Relevant tactics based on Yin are used to assure objectivity, validity and reliability and maintain the quality standard of the interviews (Yin, 2018). Yin suggests five dimensions to ensure objectivity, reliability and validity (see Table 5).

Table 2: Interview design to ensure validity and reliability

Source: (Yin, 2018)

Dimension	Strategy
Objectivity	Critical reflection of the researcher
Construct validity	Use multiple sources of evidence Maintain chain of evidence
Internal validity	Apply pattern matching
External validity	Use replication in interviews
Reliability	Provide and follow an interview protocol

Objectivity has the goal to achieve controllability. To establish controllability, the most critical variable is the researcher. The researcher recognized that the interviews' results may be influenced by one's position towards the research topic, the so-called power structure during the interview and the ideological context (Stuart et al., 2002; Patton and Appelbaum, 2003).

Construct validity is achieved by using multiple sources of evidence and maintaining a chain of evidence (Yin, 2018). Not only data from the interviews, which are the main data source, but also publicly accessible documents and information from the start-ups' homepages are utilised to paint a clear picture of the individual companies. Special attention is paid to the aspects below in order to maintain a chain of evidence: development of interview guidelines (see Appendix A.1., page 214) and preparation and use of a detailed data analysis process (tabularising data, using and showing relevant quotations) for the development of case company profiles. In this way, an external researcher can understand the process of this interviews. Pattern matching is employed to ensure internal validity. To attain external validity, which is often seen as a disadvantage of qualitative research (Newman and Benz, 1998), literal and theoretical replication logic is used. To guarantee the fifth

dimension, reliability, an interview protocol is implemented to standardise the process of data collection and enable repeatability.

2.4. Overview of the systematic literature review

SLR are described as a "replicable, scientific and transparent process" (Tranfield, Denyer and Smart, 2003, p.209). Scoping studies also pursue this goal. However, "systematic reviews are used to answer well-focused questions" (Cronin, Ryan and Coughlan, 2008, p.39), whereas scoping studies aim to provide a broad overview of the research field in a short period of time through mapping areas of research interest (Arksey and O'Malley, 2005, p.30). SLR is defined as a way of gathering evidence, enabling researchers to reach a common understanding and determine the current status of research in the field of interest (Wohlin, 2014). The aim is not only to conduct individual research studies, but also to build up knowledge by combining findings from different studies on the same topic. In this study, the SLR is used to gather and assess publications on the use of agile methods in established logistics companies and logistics start-ups published after 1999. The time restriction on papers is made as the Agile Manifesto, which is often seen as the starting point of the agile movement, is from 2001 (Beck et al., 2001) (see Section 4.2. – SLR, page 88). The agile methods, whose implementation is to be depicted in this study, are connected to the ideas of the Agile Manifesto and were only developed from around this point in time.

2.4.1. Research approach of the systematic literature review

To gather evidence and reach a common understanding between researchers in the field of research and its status, an SLR can be applied (Baker, 2000; Wohlin, 2014). As a research gap is identified based on the collection of related work (see Section 4.2.1.1. – Related work, page 88), this SLR is necessary to gather already existing research on the topic of established logistics companies, logistics start-ups and their use of agile methods and practices. It is intended to provide a framework for the subsequent research activities and to propose areas for further investigation (Brereton et al., 2007; Van Wee and Banister, 2016). To conduct the SLR, appropriate guidelines are followed, specifically the guidelines by Kitchenham and Charters (Kitchenham and Charters, 2007) and the guidelines by Durach et al. who focused on SLR in supply chain management (Durach, Kembro and Wieland, 2017). Based on these guidelines, this SLR is comprised of the following three main phases and associated stages:

Figure 8: Phases of the systematic literature review

Source: Own representation based on (Kitchenham and Charters, 2007)

In the first phase, the SLR is planned (see Figure 8). The need for the SLR is identified and a review protocol is developed and evaluated that describes the procedure of the SLR. In the second phase, the SLR is conducted. Relevant studies are searched for and selected, before they are evaluated and analysed. In the final phase, the results are discussed and a report is written. Details of the SLR are presented in section 7 (page 128).

2.4.2. Objective of the systematic literature review

In this study, the intention of the SLR is to investigate how other studies describe the use of agile methods and practices by established logistics companies and logistics start-ups. Relevant methods and practices are based on agile software development methodologies; thusly, approaches like the agile supply chain are not the main target of this SLR. Whether established logistics companies and start-ups use the same methods and practices is the focus of the investigation, as well as which benefits they want to realise with these methods and practices and what challenges they face.

The aim of the SLR is threefold:

- Clarify the state-of-the-art developments in the field of the application of agile methods by established logistics companies and logistics start-ups.
- Determine how the PhD study fits into the current body of knowledge.
- Answer the identified RQs from the literature perspective.

In contrast to the explorative interviews, not only publications on logistics start-ups are searched, but also publications focusing on established logistics companies. This allows a broader impression of the logistics industry in general. It also helps to identify whether the characteristics of logistics start-ups tend to be specific to the logistics industry.

2.4.3. Development of a research protocol

The research protocol is a detailed plan that defines the procedure for an SLR. It provides an overview of all underlying conditions and criteria applied in the selection of primary studies such as the quality

assessment of the publication. The research protocol underlying this SLR is designed based on the Kitchenham and Charters' guidelines for SLR (Kitchenham and Charters, 2007). To ensure accountability the research protocol is reviewed by two other researchers. The research protocol describes the main aspects of the research procedure, including data sources, search strategy, study selection, quality assessment, data extraction and data analysis (see Appendix A.2., page 217).

2.4.4. Search strategy of the systematic literature review

After the definition of the research objectives and the RQs, the research strategy is defined. Keywords are selected and combined into a search string. A search process is specified to reduce the number of papers found. To find keywords as criteria for the search, an iterative approach is taken. After the first definition of keywords that are also used for the scoping study (see Section 4.1, page 67), further keywords from relevant papers are extracted and alternative spellings and synonyms are subsequently identified. To optimise the search process, the keywords are refined after testing them in digital libraries and finding additional keywords in relevant papers. The final list can be found in Table 3. Using the keywords in plural made no noteworthy difference.

Table 3: Search keywords used

Topic	Subtopic	Search Keyword
Agile	Agile approach	Agile
	Agile methods	Scrum, Kanban, Extreme programming, Lean startup
Logistics	Service	Freight, Transport, Logistics service
	Logistics service industry	Third party logistics, Fourth party logistics, Logistics service provider, Supply chain
Companies	Established companies	Company, Firm
	Start-ups	Start-up, Start-up, Small medium enterprise, Venture

The keywords are then connected with Boolean operators to design the search string as follows:

Search string: ST = [Agile] + [Logistics] + [Companies]

In more detail, the search string appears as follows:

Search string: ST = (agile OR scrum OR kanban OR "extreme programming" OR "Lean startup") AND (freight OR transport OR "logistics service provider" OR "fourth party logistics" OR "Third party logistics" OR "Logistics service" OR "supply chain") AND (company OR firm OR start-up OR venture OR "small medium enterprise")

Included in the search space are digital libraries and conference proceedings. They are selected based on their research scope. As every digital library has its own characteristics regarding its search engines, the search string is adjusted for every library. Digital libraries are listed in alphabetical order. The details are documented separately (see Appendix A.2., page 217) and include the following information for each library (see extract Table 7):

- library name
- search strategy
- scope of the digital library
- date of search
- the adapted version of the search string

Table 4: Search space

Digital library	Search strategy	Scope	Date of search
ACM	abstract and keywords	Computing and information technology	09 January 2021
EBSCO	abstract, title and subject terms	Publications that focus on technology, natural sciences and economics from various publishing houses	06 February 2020
Emerald	abstract and keywords	Business, management, real estate economics and finance	10 January 2021
Google scholar	full text	As it is unclear which publishers are included in Google Scholar, it is used as a comprehensive addition to the other databases.	08 January 2021
IEEEXplore	abstract and keywords	Electrical engineering and computer science	07 January 2021
JSTOR	abstract, title and keywords	Academic journals in 75 disciplines including economics, engineering, management, technology, transportation	29 January 2020
Science direct	abstract, title and keywords	Sciences, economic and social science, and some arts and humanities titles	08 January 2021
SpringerLink	abstract and keywords	Sciences, economic and social science, and some arts and humanities titles	08 January 2021
Wiley	abstract and keywords	Sciences, economic and social science, and some arts and humanities titles	10 January 2021

At the first stage, a large number of papers is found (12,090 findings). To reduce the results, the search is conducted in several stages, as shown in Figure 9. Additionally, a reference search is used to find papers that cited the selected paper - a strategy referred to henceforth as “forward snowballing” - and papers that are in the reference list of the selected paper (backward snowballing) (Wohlin, 2014). Through snowballing, an additional 122 papers are found. 78 papers are found

through forward snowballing, and 44 papers through backward snowballing. For these papers, the search process is started at stage 3. At the end of this second search process, two further works are identified that are considered for data extraction.

Figure 9: The search process comprises six steps and snowballing
Source: Own representation

Comparing the results of this search, which is mainly based on the title, abstract and keywords of the publications, with the results of a full text search, a clear difference in the number of results becomes visible. Instead of the 12,090 papers found in this SLR in the first step S1 (see Figure 9), a full-text search finds 72,062 papers. As this number of results cannot be evaluated reasonably, this SLR is limited to title, abstract and keywords if possible in the different search engines.

2.4.5. Study selection

Studies are selected based on the search criteria described below, which are divided into inclusion and exclusion criteria. Inclusion and exclusion criteria aim to identify studies that provide direct evidence about the RQs. Three inclusion criteria are defined based on the RQs (see Inclusion criteria 4, 5 and 6 in Table 8). Since the objective of this work is to take up the international state of research, English language papers are the focus of this SLR (see Inclusion criteria 1 in Table 8). The time restriction on papers published after 1999 is made as the Agile Manifesto is from 2001 (Beck et al., 2001) (see Inclusion criteria 2 and 3 in Table 8). The agile methods, whose use is to be depicted in this research, are based on the idea of the Agile Manifesto and therefore were only developed from around this point in time. Furthermore, it is the goal of this work to reflect the current state of research

and not the development over time. Books and master theses are excluded (see Exclusion criteria 1 in Table 8). The aim is to find dedicated publications on the topic, which also have a good research quality and are peer-reviewed. Duplicates are considered only once (see Exclusion criteria 2 in Table 8). The last exclusion criterion ensures the research relevance to the RQs of this study (see Exclusion criteria 3 in Table 8).

These criteria are applied as follows at step three (see S3 – Apply selection criteria, Figure 9) of the search process:

1. The first three inclusion criteria have to be fulfilled
2. The selection criteria 4-6 are used as guideline for whether or not studies should be selected
3. Studies should be excluded if any exclusion criteria can be used

Table 5: Inclusion and exclusion criteria

#	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
1	Papers written in English	No full books, no master thesis
2	Papers published between 1999-2019	Papers with results that had been already published
3	Specific book chapter (published between 1999-2019)	Papers that were not focused on agile methodologies or whose focus moved away from agile methodologies
4	Papers presenting agile methods used in the logistics industry	
5	Papers presenting benefits logistics companies achieve through the use of agile methods	
6	Papers associated with challenges of the application of agile methods in the logistics industry	

At the end of the data extraction only thirteen papers are found that are relevant to this SLR. Two further publications are identified through snowballing. In total, fifteen papers are discovered and included in the SLR. It is verified that they not only contained relevant information but also fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Through the snowballing process, some authors who have more than one relevant publication are also discovered.

In order to evaluate how many German-speaking papers are excluded due to the restriction to English-speaking papers, the search is carried out on a trial basis in a digital library that also contains German language papers. 95 publications are found for step 1 (S1) (see Figure 9). The continuation of the SLR e.g. with German-speaking publications or other papers in further languages would be a possibility for broader research in the future.

2.4.6. Quality assessment

To assist data analysis, quality assessment criteria are used to evaluate the quality of the studies that passed the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The quality is evaluated based on the criteria elaborated in Table 9 (Schön, Thomaschewski and Escalona, 2017), for which a three-point Likert scale is used. The assessment criteria are based on the guidelines from Kitchenham and Charters and suggestions from Fink (Kitchenham and Charters, 2007; Fink, 2013). The list of suggested evaluation parameters is reviewed and appropriate questions are selected. A measurement scale is constructed since a “Yes”/”No” answer would have been misleading. Each of the five quality criteria is applied to evaluate the selected papers. Papers lacking a detailed description of the research process (QA2) or a description of the research objective (QA5) are not further included in the data analysis. Papers that do not validate their research idea (QA1), include a personal opinion (QA3) or are cited only rarely (QA4) are examined to determine if the research quality is not affected (see Appendix A.4., page 231).

Table 6: Quality assessment criteria

Item	Assessment criteria	Score	Description
QA1	Is the scientific idea validated?	-1	No, it is not validated
		0	Partially; only parts of the proposal are validated or it is validated in a laboratory
		+1	Yes, by a case study/survey/etc.
QA2	Does the publication present a detailed description of the approach?	-1	No, details are missing
		0	Partially; you need to read the references, if you want to use the approach
		+1	Yes, the approach can be used with presented details
QA3	Does the publication include a personal opinion piece or viewpoint?	-1	Yes, it does.
		0	Partially; since related work is explained and paper is set into a specific context
		+1	No, the paper is based on research
QA4	Has the publication been cited by other authors?	-1	No, no one cited the study
		0	Partially; between 1-5 articles cited the study
		+1	Yes, more than 5 articles cited the study
QA5		-1	No, aims are not described
		0	Partially; aims are described but are unclear

Item	Assessment criteria	Score	Description
	Has the publication a clear statement of the objective of the study?	+1	Yes, aims are well described and clear

2.4.7. Data extraction

Based on Kitchenham and Charters' guidelines (Kitchenham and Charters, 2007), an Excel spreadsheet is set up for data extraction. In this extraction form, the following quantitative and qualitative parameters are used.

Table 7: Overview on data extracted and need of the data to conduct the systematic literature review

Parameters	Data type	Benefit of data for the SLR
General information	Title, Authors, Publication date, DOI	Gathering of general information for recognition of the publication
Publication data	Journal/ conference, (Conference date) Publisher, Volume, Issue, Pages, Keywords, Abstract	Classification of the paper e.g. regarding age and quality
Research type	Research method (Development of a framework, Case study, Survey, Systematic literature review, other)	Understanding of the origin of the research data
Agile method	e.g. Scrum, XP, Kanban, Agile Manufacturing	Data used to answer RQ 1
Type of company	Established, Start-up	Comprehension of the context analysed
Company size	Number of employees	
Type of logistics (based on the classifications used in the identified journals)	Supply chain, Internal logistics, Freight, Inventory management, Logistics service provider, Urban logistics	
Company assets	Asset-based, Asset-light	
Addressed problems within companies	Problem 1, Problem 2,...	
Realised benefits	Benefit 1, Benefit 2,...	Data analysed to answer RQ2
Challenges with agile methods	Challenge 1, Challenge 2,...	Data analysed to answer RQ3

Parameters	Data type	Benefit of data for the SLR
Quality assessment criteria	Idea validation, Detailed approach, Personal opinion, Cited by others, Clear objective, Number of papers that cited the study	Dated collected to assess the publications' quality based on the SLR guideline
Personal assessment	Comments, Selection status (included/excluded)	Remark by author on the publication

During the data extraction process, it becomes clear that it is not always possible to excerpt data for all parameters because the studies are reported differently. Missing parameters are marked with “n/a” in order to complete the form anyway. Quantitative data is extracted, such as the publication channel and date, as is qualitative data, such as content and summaries (see Appendix A.3., page 226).

2.5. Overview of the Delphi method

An empirical and explorative approach is necessary to gather data and create knowledge on the use of agile methods in the logistics industry. In order to gather knowledge in previously unexplored areas, it is common to collect answers from experts (Dalkey and Helmer, 1963). Expert judgement techniques such as brainstorming, the Delphi method and nominal group techniques can be used for this objective. They enable a given number of experts to formulate and develop a common opinion on a research topic. Using brainstorming is a creative way to gather new and different views on a particular matter. It is therefore less suitable for an initial, exploratory collection of opinions on a research topic (Diehl and Stroebe, 1987). The nominal group technique is carried out in a convened expert group. A moderator structures the discussion of the expert group in order to find a solution to the problem of analysis (Carney, McIntosh and Worth, 1996; Torrecilla-Salinas et al., 2019). The nominal group technique involves the physical presence of experts, making it less feasible, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic. The Delphi approach uses questionnaires (see Appendix A.5., page 233) over multiple rounds and feedback loops to ascertain the opinion of the experts (see Section 5 - Delphi study, page 103). Compared to the other methods of expert judgement, the Delphi approach offers the advantage that it can be applied in cases where the sample is too narrow to assess the validity of the results with statistical methods (Rowe and Wright, 2001). To sum up, it can be stated that the Delphi approach is suitable and therefore selected to gather the views of experts. (Dalkey and Helmer, 1963; Linstone and Turoff, 2002; Diamond et al., 2014). The ultimate goal of this Delphi study was to find valuable insights from experts on the current use of agile methods and practices. Experts were selected systematically to ensure their deep extensive knowledge on agile methods. A

specific questionnaire was developed for each round to deepen the results from round to round (see Appendix A.5., page 233). Therefore, the Delphi study is called modified. The iterative approach allowed the researchers to refine the findings over several rounds and to react to unexpected answers given by the participants.

2.5.1. Research approach of the Delphi study

Originally, the Delphi method was used to reach a consensus within an expert group on the research topic. Various metrics such as Fleiss' Kappa (Fleiss, 1971) or Kendall's concordance coefficient (Legendre, 2005) are used for this purpose. However, recent studies show that even the definition of consensus is ambiguous (Diamond et al., 2014). The ultimate goal of this Delphi study is not to reach consensus but to find valuable insights on the current use of agile methods and practices (Robson, 2002). For this purpose, a questionnaire is adapted between the individual rounds in order to find responses to the RQs. Thus, the Delphi approach is modified (Dalkey and Helmer, 1963; Linstone and Turoff, 2002; Diamond et al., 2014) and used to carry out an iterative expert assessment process (Dalkey, 1969) to evaluate the use of agile methods and practices in established logistics companies and logistics start-ups. The questionnaire consists of qualitative questions as well as quantitative questions. In-depth insights can be obtained through qualitative, controlled feedback loops (Dalkey and Helmer, 1963; Fletcher and Marchildon, 2014), which could be reassessed in the following rounds with the use of quantitative questions and evaluated without distortion. Three complementary rounds are carried out to gather a comprehensive understanding of the perspectives of the panellists, who are experts in the fields of agility and logistics. The results of the previous rounds are analysed, summarised and forwarded to the experts in order to refine their views (Vijayasathy and Turk, 2012). The close involvement of a panel of experts who work in the field of IT in established logistics companies and logistics start-ups and who have extensive expertise in the use of agile methods ensures that the results of the Delphi study are close to reality. The Delphi study is carried out in four stages (see Figure 10)

Figure 10: Stages of the conducted modified Delphi study

Source: Own representation

Through the use of qualitative questions the research topic is explored (Patton, 2015). In the second stage, views of the experts are gathered to gain a deeper understanding from the perspective of

practitioners on the research topic. The third stage involves clustering the central theses of the experts to address the RQs. In the fourth stage, answers given by the experts are analysed in depth. The questionnaire combines qualitative questions with quantitative questions. Through qualitative, controlled opinion feedback, profound insights can be gained (Dalkey and Helmer, 1963; Fletcher and Marchildon, 2014), which can be assessed quantitatively and unbiased in the following rounds with quantitative questions. Feedback on the results of the preliminary rounds enables the experts' opinions to be refined (Vijayasathy and Turk, 2012).

2.5.2. Objective of the Delphi study

By surveying employees from established logistics companies as well as from logistics start-ups, the aim of this Delphi study is to collect data on the current use of agile methods. Therefore, three complementary RQs are created (see Section 3 - Interviews, page 56). In contrast to the explorative interviews, not only employees of logistics start-ups are interviewed, but also employees of established logistics companies. This allows a broader impression of the logistics industry in general. It also helps to identify whether the characteristics of logistics start-ups tend to be specific to the logistics industry.

2.5.3. Identification of related research approaches

To evaluate the need of a Delphi study in this research field related publications are analysed to verify the adequacy of the Delphi approach.

Related work

In the SLR, it is discovered that only few studies on the application of agile methods in the logistics industry exist (see Section 4.2. – SLR, page 88). The goal of this section is to decrease the research gap determined through the collection of opinions from experts. Expert judgement techniques can be employed for this objective. They enable a specific number of experts to formulate and produce a collective opinion on a research topic. Expert judgement techniques include, for example, brainstorming, the Delphi method and nominal group techniques. After comparing these three methods, it was decided that the Delphi method is the most suitable method for this study (see Section 2.5. – Overview of the Delphi method, page 34).

In order to validate whether the Delphi approach is an adequate method to address the RQs of this study, studies in the field of agility and studies in the field of logistics that use the Delphi approach are collected in order to evaluate the applicability of the Delphi approach in more detail. Table 21 shows an overview of the reported reasons for the selection of the Delphi approach. No Delphi study

that combined both research fields, logistics and agile methods, is found. Authors are listed in chronological order.

Table 8: Overview of Delphi studies in the field of agile methods and in the field of logistics

Author, Year	Aim of the study	Reason for the selection of the Delphi approach	Modification of Delphi approach
Akkermans et al., 2003	Determine supply chain management trends	Structured group communication process: individuals express effectively perspectives on complex issues Theory-building research approach that enables receiving feedback on views of other experts	None
Conboy and Fitzgerald, 2007	Review the current state of agile method tailoring	Reliable consensus through a group of experts Pooling the knowledge of a large group of experts to ensure a higher chance of coming closer to the truth Complex problems can often only be addressed by combining opinions Adaptable in its design	None
von der Gracht, Kauschke and Ruske, 2009	Energy efficiency and speed in the supply chain	Breaking the “bandwagon” and “halo” effects Strong inclusion of expert knowledge to develop systematically a consensus of expert views on prospective trends Experts can look at the views of their peers (anonymously) and potentially reconsider their own answers	None
Deschene, Don Gottwald and Clifford, 2016	Identify agile methods to increase acceptance of software security considerations	Separate interviewing of chosen experts Interviewing experts individually to guarantee anonymity, minimise the risk of group opinions and restrict the influence of dominating experts Structured, guided, iterative approach aimed at finding consensus on a particular research topic	None
Schön et al., 2017	Determine most important challenges in “Agile Requirements Engineering“	Anonymity eliminates the influence of other experts Iterative approach with controlled feedback Use of findings from earlier rounds to conduct subsequent rounds	Modification of the questionnaire between the rounds to clarify and refine results Reaching consensus was not the overall goal as this study aimed at finding valuable insights
Torrecilla-Salinas et al., 2019	Verify an agile framework with experts	Cheaper as only experts are involved which allows a smaller sample Gather perspectives of experts on new framework	Combination of Delphi method with statistical techniques

Analysing the related work, it can be stated that the Delphi approach seems to be applied especially in cases when anonymous and iterative research is needed to address complex problems.

Akkermans et al. use the Delphi approach in their study on future supply chain management, as it enables them to structure a group communication process, so that experts can give their assessments of complex problems and receive feedback from other experts during the study, for example via comments (Akkermans et al., 2003). It is also used as a theory-building research method.

Conboy and Fitzgerald seek to benefit from the fact that combining the answers of a large number of people gives a better chance to come closer to “the truth” (Conboy and Fitzgerald, 2007).

Von der Gracht et al. have designed their Delphi study in such a way that surveyed experts can immediately identify data trends and thus take into account the views of their colleagues (anonymously) to possibly rethink their own answers (von der Gracht, Kauschke and Ruske, 2009).

Deschene has chosen the Delphi method for her study on agile methods in relation to software security policies because it offers a qualitative, guided, and iterative approach to bring experts to a consensus (Deschene, Don Gottwald and Clifford, 2016).

Schön et al. have also chosen the Delphi approach in order to be able to proceed in an iterative way and to use the learnings from previous rounds (Schön et al., 2017).

Torrecilla-Salinas et al. use a modified Delphi study to deepen results found in the previous rounds to clarify and refine those findings iteratively (Torrecilla-Salinas et al., 2019).

Applicability of Delphi studies in the present research

These Delphi studies, carried out in the fields of logistics and agile methods, demonstrate that the Delphi approach can be employed to iteratively collect the opinion of experts. Advantages such as anonymity, controlled feedback between rounds and the use of insights from the preceding rounds are the reasons for choosing the Delphi approach. The following paragraph shows the main benefits of Delphi studies:

- Akkermans et al. benefit from the Delphi approach as it enables them to structure a group communication process with experts on a complex problem and it allows feedback from other experts during the study;
- Conboy and Fitzgerald use the Delphi approach to gather the opinions of many experts to create a realistic picture of “the truth”;

- Von der Gracht et al. profit from the possibility that experts identify data trends and simultaneously take into account the views of their colleagues;
- Deschene uses the advantage to achieve a consensus between the experts by using a guided, iterative, and qualitative approach to achieve consensus;
- Schön et al. benefit from the use of an iterative approach and deepen the results over several rounds. And finally,
- Torrecilla-Salinas et al. chose a modified Delphi approach to expand answers and find iteratively results that represent “the truth”.

According to my information, there is currently no qualitative study that examines the use of agile methods in logistics companies. Based on the identified research gap the Delphi study aims to find out what agile methods and practices are used by established logistics companies and logistics start-ups, why they are used, and what difficulties they encounter.

2.5.4. Description of the study design

The study is carried out in multiple successive rounds. Figure 11 provides an illustration of the process. In every round, a questionnaire is prepared and fine-tuned in five pre-tests together with experts from academia and industry. Subsequently, an email with an invite and a link to the online questionnaire is distributed to the participating experts. The results of the preceding rounds are utilised for the development of the subsequent questionnaires. The participants have two weeks to complete the questionnaire. Finally, the results are analysed with two additional researchers. The study is performed with German and English questionnaires. These are tested for consistency in advance. The English version of the questionnaires can be found in the Appendix A.6. (page 232)

Figure 11: Process of the Delphi study

Source: Own representation

All rounds of the Delphi study utilised Google Forms. Generally, it is agreed to use qualitative and quantitative questions with 7-point Likert items. It has proven to be the best choice to avoid interpolation (Finstad, 2010). In some cases a 5-point Likert item is used to reduce complexity for

the experts in the number of possible answers (Cummins and Gullone, 2000). In addition, the quality criteria proposed by Diamond et al. are considered (Diamond et al., 2014) to ensure the quality of this study. After the completion of each round a report presenting results of the previous round is sent to the participants (see Appendix A.6., page 255). Participants have the chance to engage in an online forum to both interact and discuss the results and provide immediate feedback to the researchers.

2.5.5. Questionnaire design

Three rounds of complementary activities are performed. The questionnaires for rounds 2 and 3 are developed after analysing the results of the preceding rounds. Details are provided below.

Round 1

The first round questionnaire consists of two sections. In the first section, information of a personal nature is requested, which is meant to assess the individual participants (summarised in Section 6.1., page 101). In addition, more formal data like size and age of the employing company is collected. Section two includes nine questions (see Appendix A.5.1., page 233), including some open-ended questions and some single/multiple-choice questions. The topics covered are as follows:

- Agile methods and practices applied (multiple choice)
- Manner of applying agile methods (e.g. in "pure form" or with adaptations) (single choice)
- Application frequency of agile practices (multiple choice)
- Initiator of and decision maker(s) on or for the use of agile methods and practices (multiple choice)
- Benefits of applying agile methods and practices (open question)
- Challenges in applying agile methods and practices (open question)

Learnings from Round 1

Results of the first round demonstrate that particularly in logistics start-ups several agile methods such as XP and FDD (see Section 5.3. – Implications of the findings, page 124), which are older or not as widely used as Scrum or Kanban, are applied more frequently than described in other studies, e.g., in the *State of Agile Report* (VersionOne, 2019). To further elaborate on this aspect, the second round addresses the question of which practices are used for which objective and how the methods are chosen for their application.

For logistics companies not only the use but also the scaling of agile methods is an important topic. This shows not only that the application of agile methods is extended on additional teams but gives

the impression that the logistics companies are satisfied with the use of agile methods. Also the scaling of agile methods might be an indication for the success and growth in general of the established logistics companies and the logistics start-ups. Based on these findings participants are asked in the second round how they chose agile methods and what agile practices they apply to realise certain benefits.

The results of the first round indicate as well that the logistics industry uses agile methods rather similar to other industries. Agile methods and practices used and benefits they plan to realise correspond to the results of the *State of Agile Report* where more than 1,000 experts from various industries worldwide participated. Looking at the challenges using agile methods established logistics companies and logistics start-ups face, differences become visible. Participants from established logistics companies rank challenges more or less similar to the experts that participated in the State of Agile survey. Logistics start-ups rank challenges higher that are connected to a lack of employees and to a lack of special roles such as the role of the product owner (see Section 5.3. – Implications of the findings, page 124).

The results of the first round demonstrate that agile methods are often customised to the companies' needs (see Section 5.3. – Implications of the findings, page 124). This adaptation of agile methods to the company's own specific circumstances is, according to the results, stronger than reported in the literature (Kähkönen, 2004; Fuchs, 2019). To gain an understanding of how agile methods are introduced and how long-established logistics companies and logistics start-ups set up their implementation, the following rounds focus more on the agile transformation process. The findings show that follow-up rounds are essential to respond to and enhance the insights from the first round.

Round 2

The questionnaire of the second round is developed based on the findings of the first round. The following topics are covered. The complete questionnaire can be found in Appendix A.6.2 (page 239):

- Criteria applied for the selection of agile methods (multiple choice)
- Practices applied to deal with challenges faced most frequently (described below) during round 1 and efficiency of the practices used
 - Changing internal and external requirements

- Changing priorities
- Acceleration of product delivery
- Improvement of communication between the customer and the IT department
- Increasing transparency on project risks and impediments
- Increasing product quality
- Decreasing project risk
- Increasing productivity of the team
- Approach used for the agile transformation process if applicable (multiple choice)
- Factors that influence the successful application of agile methods (multiple choice)

Although each question is designed as a multiple choice question, participants have the opportunity to elaborate on their answers after each question in a free text box that follows each multiple choice question.

Learnings from Round 2

In the second round, participants are inquired to identify which agile practices they employ to overcome the most frequently encountered challenges. Furthermore, participants are asked to rate the effectiveness of the practices in overcoming the challenges. The results show that although the effectiveness of the practices used is not rated as "high" for all practices, they are still employed to overcome the challenges (see Section 5.3. – Implications of the findings, page 124). This is an unexpected finding as agile methods are based on the aspect of continuous improvement. The effectiveness of agile practices used could be increased through improvements or the selection of alternative agile practices. In the third round, clarification is necessary for this finding. Based on the unforeseen findings the third round is used to challenge the agile methods selected and the way they are used.

Two participants from established logistics companies and one participant from logistics start-ups express that they are currently transforming and introducing new or other agile methods (see Section 5.3. – Implications of the findings, page 124). Overall, that shows that nearly as much participants from established logistics companies as participants from logistics start-ups plan to use (further) agile methods. Looking more closely indicates that two thirds of all participants from logistics start-ups used agile methods right from the beginning whereas only about one third of the participants from established logistics companies used agile methods from the outset.

Qualitative answers provided by the participants in free text fields are organised and integrated into the reports that are sent to the participants in between the individual rounds to reflect on the results of the first and second round. The reports are applied to feed back the results to the participants and allow room for a structured communication in an online forum.

Round 3

To enhance the gained knowledge of the second round the following aspects are included:

- Importance of the criteria applied for the selection of agile methods (multiple choice)
- Assessment of the utility of the applied agile methods (multiple choice)
- Planned application of further agile methods (multiple choice)
- Effects of the challenges faced using of agile methods (multiple choice)

The questions are all developed as multiple choice questions (see Appendix A.5.3., page 249).

Learnings Round 3

Even though participants state in the second round that the use of agile practices is not effective in every case to realise certain benefits, the third round shows that the participants do not plan to change the agile practice used. On the contrary, they prepare to introduce additional agile practices. This is a sign that the participants are convinced of the general benefits of agile methods and practices (see Section 5.3. – Implications of the findings, page 124).

The participants are asked about different topics in several rounds. Changing the question design leads to slightly different results. Modifying the question design aided in finding uncovered nuances in the results.

In the course of the three questionnaire rounds, the number of outliers does not decrease significantly. The aggregate reports of the individual rounds therefore do not lead to a significant alignment of the participants' answers.

In the so far rather under explored research field in question, partial responses can be given for all three RQs. Through the use of complementary rounds, RQs could be addressed in more detail, as it was feasible to react to unexpected results. The results show that saturation is achieved after three rounds as considerably fewer new insights were gained than in the previous rounds. Therefore, the Delphi study was terminated after the third round.

2.5.6. Objectivity, validity and reliability

Relevant tactics of Clark and Watson, Okoli and Pawlowski and Yin are employed to ensure validity and reliability and secure the quality standard of the Delphi study (Clark and Watson, 1995; Okoli and Pawlowski, 2004; Yin, 2018). They suggest five dimensions to ensure objectivity, reliability and validity (see Table 12).

Table 9: Delphi study design to ensure validity and reliability

Sources: (Clark and Watson, 1995, Okoli and Pawlowski, 2004, Yin, 2018)

Dimension	Strategy
Objectivity	Critical reflection of the researcher Incorporation of feedback of experts during the three rounds of the Delphi study
Construct validity	Use a simple random sampling for the selection of experts Feedback loops of results
Internal validity	Apply content analysis and survey techniques
External validity	Use replication logic and include experts with different roles from various kinds of logistics companies
Reliability	Document every process step Describe how interview rounds build on each other

Objectivity has the goal to achieve controllability of the results. To guarantee objectivity the researcher has to recognise that her own viewpoints possibly influence the development of the questionnaires. Pre-tests and the incorporation of feedback of the experts during the rounds aim to secure objectivity (Patton and Appelbaum, 2003).

Sending back the results of the precedent rounds to the experts for further assessment secures construct validity (see Appendix A.6., page 255) (Okoli and Pawlowski, 2004). For internal validity, specific attention is paid to the following aspects: content analysis and survey techniques. A detailed data analysis process (tabularising data, using and showing relevant quotations) is performed. Additionally, some aspects are questioned several times with changing instruments during the Delphi study to validate previous answers of the experts. To achieve external validity, replication logic is applied. Experts with different roles and from various logistics companies take part in the Delphi study. To realise the fifth dimension, reliability, every step of the process of the Delphi study is documented. After every round the most important findings are sent to the experts. It is described how the different rounds build on each other and how the questions are developed (see Section 2.5.5. – Questionnaire design, page 40).

2.6. Overview of the survey

After uncovering the research gap in the SLR and developing first insights in the Delphi study, the following step is to complement the research data with the views of further participants. In addition, it is examined whether the first results stand up to the assessments of a broader group of participants. Possible methods for quantitative research are for example experiments, observations and surveys. Experiments are especially used when variables can be controlled and changed to assess the existence of cause-and-effect relationships. In the research field of this study it is not possible to control variables as the data is not collected in a laboratory but in real life. The data is gathered from companies that have to act economically and cannot adjust scientific variables to facilitate data collection of researchers (Almeida et al., 2017). Observations monitor the objects of interest in real life. It would have been possible to collect data by observing procedures and processes in logistics start-ups. However, this approach is very time-consuming (Boyko, 2013; Almeida et al., 2017). Furthermore, collecting data from companies worldwide would not have been possible especially during the Covid-19 pandemic. The use of focus groups would also have been possible to question the results of the Delphi study. However, this would have been regionally limited. The advantage of the surveys was the participation of employees from logistics start-ups worldwide. Longitudinal studies offer a comprehensive picture of the development of the use of agile methods but are much more time-consuming than surveys. Surveys constitute an applicable solution: they can address participants worldwide and enable a relatively quick collection of data.

Online surveys are a standardised written version of the survey in which an online questionnaire is available to the participants for a limited period of time. The questions can be answered directly on the screen. Participants are either invited via web or personally contacted via e-mail. If existing e-mail address lists or databases of organisations can be accessed, it is advantageous to contact potential participants directly. The individual approach by e-mail can significantly increase the willingness to participate. Table 13 shows the main advantages and disadvantages of online surveys.

Table 10: Advantages and disadvantages of online surveys

Sources: (Kühl, Strodtholz and Taffertshofer, 2009, Schweiger and Beck, 2019)

Advantages	Disadvantages
Time and accuracy: the answers can be transferred to a data evaluation software without much risk of transmission errors and are thus available quickly	Anonymity of participants: not verifiable who fills in the questionnaire and how often
Validity: the validity can be enhanced by functions in the online questionnaire. e.g. setting of mandatory fields	Requirements: technical requirements such as a PC and internet access at the researcher and participant are necessary and influence the group of participants
Focusing on relevant questions: the questionnaire tool can use automatic filters to block questions or answer options that are not relevant for the participants	Costs: participants do not have a fixed time to complete the questionnaire and could then postpone it, forget it or miss the deadline.
Reachability of participants: the target group can be enlarged through the use of mobile phones and PCs, as participants who are difficult to contact can also be reached.	Questionnaire design: the many design options of the online questionnaire tool can become a source of error and affect the quality of the data.

In this study, the online survey is used to expand and deepen the findings of the Delphi study. To achieve this objective, a questionnaire-based online survey (see Appendix A.7., page 286) using guidelines from Alreck, Molléri and Kitchenham is designed (Alreck and Settle, 1995; Kitchenham and Pfleeger, 2008; Molléri, Petersen and Mendes, 2016).

2.6.1. Research approach of the survey

The survey tests statements derived during the Delphi study. The survey results in a comprehensive picture of the use of agile methods in real-life. For the online survey of this study, four stages are completed (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: Stages of the conducted survey

Source: Own representation

For the development of the survey questionnaire on the use of agile methods findings of the Delphi study are used. After the analysis of the results from the Delphi study, hypotheses are derived and

transformed into questions that can be used in the survey. The questionnaire is sent to employees of logistics start-ups worldwide. The responses of the participants are assessed and central aspects are abstracted to enable an overall evaluation of all findings of the SLR, the Delphi study and the survey.

2.6.2. Objective of the survey

The goal of this survey is to collect information on the current application of agile methods by questioning employees from logistics start-ups worldwide. In contrast to the Delphi study, only employees of logistics start-ups are surveyed to focus on their views.

2.6.3. Identification of related surveys

To evaluate the need for a survey, related surveys are analysed to verify the existence of a remaining research gap and to validate the methodological approach.

Related work

Publications that utilised surveys in order to analyse the practical use of agile methods are presented and briefly discussed in preparation for the development of the questionnaire and conducting of this survey. Table 23 shows an overview of these related studies. Authors are listed in chronological order. The aim of this overview is twofold: on the one hand, the survey is embedded in the research context of this study, while on the other, it shows that surveys are a useful tool for collecting information on the use of agile methods at large.

Table 11: Overview of surveys in the field of agile methods

Author, Year	Aim of the study	Summary of the results
Salo and Abrahamsson, 2008	Examine the use and usefulness of Extreme Programming and Scrum	This questionnaire-based survey research provides results from 35 projects from 13 software organisations of different sizes from a total of eight European countries. Overall, results show that 54% of the participants use XP whereas Scrum is only used by 27% of the participants. In most cases not the whole method, whether XP or Scrum, are used but rather single practices from XP or Scrum.
Chow and Cao, 2008	Critical success factors in agile software projects	Among agile professionals, a survey was conducted to gather data from 109 agile projects from 25 countries worldwide. Using multiple regression techniques results revealed that only 10 out of 48 hypotheses were supported. Three critical success factors for ASD projects were identified: Delivery Strategy, Agile Software Engineering Techniques, and Team Capability.
Azizyan, Magarian and Kajko-Mattson, 2011	Identify current agile tool usage and needs	This survey included 121 responses from 120 different companies in 35 countries. Managers as well as developers decide on the use of agile methods. Mostly Scrum and XP are used. Almost all of

Author, Year	Aim of the study	Summary of the results
		the agile project management tools applied support Scrum and XP and are used more by distributed teams than by collocated teams.
Laanti, Salo and Abrahamsson, 2011	Gather opinions on the impact of agile transformations	Answers from more than 1,000 respondents in seven different countries in Europe, North America, and Asia are covered in this survey. The results show that most respondents fully agree with the claimed benefits of agile methods such as increased product quality and transparency, earlier detection of defects, higher satisfaction and effectiveness, and increased autonomy and happiness within the team. 60% of the participants state that they would not return to the old way of working.
Pantiuchina et al., 2017	Use of agile methods in software start-ups	Findings from a large survey of 1,526 software start-ups display that speed related agile practices are used to a greater extent as compared to practices focusing on the increase of product quality. However, it needs to be noted that software start-ups using the Lean startup approach do not sacrifice quality for speed any more than other start-ups do.
VersionOne, 2021	Annual survey on the application of agile methods and practices worldwide	The survey included the views of 4,182 respondents with 1,382 complete survey responses collected. The application of agile methods increases each year, and the adoption of agile methods during the Covid-19 pandemic allowed numerous companies to remain in business. Compared to previous years, organisational culture is no longer one of the top challenges when introducing the use of agile methods.

For the search of related papers, Google Scholar and the keywords "survey", "agile methods", "quantitative method" and "Scrum" are used in various combinations. Five research publications that use surveys to explore the use of agile methods in software companies were found. No study looking at agile methods within the specific field of logistics or logistics start-ups is identified. In the following, reasons for the use of surveys are consolidated. Summaries of the studies and findings are presented in Table 23.

Salo and Abrahamsson use a descriptive survey. The intention is not to understand causal relationships, but to describe what proportion of the sample has a certain perception and how often certain events occur. Combining the answers of a large sample increases the chances of gaining a realistic picture of “the truth” (Salo and Abrahamsson, 2008).

Chow and Cao gather a large set of different views and perceptions through the implementation of a survey. A main benefit for them is that they are able to find answers to quantitative questions (Chow and Cao, 2008).

The study and survey conducted by Azizyan et al. achieves two objectives (Azizyan, Magarian and Kajko-Mattson, 2011): firstly, they collect objective statistics of the usage of agile tools and needs, and secondly, they aim to gain a deeper understanding of the specific tool features companies need by gathering comments in free text fields (Azizyan, Magarian and Kajko-Mattson, 2011).

Laanti et al. aim to collect practitioners' opinions on and experiences with agile methods. They want to understand which factors affect the satisfaction of stakeholders concerning adoption of agile methods. Laanti et al. have chosen to conduct a questionnaire-based online survey, as it is faster and reduces the human error rate as compared to other methods such as interviews. Online questionnaires are more accessible than a paper survey and the handling of the responses is also easier (Laanti, Salo and Abrahamsson, 2011).

To collect a large set of answers, Pantiuchina et al. have decided to use data from an online survey that was conducted between 2013 and 2014, from which, they gathered the responses of 1,526 participants. Pantiuchina et al. analyse the use of five agile practices and cluster them into five areas that are related to quality, speed and communication (Pantiuchina et al., 2017).

CollabNet (2021) conduct an annual survey on the use of agile methods and practices, their benefits, and challenges that occur during their application. Through the annual online surveys, views are collected from participants worldwide, and from them trends in the development of agile IT project management can be derived (VersionOne, 2021).

Applicability of surveys in the present research

The surveys presented above demonstrate that surveys are a suitable method to capture perspectives on the application of agile methods. Advantages such as anonymity, the collection of different views and the opportunity to mix qualitative with quantitative questions are some of the factors that lead to the use of surveys. The following paragraphs delineate the main benefits of surveys that are possibly helpful for the present research and how the studies conducted differ from the objective of the survey in this study:

- Salo and Abrahamsson use their survey to gather data that can be used to describe the usefulness of Scrum and XP realistically. They focused only on the software industry and not on the logistics industry;
- Chow and Cao profit from the application of a survey, as it allows them to gather a large sample. They collect data from software projects but do not explicitly focus on software

development in logistics start-ups. In their publication they do not state clearly from which industries the participants come;

- Azizyan et al. benefit from the survey conducted as they aim to gather the objective opinions of experts on their research topic. They focus only on software companies and do not consider the logistics industry;
- Laanti et al. chose a survey to benefit from fast online reaction times and to reduce manual process steps on the part of the researchers, minimising the human error rate. They include data from employees of only one large telecommunications company.
- Pantiuchina et al. use the advantages of the survey format to gather data online from more than 1,500 software start-ups. They do not include any logistics start-ups. And finally,
- CollabNet apply surveys because surveys allow them to collect data from experts worldwide on the use of agile methods and analyse trends every year with the help of the online surveys. However, all sectors are considered and no dedicated results for the logistics sector can be derived.

As far as I know, no qualitative or quantitative research has yet been conducted on the introduction of agile methods in logistics start-ups. Based on the identified research gap the survey aims to find out what agile methods and practices are used by logistics start-ups, why they are used, and what difficulties are encountered in their use.

2.6.4. Description of the survey design

In general, three main methods of data collection via questionnaire can be identified: personal interviews, telephone interviews, and online questionnaires (Alreck and Settle, 1995). The use of online questionnaires continues to become more popular (Nardi, 2018). Online questionnaires allow for digital data storage and immediate access to the data for the researchers, which allows them to analyse the collected data in real time, if necessary. Data no longer has to be entered manually into data bases, which also reduces the rate of human error (Nardi, 2018). Online questionnaires also increase speed and reduce costs (Salo and Abrahamsson, 2008). Response rates to online questionnaires are generally higher than for example data collection by mail (Alreck and Settle, 1995; Nardi, 2018). Some studies even show that the data quality of surveys in which participants are invited to participate via e-mail are equal or even superior to data gathered via mail or telephone (Coderre, Mathieu and St-Laurent, 2004; Nardi, 2018).

To collect the data used in this study, a questionnaire-based survey was sent to employees of logistics start-ups. The survey design allows for a descriptive analysis. The objective of the survey is to capture the perspectives of employees of logistics start-ups around the world on the use of agile methods (Oppenheim, 1992). Participants had four weeks to finish the questionnaire: two weeks before the deadline, a reminder was mailed to the survey participants as was suggested by Rea and Parker (Rea and Parker, 1997).

The questionnaire consists of two parts. The first section focuses on the organisational details of the participants, such as company size and age, roles of the participants and their level of expertise in the application of agile methods. The second section asks about the agile methods and practices applied, the anticipated benefits and challenges of applying agile methods, and the impact of applying agile methods on the success of logistics start-ups. In total, it comprised 12 multiple-choice questions and eight 7-point Likert questions (see Appendix A.8., page 295).

The questionnaire is pretested with a focus on content validity and readability: two academic experts as well as two practitioners from logistics start-ups supplied feedback to improve the survey, which was subsequently incorporated into the survey.

2.6.5. Non-response bias

4,176 possible participants were approached, 2,183 e-mails could not be delivered. This leaves 1,993 emails that were deliverable, but in total only 95 participants (4.7% of 1,993) filled out the questionnaire, and 228 (11.4% of 1,993) began filling out the questionnaire. It must be expected that the participants who finished the questionnaire have a positive perception of agile methods and practices and that a non-response bias (NRB) exists (Armstrong and Overton, 1977; Lambert and Harrington, 1990).

The larger the NRB is, the more complicated it is to generalise the results to a larger population. There are several ways to estimate non-response bias, e.g. comparison with known values for the population, extrapolation, and subjective estimates (Armstrong and Overton, 1977; Lambert and Harrington, 1990):

- Comparing the gathered results with known values of the overall population such as ages and the sizes of non-participating logistics start-ups can be helpful. A comparison to organisational values such as size, age, and growth might have been possible, but these are not the values that are the focus of this survey. For this study, a comparative approach is not

an alternative, as information on the use, benefits, and challenges of agile methods are not known values of the non-participating start-ups that can be used for comparison. Additionally, known values would have come from a different source which could have increased potential biases and differences in the data even more.

- Extrapolation methods can be used to extrapolate values of non-respondents based on the answers of participants who completed the questionnaire later, or after a reminder was sent out. Here the idea of extrapolation is based on the idea that the answers of so-called “late” respondents are more similar to those of non-respondents than to the answers of early respondents. This study consists of a rather small data set of 95 answers in total. Comparing the answers of “early” respondents with those of “late” respondents did not show significant differences using independent t-tests. Extrapolation was not used to decrease NRB.
- Subjective estimates are the third possibility for reducing NRB. One of the bases for subjective estimates is the “interest” hypothesis, based on the idea that participants who are more interested in the research topic will respond more often. The 228 participants who did not finish the questionnaire might have left the questionnaire at a question where their interest decreased. Looking at the results of the 228 participants, most of them left the questionnaire at the ninth question, which is about the level of adjustments applied to the agile methods used in the start-ups. It is in a matrix format and possibly included too many options for answers. The questionnaire design should have been easier to understand in order to receive more valuable answers and more completed questionnaires in total. Additionally, the ninth question is followed by another question in matrix format, which may have decreased the interest of the participants even more.

Overall, it can be assumed, that the participants who finished the survey have a more positive perception towards the use of agile methods and practices than a more generalisable, larger population likely does.

2.6.6. Objectivity, validity and reliability

Relevant tactics of Nardi, Alreck and Settle are used to assure validity and reliability, and to secure the quality standard of the survey (Alreck and Settle, 1995; Nardi, 2018). They suggest five dimensions to guarantee objectivity, reliability and validity (see Table 15).

Table 12: Delphi study design to ensure validity and reliability

Sources: (Alreck and Settle, 1995, Clark and Watson, 1995, Okoli and Pawlowski, 2004, Nardi, 2018, Yin, 2018)

Dimension	Strategy
Objectivity	Participants are answering the questions on their own Standardised procedure for data evaluation
Construct validity	Develop questionnaire based on findings from SLR and Delphi study
Internal validity	Guarantee anonymity of participants Use Likert scales instead of cardinal numeric values
External validity	Invite employees from logistics start-ups worldwide to participate
Reliability	Participants take part in the survey out of intrinsic motivation Describe how the data is analysed

To guarantee objectivity, the online-based survey offers several advantages. Ideally, the participants are on their own when filling out the questionnaire so that they are not influenced by their environments. Additionally, data collected online is recorded and analysed in a standardised way, so the error rate is minimised as no manual transmission needs to be carried out. Construct validity is achieved, as the questionnaire is developed based on findings of previous studies (SLR, Delphi study). Internal validity is ensured through the anonymity of the participants: they do not have to publish their origin and the disclosure of e-mail addresses is voluntary. To simplify the answering of the questions, Likert scales are used so that the participants do not have to estimate by using cardinal numerical values that can be more accurate in other contexts. Replication logic is applied to secure external validity. Participants from logistics start-ups worldwide take part in the survey. Reliability can be realised through the intrinsic motivation of the participants; as no one forces the participants to answer the questionnaire, it is probable that responses to the questions are genuine and that answers are consistent. In addition, section 3.6.6. describes the clusters according to which the data are analysed.

2.7. Consolidation of the data gathered

The “heart” of this study is the framework. Based on the focus that is set through the interviews, the theoretical findings from the SLR, the empirical findings from the quantitative and qualitative data extraction from the Delphi study and the survey, the aim was to develop a practical framework (Ekins et al., 2003; Smith and Colgate, 2014).

The four studies (interviews, SLR, Delphi study and survey) are deliberately chosen in order to develop a framework based on the results. The connection of the studies to the framework is presented below:

- The interviews serve as the basis for the entire work. The RQs that are formed based on the results of the interviews are answered in all subsequent studies and these answers are consolidated in the framework. The seven dimensions of the framework are based on the RQs.
- The SLR contributes to the framework from the theoretical point of view: some specifications from the identified papers are part of the framework. The questions of the Delphi study and the survey were substantially influenced by the results of the SLR.
- The Delphi study starts to close the research gap and provides first answers from the perspective of practitioners. Through the Delphi study, the survey questionnaire could be developed in a targeted way so that the results are relevant for practitioners.
- Finally, the survey collects perspectives from a large number of logistics start-ups worldwide and allows the derivation of a framework. By using the Delphi study and survey, the perspectives of German start-ups can be compared with logistics start-ups worldwide. In addition, the survey can be used to verify the results of the Delphi study.

2.8. Conclusion

This chapter provides the background for understanding the methodology of this study. In the first step, the overall research design is presented. Afterwards, the methods that are selected based on the research design and their specifics are illustrated in this chapter. For each of the studies that are conducted within this study, a general overview is given, the reasons for the selection of the methods are explained and details of the methodological approach are described. Results of the individual studies can be found in the following chapters (see Section 4, 5, 6 and 7). The results of the studies are consolidated in one framework (see Section 7 – Framework, page 155). In the next chapter the approach and results of the interviews are illustrated.

3. Interviews

In the previous chapter, the methodology and the research design of the conducted studies are described. The aims and benefits of the selected research methods are explained together with the research approaches. In this chapter, the results of the interviews are presented in more depth. As described in the methodology chapter, interviews are used as exploratory tool to evaluate the relevance of the research topic. Interviews with employees of logistics start-ups are conducted in order to gain an understanding of the practical use, the need and the benefits of agile methods in logistics start-ups. Furthermore, the results of these interviews are used to derive the RQs of this study (see Section 3.3.1. – Implications for theory and practice, page 64).

3.1. Placing the interviews in the context of existing research

To situate the interviews in the context of existing publications and to develop the interview guide, publications that analyse the implementation of agile methods in start-ups are evaluated.

3.1.1. Related work

Before conducting the interviews, a closer look is taken on related publications to gain a first impression whether the application of agile methods has positive effects on start-ups and the logistics industry. There are related studies in the literature that investigate whether start-ups apply agile methods and if the implementation of agile methods enhances business success through the skills to cope with fast-changing customer expectations, uncertainties in the business model and complex technological decisions (Paternoster et al., 2014; Nirwan and Dhewanto, 2015; Gunasekaran, Subramanianm and Papadopoulos, 2016; Ghezzi and Cavallo, 2020). However, no specific article on logistics start-ups was found. Therefore, one publication that performs an SLR on agility in the logistics industry is included to gain an understanding on the importance of agility within the logistics industry. Table 16 shows the related publications. Authors are listed in chronological order.

Table 13: Overview of studies in the field of start-ups, logistics and agile approaches

Authors, Year	Aim of the study	Research method	Reported use of agile approaches of start-ups/ of the logistics industry
Paternoster et al., 2014	Assessment of software development in start-up companies	Systematic mapping study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agile methods are the most viable processes for start-ups • Accept change • Lightweight processes • Iterative, incremental approach • Fast releases • IT follows the business strategy • Culture that embraces failure • Agile method: Lean startup, Extreme Programming (XP), Scrumban • Agile practice: Minimum viable product (MVP), pair-programming, evolutionary workflows
Nirwan and Dhewanto, 2015	Analysis of barriers in implementing the Lean startup Methodology in an Indonesian B2B start-up	Case study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agile method: Lean startup • Agile practice: agile testing, learning cycles, early customer interaction, pivot, MVP, iterations, customer testing
Gunasekaran et al., 2016	Evaluation of information technology for strategic advantage within logistics and supply chains	Systematic literature review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supply chain agility • Strategic advantage through adaption, alignment and agility • Rapid response to short term alterations in the up- and downstream supply chain • Agility is linked to business and IT performance • To become agile, firms need to invest in IT
Mansoori, 2016	Assessment of the impact of the Lean startup method on entrepreneurs and start-ups	Case study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agile method: Lean startup • Agile practice: experimental learning, feedback loops, hypothesis testing, adaption
Ghezzi and Cavallo, 2020	Assessment of agile Business Model Innovation and Lean startup approaches in digital start-ups	Multiple case study	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agile method: Lean startup, Scrum, Feature-driven-development • Agile practice: customer centricity, feedback loops, MVP, upfront testing, sprints

The analysis of the related works shows that two different research approaches are applied. On the one hand, Paternoster et al. and Gunasekaran et al. use available evidence in published research to

describe the use of agile methods. Nirwan and Dhewanto, Ghezzi and Cavallo and Mansoori apply (multiple) case studies to explore the use of agile methods.

The results of Paternoster et al. were already published in 2014. The case study by Nirwan and Dhewanto and Mansoori released in 2015 and the multiple case study by Ghezzi and Cavallo released in 2018 confirm the theoretical results of Paternoster et al. For start-ups, the application of agile methods can be very beneficial. Start-ups profit from the lightweight processes, transparent communication and fast releases. This allows them to respond to rapidly changing situations. The biggest challenge for start-ups is adapting the product to the market. The Lean startup method (Ries, 2011), which includes MVP and fast feedback cycles, has proven expedient in the interviews.

No publication specifically intended for logistics start-ups was discovered. For this reason, the SLR by Gunasekaran et al. from 2016 is incorporated in this section. This publication demonstrates that agility also plays a role in the logistics industry. However, it needs to be mentioned that the agile supply chain described by Gunasekaran et al. differs from the agile project management methods that are the focus of this study. This difference is described in section 2.2 (page 17) where different areas of agility are distinguished.

3.1.2. Necessity of exploratory interviews

The studies identified in the areas of start-ups, logistics and agile methods confirm the relevance of agile methods both for start-ups and for the logistics industry. However, no study could be found that looks at logistics start-ups. As the logistics industry faces other preconditions than for example the software industry a research gap is identified. To the best of my knowledge there is no existing publication focusing on the use of agile methods by means of a qualitative study with founders and executive managers of logistics start-ups. Based on the identified research gap the interviews are used to identify the agile methods used by logistics start-ups by gathering views from twelve companies in the field.

3.2. Interview results

This section shows and discusses the results from the cross-case analysis of the data collected from the participants.

3.2.1. Definition of agility

Using an open question format the interviewees are asked what they understand under the term “agility”. Figure 13 demonstrates that the comprehension of the interviewees about the concept of agility covers different areas.

Figure 13: Understanding of agility of the interviewees

Source: Own representation

Three different clusters could be derived from the analysis of the participants' answers. The different views were assembled according to the aspects “Individual attributes”, “Practices” and “Objective”. The three aspects are developed based on the Agile Manifesto where they are used to describe fundamental specifics of the agile approach. The “Objective” cluster contains the targets that the participants want to achieve through the use of agile methods. These aspects are the motivation for the use of agile methods. The “Practice” cluster contains concrete practices or methods (here Scrum and Kanban) that are named by various authors and are stated by the participants. The “Individual attributes” cluster collects aspects that the participants name as prerequisites for the use of agile methods. It is essential to understand that some terms, such as "Focus on customer requirements" and "Use Scrum or Kanban" were named several times, while the other terms were mentioned only once.

3.2.2. Examples of agility and application of agile methods in the logistics start-ups

The interviewees are asked for examples of their own agility such as agile methods and practices used. Figure 14 indicates that the examples of the interviewees cover different areas.

Figure 14: Examples of agility in the interviewed start-ups

Source: Own representation

These examples are sorted according to the aspects “Processes and organisation”, “Culture” and “Communication”. The three aspects are derived from the Agile Manifesto and describe fundamental characteristics of the agile approach. The potential need to adapt/pivot the business model, the importance of using core values, the visualisation of the common goal and the necessity of frequent communication are stated multiple times.

3.2.3. Necessity of agility for logistics start-ups

When interviewed about the necessity of agility for logistics start-ups, the interviewees confirm that agility is an important characteristic for logistics start-ups, which also involves the mindset of founders and employees. One interviewee outlines that start-ups and agility cannot be separated: a start-up needs to be agile. Other interviewees state that agility is not only important for logistics start-ups, but for all start-ups in general, as start-ups still need to explore their business model. One respondent states that agility is not the most important aspect for start-ups: for larger and longer established companies agility is more crucial than for start-ups.

3.2.4. Comparison of the application of the most important agile methods

These interviews investigate which agile methods and practices are used by the logistics start-ups questioned. In advance, a systematic search is made for scientific models that seek to assess the level of agility of companies. The agile practices used in these models as indicators of agility are compared and ranked in terms of their frequency of occurrence (Lin, Chiu and Chu, 2006; Escobar-Sarmiento and Linares-Vasquez, 2012; Jalali, Wohlin and Angelis, 2014). In these multiple case studies, the interviewees are asked which of the most common agile practices they apply. If an interviewee states that they only use a practice partially/irregularly, this practice is not taken into account, as agile practices only bring great benefits when used regularly (see Figure 15).

Figure 15: Application of agile practices in the interviewed logistics start-ups

Source: Own representation

The practice used most often by the logistics start-ups are the prioritisation of the backlog which is followed by self-organised team, transparent process control, use of user stories and hypothesis testing.

3.2.5. Effects of agility on the cooperation between the colleagues

Agility has an impact not only on employees in their daily interaction, but also on the requirements and selection of new employees. One interviewee states that since close cooperation and constant communication are becoming even more essential at the time of this research (Jin et al., 2017), “it is important to recruit new employees who fit best into the “agile” team”¹. The influence of agility on potential conflicts between the employees was explained in particular. On the one hand, more

¹ Some quotes were translated by the author for interviews not conducted in English.

conflicts arise due to the higher decision-making power of the employees, but on the other hand, these can be resolved more quickly and thus lead to fewer escalations.

3.2.6. Application and improvements through retrospectives

Interviewees are questioned about the use of reflective meetings, so-called “Retrospectives” as “Retrospectives” represent one of the main ideas behind the agile approach. “Retrospectives” allow employees to reflect systematically and enable empirical learning. All interviewees of the logistics start-ups affirm to perform “Retrospectives”, where they gather lessons-learned and optimise the existing processes. Nine of the twelve start-ups do not perform these “Retrospectives” regularly or do not include all employees but only the team leaders. However, all interviewees are able to apply the learnings from the “Retrospectives”.

3.2.7. Measurement of success

Employees are interviewed how they measure the success in their logistics start-ups. Most interviewees explain that turnover and the number and the development of customers is an important factor for their evaluation of success (see Figure 16).

Figure 16: Factors used to measure success in logistics start-ups

Source: Own representation

When differentiating between so-called "asset-based" and "asset-light" logistics start-ups, it is noteworthy that in the case of the "asset-based" logistics start-ups, success is also strongly connected to the physical assets, e.g. the transport vehicles. In comparison, "asset-light" start-ups are more

interested in the number of users of their "light" assets such as IT platforms, their market share and their ability to digitise the logistics industry. Asset-light logistics start-ups include key figures such as turnover growth and employee growth in their measurement of success. It is striking that for "asset-light" start-ups with fewer than 50 employees, surviving itself is also an essential factor. In addition, three start-ups state that a success factor they value (even) more than business growth itself is sustainable and healthy growth. One participant from a more mature start-up states that the level and growth of efficiency are also important.

3.2.8. Success rate

The interviewees are requested to evaluate their success compared to the success of competitors. The aim of this question is to discover whether agility is a crucial competitive factor. If so, agile logistics start-ups should be more successful than their competitors in terms of survival, profit and economic growth. However, it does not necessarily imply that a successful logistics start-up is agile. The causes of success may also be found elsewhere. Nevertheless, some respondents in these interviews either do not rate their start-ups as stronger than their competitors or cannot compare themselves to them for various reasons. Two respondents who rate themselves as less successful than their competitors are not the participants with the least adopted agile practices. Otherwise, three respondents indicate that they are more successful than their competitors because of the adaptability of their business model. One asset-based and two asset-light start-up respondents state that their competitive advantage is based on the solution they have designed, which can respond more flexibly to future changes than their competitors' products, allowing them to adapt in an agile way. One way to deepen this study would be to measure the agility of logistics start-ups in depth and determine their success based on quantitatively measurable factors.

3.2.9. Relationship of agility and success

All interviewees confirm the relationship between agility and success even though the interviewees rate the relationship differently in strength. One interviewee states, that a start-up cannot survive without being agile. Another interviewee explains contrarily that agility was not the most important factor that determines the success of start-ups. Another interviewee stated that even though agility was important, it was not as important as a functioning and experienced team.

3.2.10. Development of employees and revenue

Eleven of the twelve start-ups grow in terms of employees at the point of time of the interview. The twelfth start-up is interviewed just before a fundamental pivot in their business model takes place. Because of this pivot, the start-up had lost two of its four founders at the time of the interview, but

plans to continue to pursue the new business model with five new employees. Regarding turnover, all start-ups except the start-up that was about to pivot have rising turnover. Some start-ups are on the verge of breaking even in the next few months and others report that turnover is following a positive curve that is steepening and eventually becoming a "hockey stick" curve.

Taking the results back to theory, it can be seen that the logistics start-ups questioned are more or less proactive, reactive or inherently able to deal with change and that this ability was rated as essential. It became apparent that they follow the agile values (see Section 4.1.1. – Agile methods and practices, page 68) in varying degrees. Overall, the interest of the participants and their use of agile methods confirms the relevance of the research topic.

3.3. Implications of the findings and limitations

In the following, the implications of the findings are presented.

3.3.1. Implications for theory and practice

The interviews result in:

- A list of parameters that are important for start-ups when defining agility,
- A list of agile methods and practices applied by logistics start-ups,
- A list of parameters applied by logistics start-ups to measure success,
- A first indication about the relationship of agility and success of start-ups.

Different points of view from the interviewees are expressed: Some explain that agility is the foundation of success, others describe, that agility is necessary but not the most important success factor. It is interesting to note that one respondent who does not rank agility as a very important success factor also applies agile practices extensively in his logistics start-up. It is striking that nine out of twelve respondents confirm that they do not conduct regular reflection meetings, so-called "Retrospectives", although these are a core element that should enable the continuous improvement of processes and interactions in organisations (Schwaber and Beedle, 2002). Moreover, the degree of agility seems to depend on the size of the logistics start-up, as communication and the involvement of all employees, which was understood as a core feature of agility, is rated as easier in smaller start-ups. Other respondents state that the larger the start-up becomes, the more important it is to invest in the application of agile methods to organise internal processes.

Overall, the explorative interviews validates the relevance of agile methods in logistics start-ups. This confirms the necessity of the research topic and enables the development of the following three RQs:

1. What agile methods and practices do established logistics companies and logistics start-ups use?

The aim is to find out what agile methods and practices are used in logistics start-ups and in established logistics companies.

2. What benefits do established logistics companies and logistics start-ups realise with agile methods?

In the interviews it is found out that the use of agile methods and practices is considered beneficial for logistics start-ups. The aim is to evaluate what exactly the benefits of using agile methods are.

3. What challenges do established logistics companies and logistics start-ups face concerning the adoption of agile methods and practices?

The participants of the interviews express that they pay particular attention to the mindset of their employees when selecting them (see Section 2.3.5., page 24), so that they can cope with the rapid changes in the start-up. The third RQ aims to find out what other challenges logistics start-ups face.

3.3.2. Limitations of the interviews

This research has certain limitations. The first limitation is that only a small number of interviewees from mainly German companies participated. In addition, only managers and founders took part in the interviews. This may lead to a one-sided view. The point of view of other employees with different roles might differ. These first two limitations need to be kept in mind when looking at the gathered data. However, these interviews are an exploratory approach to get a first overview. In-depth studies should include perspectives from other employees with other roles and backgrounds.

The third limitation is related to the difficulty of evaluating the understanding and expertise of the interviewees with regard to agility and agile methods. The agile approach is closely related to an agile mindset, which is difficult to evaluate.

In order to verify the expertise of the participants, a self-assessment took place during the interviews. In addition, the personal conversations during the interviews allowed the researchers to verify the expertise of the interviewees. Since the assessment of expertise was undertaken from two sides, the participant herself and the researchers, the limitation could be reduced.

3.4. Conclusion

The results of interviews on the application of agile methods and practices in twelve logistics start-ups is presented to validate the need for further research. The contributions of the interviews are threefold. First, it shows the relevance of agile methods for logistics start-ups. Second, it allows a first explorative comparison on the way logistics start-ups organise themselves and deal with a high level of insecurity towards their future business model. Third, it gives an indication that due to the relevance and the paucity of existing literature on the research topic further research needs to be performed. The interviews allow the development of the RQs. The following studies, the SLR, the Delphi study and the survey aim to answer the RQs.

4. Theoretical background and literature review

The previous chapter presented the results of the interviews, validated the need for in depth research and derived three RQs. This chapter consists of two sections, the scoping study and the SLR. The goal of the scoping study is to provide necessary definitions and descriptions to present the state of the art of the research field based. After discussing how the information from the literature is collected in the first step, definitions and descriptions of agile methods, agile practices, logistics companies and logistics start-ups follow. The presentation of these definitions serves to establish a common understanding of the terms within this study. The SLR presented in the second section aims to find answers to all three RQs. Its objective is to find out how the use of agile methods and practices by established logistics companies and logistics start-ups is described in literature.

4.1. Scoping study

An initial literature review was conducted to gather necessary data and to create a common understanding for the research topic. For this scoping study, a narrative approach was taken. The objective of narrative scoping studies is to describe the investigated area qualitatively (Huff, 2008, p.169). Pieces of information from selected sources such as publications of scientific value are summarised (Cronin, Ryan and Coughlan, 2008, p.38). Due to the rather open and flexible procedure, a limitation of the narrative literature review is that it may be not as comprehensive as SLR. However, by selecting at least two qualitative databases, searching with search terms and using selection criteria, the quality of narrative literature reviews can be guaranteed (Green, Johnson and Adams, 2006, p.107). The research field (see Section 1 – Introduction, page 1) contains two aspects that require definitions: agile project management methods and logistics companies. In this study, the terms “agile project management methods” and “agile methods” are used synonymously. For the purpose of simplicity, only “agile methods” are used in the following. The objective of this narrative approach is to gather available knowledge on agility, agile methods and the logistics industry to establish a common and comprehensive understanding of the research topic. Therefore, the scoping study includes information on the following two aspects, as stated above in the research objective of this chapter:

1. History and definition of agility and agile methods
2. Definition of established logistics companies, logistics start-ups and IT departments and projects of logistics companies

In this narrative literature review, Google Scholar, SpringerLink and Elsevier are used. Search terms were “agility”, “agile methods”, “logistics” and “start-ups”. Only publications published in journals or conferences using peer-review processes are selected as sources to define the terms “agility”, “agile methods”, “logistics companies” and “logistics start-ups”.

4.1.1. Agile methods and practices

In this section, it is described how the term agility is defined in the literature and what different types of agility exist. So far, there is no uniform definition of agility in research and the term has different meanings in the individual areas of application within (logistics) companies. In this chapter, to understand the origin of agility in the logistics industry, different types of agility such as “agile supply chain” but also “agile software development methods” are described, and how these types of agility have evolved over time is explained and discussed. The chapter concludes with a detailed description of software development departments and projects in logistics companies, as the application of agile methods in the IT departments and projects of logistics companies is the focus of this study.

4.1.1.1. Different areas of agility

The concept of agility has evolved since the 1940s from one that encompasses flexibility and leanness to one that is value-based, even though the terms “agility” and “lean” were coined only in the 1980s (Ohno and Bodek, 1988; Förster and Wendler, 2012). Agility focuses not only on customer value, but also on individuals, cooperation and interaction to achieve flexibility and leanness (Conboy, 2009) and depends strongly on the way all employees think (Beck et al., 2001). At the time of this study, the concept of agility is a multifaceted concept and is still interpreted in research and practice in many different ways (Conboy, 2009). Conboy and Fitzgerald provided a general definition of the term and describe agility as “the ability of an entity to proactively, reactively or inherently embrace change in a timely manner, through its internal components and its relationships with its environment” (Conboy and Fitzgerald, 2004, p.39). They described the principle values of agile process models, willingness to change and cooperation as the most important (Cohn, 2009). Qumer and Henderson-Sellers deepened this definition with different angles of agility such as “nimbleness, suppleness, alertness, responsiveness, swiftness and activeness” (Qumer and Henderson-Sellers, 2006, p.122). Various other authors use the facets “flexibility”, “speed”, “leanness”, “learning” and “responsiveness” (Wong and Whitman, 1999; Boehm and Turner, 2003; Conboy and Fitzgerald, 2004). In this study, agility is conceived as a concept that seeks to attain the attributes flexibility, speed, leanness, learning and responsiveness through the capability to deal with change in a proactive,

reactive or inherently fast way. These attributes are reflected in the agile methods that are the focus of this work (Beck et al., 2001; Conboy, 2009). An overview of the attributes used by different authors can be seen in Table 1. Authors are listed in alphabetical order.

Table 14: Attributes used to describe agility

Sources: (Ohno and Bodek, 1988, Wong and Whitman, 1999, Beck et al., 2001, Boehm and Turner, 2003, Qumer and Henderson-Sellers, 2006, Cohn, 2009; Conboy, 2009, Sarker and Sarker, 2009, Pikkarainen and Wang, 2011, Förster and Wendler, 2012, Lindsjörn et al., 2016)

Author, Year	Criteria used to describe agility									
	Flexibility	Lean-ness	Swift-ness	Active-ness	Customer value-driven	Empirical approach	Focus on employee satisfaction	Focus on cooperation	Focus on communication	Depending on employees' mindset
Beck, 2001	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Boehm and Turner, 2003	x	x		x		x		x	x	
Cohn, 2009	x				x	x	x	x		
Conboy, 2009	x	x			x	x	x	x	x	
Conboy and Fitzgerald, 2004	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Förster and Wendler, 2012	x	x			x			x	x	x
Lindsjörn et al., 2016	x		x	x	x		x	x		x
Ohno and Bodek, 1988	x	x			x					x
Pikkarainen and Wang, 2011	x		x	x	x		x	x		
Qumer and Henderson-Sellers, 2006	x	x				x				
Sarker and Sarker, 2009	x		x	x	x		x	x		
Wong and Whitman, 1999	x	x				x				

At the time of this research and especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, many industries are facing unexpected changes, which can affect customer requirements, cooperation with suppliers and

partners, but also internal alterations (Ratten, 2021). There are different areas of agility such as “Enterprise agility” and “Agile supply chains” because requirements vary between different areas of application. In this study, areas of agility are understood as the variety of agile approaches used in different business areas. In this section, a closer look is taken at areas of agility that are relevant for logistics companies and their associated processes. Agility in software development is considered as well, as it is due to the digitalisation increasingly relevant for logistics companies nowadays. Some commonalities become apparent when looking at the origin of the agile supply chain and agile software development methods (Kettunen, 2009). In the field of logistics agility is not limited to one area but “can be addressed in different business competence areas”, such as (Huang and Nof, 1999; Beck et al., 2001; van Oosterhout, Waarts and van Hillegersberg, 2005; Bottani, 2009; Kettunen, 2009; 2012; Holcomb and Gligor, 2012; Gunasekaran, Subramanianm and Papadopoulos, 2016):

- Agile software development (ASD)
- Agile manufacturing
- Agile supply chain
- Enterprise agility
- Agile organisation
- Agile business model

Below, these terms are explained in more detail. The definitions of the terms can overlap to some extent, as they all pursue the goal of allowing companies to react more flexibly to changes. However, the approaches of the individual areas differ.

Figure 17: Agile areas and their relationships

Source: Own representation based on (van Oosterhout, Waarts and van Hillegersberg, 2005, Helaakoski et al., 2006, Kettunen, 2009, 2012, Daniels, 2014, Diebold, Schmitt and Zehler, 2016)

The different areas of agility shown in Figure 17 are described below. The understanding of these different areas of agility is fundamental for the classification of the SLR and the classification of the results of the SLR.

- **Agile software development (ASD)** aims at fulfilling customer requirements in complex environments through an iterative and customer-focused process (Schwaber and Beedle, 2002). It values collaboration of self-organising and cross-functional teams. ASD is based on an empirical and adaptive planning process of the next steps and continuous improvement to be able to react flexible to changes such as altering customer requirements, technical updates and necessary adjustments of the (human) resources (Beck, 2000; Beck et al., 2001; Palmer and Felsing, 2002; Diebold and Dahlem, 2014).
- **Supply chain and manufacturing agility** are relevant for companies that increase their business value through the ability to react to changes in their supply chain or manufacturing processes. Supply chain and manufacturing agility describes the ability of companies to “produce, and deliver innovative products to customers in a timely and cost effective manner” (Swafford, Ghosh and Murthy, 2006; Yang, Ling and Zhang, 2013, p.153) and to satisfy

customers with short lead times, individualised products and small lot sizes (Goldman et al., 1995; Fliedner and Vokurka, 1997; Bernardes and Hanna, 2009).

- **Organisational agility** focuses on leadership that is needed to create or transform a company to a continuously learning and improving organisation that has the ability, knowledge and resources to deal with change (Yang and Liu, 2012; Appelbaum et al., 2017; Schirmmacher and Schoop, 2018). Processes need to be transparent and adjustable and need to connect the whole organisation (Crocitto and Youssef, 2003). Organisational agility can be seen as a pre-condition for enterprise agility.
- **Enterprise agility** can be defined as the company wide ability to sense and deal with change. Knowledge needs to be managed effectively and spread among employees for a company to succeed in an unpredictable business environment (Overby, Bharadwaj and Sambamurthy, 2006; Gurahoo and Salisbury, 2018). The following attributes are stated in numerous sources to describe enterprise agility: flexibility, responsiveness, speed, culture of change, integration, low complexity, high quality, customised products, and mobilisation of core competencies (Sherehiy, Karwowski and Layer, 2007; Tseng and Lin, 2011). The aim of enterprise agility is to transfer agile principles from (software) teams to the product and portfolio level (Ganguly, Nilchiani and Farr, 2009).
- The **agile business model** approach is based on the business model innovation approach that encourages companies to think in the field of strategy beyond isolated products and services and concentrate on the innovation of the entire business model. The goal is to combine agile methods such as Scrum, Kanban and Lean startup and the strategic business model innovation approach so that an iterative, customer focused innovation process with short feedback cycles can be carried out (Helaakoski et al., 2006; Kettunen, 2012).

4.1.1.2. History and origin of agility and agile methods

To better understand the different areas of agility, their origins are explained in the following. Comprehending the origins of agility helps to identify the most important, recurring aspects of agility and thus to understand what the term agility really comprises.

The first ideas that can be classified as agile approaches date back to the 1940s and 1950s. Until the 1980s, however, the approaches were not yet referred to as “agile”, but they did shape the initial approaches. The first approaches include the idea of flexibility and leanness, followed later by the

aspect of customer value and the focus on employees and communication among each other (Ohno and Bodek, 1988; Conboy, 2009).

In 1947, the Kanban method was first applied by Toyota in its main plant to adjust the production rate to the demand rate in order to be more reactive to change and customer requirements (Ohno and Bodek, 1988; Bichler and Schröter, 2004). In organisational theory in the field of social science, the concept of agility was introduced as corporate agility in the 1950s to respond effectively to changes in an insecure world. Brown and Agnew defined agility as “the capacity to react quickly to changing circumstances” in 1982 (Brown and Agnew, 1982). They refer not only flexibility of companies and their employees but also to the commitment of key assets, especially human resources to output-oriented objectives (Schirmacher and Schoop, 2018). In 1985, Womack, Jones and Ross started working on the topic of lean production to reduce waste of time, resources and money and to increase focus on customer values (Womack, Jones and Roos, 1991). Lean production is a systematised production organisation, which contrasted the buffered production prevailing in the USA and Europe at the time (Womack, Jones and Roos, 1991). In buffered production, all production lines are kept running all the time and warehouses are replenished regardless of demand. In contrast, inventories in a lean production facility are kept to the absolute minimum so that quality problems and downtime can be quickly identified and resolved (Ohno and Bodek, 1988; Womack, Jones and Roos, 1991). The application of agility was substantiated in the Lehigh Report, which was published in 1991 and specifies agile manufacturing (Nagel and Dove, 1991; Hooper, Steeple and Winters, 2001). Hooper described agile manufacturing as a "manufacturing system with extraordinary capabilities (internal capabilities: hard and soft technologies, human resources, educated management, information) to meet the rapidly changing needs of the marketplace (speed, flexibility, customers, competitors, suppliers, infrastructure, responsiveness)” (Yusuf, Sarhadi and Gunasekaran, 1999; Davarzani and Norrman, 2015; Mourtzis, 2016). In 1995, Goldman et al. amplified the Lehigh report and found that agility is also relevant to other organisational units such as marketing, design and management. Goldman et al. describe agility as “a comprehensive response to the business challenges of profiting from the rapidly changing, continually fragmenting, global markets for high-quality, high-performance, customer-configured goods and services” (Goldman et al., 1995). Dove supports Goldman et al.’s definition of agility by describing an agile organisation. According to Dove, agility consist of four dimensions: cost, quality, time and scope. In an agile organisation, all dimensions have to be considered (Dove, 1994). To deal with high product variety, variable quantities and

individualised services with short throughput times and low costs, the agile supply chain approach was developed by Yusuf and Gunasekaran in the late 1990s (Yusuf, Sarhadi and Gunasekaran, 1999). Supply chain agility seeks to allow for quick reactions and changes at short notice to respond to uncertainties in both the upstream and downstream supply chain (Fayezi, Zutshi and O’Loughlin, 2015). Following Yusuf and Gunasekaran, a company is only truly agile if it not only follows change but also takes advantage of the change (Yusuf, Sarhadi and Gunasekaran, 1999). An agile supply chain is characterised by the ability to cope with unforeseen changes in market demand and to provide “the appropriate capabilities to transform these changes into opportunities” (Swafford, Ghosh and Murthy, 2006; Gunasekaran, Subramanianm and Papadopoulos, 2016, p.15). At the beginning of the 21st century, the concept of enterprise agility was introduced. It shows the increased need of the entire business to be agile (Tsourveloudis and Valavanis, 2002; Sherehiy, Karwowski and Layer, 2007). Enterprise agility has the goal to manage and leverage knowledge effectively, so that an organisation has the potential to succeed in constantly changing and unpredictable business environments (Bottani, 2009).

IT and software development has been and is still affected by the unpredictability of changing requirements and the increasing use of computers in other company areas such as marketing, production, design and management described above (Goldman et al., 1995). The IT and software development department had difficulties reacting fast and flexible enough to the complex requirements of other areas of the company. Experts refer to that phase which took place in the 1960s as "development crisis" or "application delivery delay" (Conboy and Fitzgerald, 2004; Schirmacher and Schoop, 2018). The time between a validated business need and the deployment of the actual IT application was on average three years (Schirmacher and Schoop, 2018). Due to the absence of flexibility, Takeuchi et al. expressed that a sequential phases approach to product development is not well suited. In a sequential phases approach, the development process is organised in successive phases: analysis, design, implementation, testing, and maintenance. Since the 1980s, new process models have been developed to deal with complexity and uncertainty (Takeuchi and Nonaka, 1986). With the implementation of new architectural patterns, the combination of technical, “anthropic-oriented soft skills” and the increase of agility the so-called development crisis was put to an end (Zykov, 2020). In IT and software development, the benefits of agile approaches increased due to the dynamic circumstances of the other business areas and their increasingly complex requirements.

A visual timeline of the development of agile approaches and methods in the logistics industry and in IT departments can be found in the following overview (see Figure 18).

Figure 18: Development of agility in the logistics industry and in the software development

Source: Own representation based on (Brown and Agnew, 1982, Takeuchi and Nonaka, 1986, Womack, Jones and Roos, 1991, Goldman et al., 1995, Kruchten, 1998, Yusuf, Sarhadi and Gunasekaran, 1999, Beck et al., 2001, Dove, 2001, Hooper, Steeple and Winters, 2001, Palmer and Felsing, 2002, Schwaber and Beedle, 2002, Gunasekaran and Yusuf, 2002, Schwaber, 2004, Bichler and Schröter, 2004, Augustine, 2005, Overby, Bharadwaj and Sambamurthy, 2006, Bernardes and Hanna, 2009, Förster and Wendler, 2012, Larman and Vodde, 2016, Schirmacher and Schoop, 2018)

The development of the various agile approaches shows that agility was first important in functional areas, such as logistics, and that IT had to follow suit in order to keep up with the speed of other areas. At the time of this study, digitalisation continues to increase the importance of IT products and services. Therefore, this paper examines how agile methods support IT departments of logistics companies to keep up with the necessary development speed through the use of agile methods.

Since the 1980s, new process models for product development and first agile project management methods have been developed (Schwaber, 1997; Beck, 2000; Palmer and Felsing, 2002; Dingsøyr et al., 2012). Agile methods seek to apply agile principles and values and are a combination of agile practices. Generally, agile methods describe how products are developed over their “[...] whole lifecycle or major parts of it using a specifically named set of agile practices” (Diebold and Zehler, 2016, p.21). The most frequent examples of agile methods are Scrum and Extreme Programming (XP). Compared to agile methods, agile practices are “[...] one level below” (Diebold and Dahlem, 2014, p.2; Schmidt, Weiss and Paetzold, 2018). They are a rather small and very specific piece of a method that deals with different aspects. Some well-known examples of agile practices are the so-called "Retrospective" or "Daily Standup" meetings. All agile methods have a common characteristic

as they all focus on the increase of customer value through iterative approaches and feedback e.g. from the customers (Takeuchi and Nonaka, 1986). Crystal was developed in 1991 as a family of methods by Alistair Cockburn for IBM (Cockburn, 2005). Feature Driven Development (FDD) was defined in 1997 by Jeff de Luca to increase the customer value of pieces of software that are combined into functional features (Palmer and Felsing, 2002). Iterative process models like Rational Unified Process were developed by Kruchten in 1998 (Kruchten, 1998). Extreme Programming (XP) was developed in the late 1990s and Scrum followed in the early 2000s (Beck, 2000; Schwaber, 2004). To consolidate the different approaches the so-called “Agile Manifesto” of software development projects was introduced in 2001 by the founders of the individual agile methods described above (Beck et al., 2001). The Agile Manifesto consists of twelve principles and four values with the aim of improving the software development process and cooperation between and within teams. The Agile Manifesto, its four values and twelve principles can be seen in the following (Beck et al., 2001).

“We are uncovering better ways of developing software by doing it and helping others do it. Through this work we have come to value:

*Individuals and interactions over processes and tools
Working software over comprehensive documentation
Customer collaboration over contract negotiation
Responding to change over following a plan*

That is, while there is value in the items on the right, we value the items on the left more.”

We follow these principles:

*Our highest priority is to satisfy the customer
through early and continuous delivery
of valuable software.*

*Welcome changing requirements, even late in
development. Agile processes harness change for
the customer's competitive advantage.*

*Deliver working software frequently, from a
couple of weeks to a couple of months, with a
preference to the shorter timescale.*

*Business people and developers must work
together daily throughout the project.*

*Build projects around motivated individuals.
Give them the environment and support they need,
and trust them to get the job done.*

The most efficient and effective method of conveying information to and within a development team is face-to-face conversation.

Working software is the primary measure of progress.

Agile processes promote sustainable development. The sponsors, developers, and users should be able to maintain a constant pace indefinitely.

Continuous attention to technical excellence and good design enhances agility.

Simplicity--the art of maximizing the amount of work not done--is essential.

The best architectures, requirements, and designs emerge from self-organizing teams.

At regular intervals, the team reflects on how to become more effective, then tunes and adjusts its behaviour accordingly.

The agile methods detailed above (XP, Scrum, FDD, etc.) were developed for organisations consisting of just one development team per software product. Agile methods for scaled teams, such as the Scaled Agile Framework (SAFe), the Spotify model and Large Scale Scrum (LeSS), were created later (Larman and Vodde, 2016; Ebert and Paasivaara, 2017; Salameh and Bass, 2019). The term “scaled teams” describes organisations where multiple teams work together on one product and hereby raise the dependencies, and the need for frequent communication between the teams and the urgency to adapt agile methods. To this end, it should be noted that many agile methods and practices can also be used in other, non-IT related domains (Highsmith, 2010; Parente, 2015).

4.1.2. Definition and application of agile methods and practices

This work focuses specifically on agile methods and their application in the software development of established logistics companies and logistics start-ups. Therefore, in this section the most important agile methods and practices are defined and described.

4.1.2.1. Description of the most common agile methods and associated agile practices

The application of agile methods is ideal for complex product developments or project situations that are characterised by frequent and rapid changes (Kurtz and Snowden, 2003; Stacey and Mowles, 2016). Agile methods are designed to minimise the resulting complexity by accelerating the speed of

response, improving collaboration (Kaim, Härting and Reichstein, 2019), increasing trust between team members and customer confidence in the product. Additionally, simpler processes and reduced changing costs result in increased productivity and a lower defect rate (Prater, Biehl and Smith, 2001; Shah and Nies, 2008; Baig, Shah and Sajjad, 2017). This raises the product's quality and decreases its complexity. (Anwer et al., 2017).

The following table shows the most frequently used agile methods and the corresponding practices (Lankhorst et al., 2012; Butt, 2016; Anwer et al., 2017; VersionOne, 2019). The individual practices can also be used in combination with other methods, but originally belong to the adjacent method. As described above, many agile methods and practices are also applicable in other, non-IT related domains, as the focus is generally on developing customer value (Highsmith, 2010; Parente, 2015). The use of agile methods in non-IT related domains is described in section 2.2.5. In Table 2 agile methods and practices are listed in alphabetical order.

Table 15: Overview of the most common agile methods and associated agile practices

Sources: (Cockburn, 1998, Beck, 2000, Palmer and Felsing, 2002, Abrahamsson et al., 2003, Schwaber, 2004, VersionOne, 2019)

Agile method	Agile practices
Crystal	Close Communication, Frequent Delivery, High User Involvement, Reflective Improvement, etc.
Extreme Programming	Continuous Integration, Pair Programming, Regular Software Builds, Test-driven Development, etc.
Feature Driven Development	Code Inspections, Code Ownership, Feature Teams, Regular Builds of the Software, etc.
Kanban	Feedback Cycles, Limit Work in Progress, Visualisation, etc.
Lean startup	Build-Measure-Learn, Minimum Viable Product, Pivots, etc.
Large Scale Scrum	Lean Thinking, Overall Retrospectives, Sprint Planning 1 & 2, etc.
Scrum	Daily Standups, Product Owner, Retrospectives, Scrum Master, Sprint Planning, etc.
Scaled Agile Framework	Agile Release Train, Inspect & Adapt Event, Product Increment Planning, etc.

The most common agile methods are presented below (VersionOne, 2021). These agile methods are selected as they are used by more than 90% of all agile teams (VersionOne, 2021):

1. Scrum
2. Kanban
3. Extreme Programming
4. Feature Driven Development

5. Crystal
6. Lean startup
7. Large Scale Scrum
8. Scaled Agile Framework

In the following sections, these methods and associated practices are explained and discussed.

1. The creators of Scrum, Schwaber and Sutherland, describe **Scrum** as a framework for people to tackle complex, adaptive business problems while continually providing creative products of the highest value (Schwaber, 2004). By applying an iterative approach with a combination of sprints, synchronisation sessions (such as “Daily Standups”, “Sprint Plannings” and “Reviews”), and “Retrospectives”, various enhancements are realised through the Scrum team. The tasks of the team are gathered into the so-called backlog that is organised according to the prioritisation of the tasks by the product owner. The Scrum team is composed of the product owner, responsible for the product vision and prioritisation of the backlog, the scrum master, responsible for the Scrum process that consists of the Scrum meetings described above, and the software developers (Ashraf and Aftab, 2017). As Scrum mainly focuses on the management activities and does not prescribe any specification or development practices it can be applied to other project types as well (Dingsøy et al., 2012). Scrum is “lightweight” and easy to understand. Scrum encourages teams to learn through experiences, self-organise while working on a problem, and reflect the things that worked well and the things that worked rather badly to continuously improve (Schwaber, 2004; Dingsøy et al., 2012). Compared to other methods, Scrum is rather strict about the course of action and the meetings taking place during one iteration, the so-called Sprint, as it aims to protect the developers during the iteration from external interruptions (Schwaber, 1997). Scrum describes the project organisation for only one team with a maximum of ten members (Schwaber and Beedle, 2002). The Scrum guide makes no reference to project situations in which more than ten people work together on a product and often have to coordinate the implementation of new software features (Schwaber and Beedle, 2002). Here, so-called scaling methods such as SAFe and LeSS are better suited (Larman and Vodde, 2016; Ebert and Paasivaara, 2017).
2. **Kanban** used as a method for software development aims to adopt the lean principles from manufacturing such as the elimination of waste, the amplification of learning, and making decisions as late as possible. A core idea of the Kanban method is to use a signboard to

visualise the current tasks. Different columns are used to present the status of the individual tasks, which are displayed on Kanban cards. Additionally, the aim of this visualisation of the workflow is a limitation of the amount of tasks that are currently in progress. Kanban encourages continuous improvement to realise an efficient workflow (Anderson, 2010; Ahmad et al., 2018). Compared to other methods like Scrum, XP, LeSS and SAFe Kanban does not rely on fixed intervals like the Sprints of Scrum, but on a continuous workflow. This allows a rapid reaction to changes, whereas the iterations of other methods like Scrum, XP, LeSS and SAFe want to protect the teams within the iteration from external disturbances. Kanban has no predefined roles (Dingssoeyr, Falessi and Power, 2019).

3. A "lightweight" method - this is how the inventor of **XP**, Kent Beck, characterises his agile method, which is built on simplicity, communication, courage, feedback and respect (Beck, 2000). It is a process of trial, error, and continuous improvement, without a “given software process that can be pointed to as the one and only definition of Extreme Programming” (Keenan and Bustard, 2006, p.1). The core idea of XP is the cyclical approach at all levels. For example, two developers coordinate their work permanently (every second) through the agile practice Pair Programming. Using Pair Programming two software developers work on the same piece of software and implement new features together. During software development, the new software is checked every minute through Test-Driven Development. In XP, the software is integrated continuously into the overall system once every hour to enable regular software builds (Beck, 2000). At least once a day, the entire team synchronises during a “Daily Standups” Meeting. XP is a very technical method that uses software engineering practices such as Refactoring, Continuous Integration of the software, and Test-Driven development to produce software of high quality and create a pleasant work space for the development team (Beck, 2000). XP is the agile method that is the most specific regarding the use of software engineering practices but is more flexible to changes concerning the upcoming tasks and work packages than Scrum, LeSS and SAFe. XP uses similar roles and meetings as Scrum, LeSS and SAFe but additionally prescribes the use of software engineering practices, which is why its focus on software development is stronger.
4. Scrum, XP, and other agile methodologies all use an iterative approach to deliver software. By contrast, the five steps in **FDD** require the team to follow a set of engineering best practices as they develop small feature sets. The first three activities (“Develop overall system model”, “Build feature list”, “Plan by feature”) are performed at the beginning of the project. After

the overall system model is developed, the required features are collected in a list and planned in a sequential order (Palmer and Felsing, 2002). These first three phases are unique to FDD, as other agile methods do not define the product scope beforehand in such detail. Afterwards, the remaining two activities (“Design Feature” and “Build Feature”) are performed continuously and iteratively, as a feature is defined as "a customer-evaluated functionality that can be implemented in two weeks or less" (Pang and Blair, 2004, p.86). Feature teams, that work together on related features, inspect the team members’ code and own it together (Palmer and Felsing, 2002). Through the short development cycles, regular software builds can be guaranteed in the fourth and fifth step. These five steps ensure that the product development remains consistent so that the project can grow and new team members can come up to speed much faster. FDD uses a greater number of different roles than other agile methods.

5. Unlike more fixed frameworks like Scrum, **Crystal** recognises that different teams will perform differently depending on team size, criticality and priority of the project and encourages users to adapt the framework for their individual situation (Cockburn, 2005). Criticality is assessed according to criteria such as satisfaction of the customer and potential loss of money. Depending on the selected Crystal variant, the number of roles, the number of practices used and the scope of documentation change. For example, a small team can keep itself aligned with regular communication, so it does not need much status reporting and documentation, whereas a large team is likely to get out-of-sync and benefits from a more structured approach. However, certain rules, characteristics, and values are common to all variants of the Crystal family (Dingsøyr et al., 2012). These include the incremental approach, focus on human face-to-face communication and collaboration, frequent software delivery, involvement of the user and reflective improvement meetings. Teams have a lot of autonomy but may lack structure compared to other methods like Scrum and XP.
6. The **Lean startup** is designed for any start-up or business that has to manage uncertainty regarding the product design. A core principle of Lean startup is that the faster companies and start-ups learn, the faster they succeed. According to the founders of the Lean startup method, Ries and Blank, the only way to learn is to get the product or service in front of real paying customers (Ries, 2017). Lean startup aims to go through feedback loops with the customer as fast as possible to test hypothesis and learn from the results as early as possible (Ries, 2011; Nilsen and Ramm, 2015). Lean startup does not include specific roles or meetings.

7. One of the product development frameworks for multiple teams who work together on a single product is called **Large-Scale Scrum (LeSS)**. It extends the agile method Scrum with scaling rules and guidelines (Beck et al., 2001; Schwaber, 2004). Nevertheless, the focus remains on the original goals of Scrum as LeSS uses only few additional meetings and roles compared to the original Scrum method (Larman and Vodde, 2016). LeSS is more lightweight than SAFe and does not include guidelines regarding the program and the overall organisation. It shows how up to eight teams can work together with Scrum without introducing many further practices. If more than eight teams work together, LeSS Huge is available (Larman and Vodde, 2016). LeSS Huge uses overall “Retrospectives” to reflect the collaboration between the teams, “Sprint Plannings” for all teams together before the individual teams perform a separate “Sprint Planning” and encourages the use of additional methods such as Lean Thinking.
8. The **Scaled Agile Framework (SAFe)** is a combination of workflow and organisational patterns. Many of them are based on Scrum. The goal is to support companies in scaling teams with more than 100 people with lean and agile approaches (Ebert and Paasivaara, 2017). SAFe is based on the Scrum method and introduces more additional roles and processes than LeSS. SAFe considers not only the team level, but also the overarching project program and organisational level, so that governance and product management are also included. An iterative approach is taken and realised through the so-called “Increment Planning”. After completion of several sprints, the results of the teams are integrated in the overall system through the agile release train and the development process itself is reflected in so-called “Inspect and Adapt” events. Due to the definition of additional levels besides the team level, SAFe is often used in companies that have worked in a rather classical setting for a long time, e.g. according to the Waterfall model (Ebert and Paasivaara, 2017).

4.1.2.2. Application of agile methods in non-IT related domains

The majority of scientific publications on agile methods are restricted to the aspect of software development (Chin, 2004; Sliger and Broderick, 2008; Birgün and Çerkezoğlu, 2019). But other authors state that the agile methods and practices can be adapted to alternative environments like project management in general, but also to newly founded logistics start-ups to improve their flexibility for upcoming challenges, their ability to create customer value faster and to deal with complex environments (Highsmith, 2010; Parente, 2015). Several case studies show that agile project management can be used successfully and offers many advantages over traditional approaches such

as the Waterfall model (Gustavsson, 2015; Papadakis and Tsironis, 2018). Agile methods like Scrum can be applied without much effort in many cases (Sheffield and Lemétayer, 2013; Edwards et al., 2020) but to apply them organisational prerequisites have to be met. These prerequisites are among others a stable project team, (agile) project management experience and openness for a defined product development process to enable the application of methods like Scrum or XP in the organisation (Cervone, 2011; Conforto et al., 2017; Menges et al., 2018). The prerequisites of agile project management correspond in many aspects to those of ASD. It is not only software development and project management that benefit from agile approaches, but also complex business processes, e.g. logistics processes like the ones belonging to a supply chain (Swafford, Ghosh and Murthy, 2006).

It can be assumed that also the IT departments of established logistics companies and logistics start-ups may benefit from the use of agile methods and practices. Until January 2021, no publications is identified that address the use of agile methods in software development of logistics start-ups (see Section 4.2. – SLR, page 88).

4.1.3. Background and relevance of logistics industry

After developing a common understanding on agile methods, the relevance of the logistics industry for this study is explained and a common view on logistics companies is established. This study focuses on how the logistics industry deals with agility and how established logistics companies and logistics start-ups use agile methods to deliver innovative (software) products that are appreciated by customers (Vogel and Lasch, 2018). Therefore, a short distinction between the different kinds of logistics companies and their relation to IT departments is given. In order to link logistics companies to the use of agile methods in the IT, definitions of the terms “IT department” and “IT project” in logistics companies are presented. IT in the logistics industry can be used to support logistics processes, but can also represent the product itself, for example in platforms (Founou, 2002; Gleissner and Femerling, 2013). When the term “IT” is applied in the following, it refers to information technology or IT projects and departments.

As described in the Introduction (see Section 1 – Introduction, page 1) the logistics industry is known for being a "slow adapter" - especially with regard to product and organisational innovations (Kupp, Marval and Borchers, 2017). Many logistics companies react rather slowly to changes even though these changes might already be more established in other industries. Agile methods can assist in responding to change. Therefore, it is interesting to understand to what extent the logistics industry

is already using agile methods. The question is whether logistics start-ups, which generally seem to be better at responding to change, use agile methods differently than established logistics companies. In order to answer this question, the following section lays the foundation by explaining what distinguishes logistics companies and how established logistics companies and logistics start-ups differ.

4.1.3.1. Definition of established logistics companies

In the context of this study, logistics companies are primarily concerned with the management and execution of transport, handling and storage of goods, but also with the optimisation of material flows and overarching, cross-company logistics management, i.e. supply chain management (Göpfert and Seeßle, 2017). The supply of logistics services constitutes a derived demand and is therefore strongly dependent on the development of primary demand (Schmitt, 2006). Service providers operate as a link between the individual stages of the value chain and the companies represented in it. Logistics companies do not necessarily have to handle the goods themselves, they can also offer a platform for doing so (Sucky and Asdecker, 2019). As logistics start-ups are defined as organisations that are younger than ten years and that offer innovative products (see Figure 19) logistics companies are called established when they are older than ten years (Skala, 2019). When the term “logistics companies” is applied in the following, it refers to established logistics companies *and* logistics start-ups.

Commonalities of traditional logistics companies and logistics start-ups	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management and execution of transport, transshipment and storage of goods • Optimisation of material flows and overall, cross-company logistics management • Act as links between different companies of the value chain 	
Specifics of traditional logistics companies	Specifics of logistics start-ups
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are older than ten years or do not fulfil start-ups specifics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Younger than ten years • Newly founded company • Innovative technology and/or business model • Aim for a significant growth in workforces and/or sales

Figure 19: Characteristics of established logistics companies and logistics start-ups
Source: Own representation

4.1.3.2. Definition of logistics start-ups

Logistics start-ups focus on rather similar tasks as the established logistics companies (see Section 2.3.1. –Definition of established logistics companies, page 32). In order to clarify the differences between the requirements of different logistics companies, it is explained in which attributes logistics start-ups deviate from established logistics companies. Steve Blank, one of the best-known

entrepreneurship educators, and his co-author Bob Dorf, an experienced start-up trainer and consultant, describe a start-up as follows:

"A start-up is not a smaller version of a large company. A start-up is a temporary organisation in search of a scalable, repeatable, profitable business model." (Blank and Dorf, 2012, p.XXI)

Other aspects found in the entrepreneurial literature can broaden this definition. Many sources agree upon the following aspects. On the basis of their definitions, a start-up can be defined as follows:

- a newly established company in its first phase of operation, which is to create a new product or service (Gaida, 2011; Xavier and Martins, 2011; Giardino et al., 2014)
- a company that resolves a problem whose solution is not yet known or obvious (Albats and Fiegenbaum, 2016; Bajwa et al., 2017). Therefore, the idea of the product or service must be unique or involve highly innovative technologies and/or business models to be successful (Kollmann, 2009; Albats and Fiegenbaum, 2016; Giardino et al., 2016)
- a company that faces the uncertainty of its business model on a weekly or monthly basis (Ries, 2011; Moogk, 2012; Paternoster et al., 2014)
- a company that is designed to grow (Davidsson and Wiklund, 2006) and aims to build a scalable and profitable business model (Blank and Dorf, 2012; Unterkalmsteiner et al., 2016)
- a company that often operates in very volatile markets (Bohn and Kundisch, 2018; Unterkalmsteiner et al., 2016)
- a company facing a lack of resources (Giardino et al., 2014; Unterkalmsteiner et al., 2016)

An overview of the criteria used to define the term “start-up” is shown in Table 3. Authors are listed in alphabetical order.

Table 16: Overview of criteria used to define start-ups

Sources: (Davidsson and Wiklund, 2006, Kollmann, 2009, Ries, 2011, Xavier and Martins, 2011, Gaida, 2011, Blank and Dorf, 2012, Moogk, 2012, Paternoster et al., 2014, Giardino et al., 2014, 2016, Klotins, Unterkalmsteiner and Gorschek, 2015, Albats and Fiegenbaum, 2016, Unterkalmsteiner et al., 2016, Bajwa et al., 2017)

Criteria used to define start-ups									
Author, Year	Newly founded	Younger than ten years	Innovative product/service	Unique business model	Deals with uncertainty	Aims for significant growth	Scalable business model	Operates in volatile markets	Lack of resources
Albats and Fiegenbaum, 2016	x	x	x	x		x			
Bajwa et al., 2017	x	x	x		x			x	x
Blank & Dorf, 2012	x		x	x	x	x	x		
Bohn and Kundisch, 2018	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	
Davidsson and Wiklund, 2006	x	x				x			
Gaida, 2011	x		x						
Giardino et al., 2014	x	x	x		x				x
Giardino et al., 2016	x	x	x	x				x	x
Kollmann, 2009	x		x	x					
Moogk, 2012	x	x			x				
Paternoster et al., 2014	x	x			x				
Ries, 2011	x				x				
Ripsas and Tröger, 2015	x	x							
Unterkalms teiner et al., 2016	x	x					x	x	x
Xavier and Martins, 2011	x		x						

Not every newly founded company is a start-up. Based on the definitions used in the literature, logistics start-ups in this study have to be younger than ten years, have to be (highly) innovative with their technology and/or their business model and have or aim for a significant growth in workforces and / or sales (Ripsas and Tröger, 2015). Innovativeness can be measured with various scales that can be found in the literature (Price and Ridgway, 1983; Gamal, 2011). Logistics start-ups can be founded as a venture capital backed small operation, but also as non-profit organisations and even in cooperation with the government (Moogk, 2012).

Agile methods considered in this study are mainly used in IT departments and projects. In the following, a final link is made to IT in logistics companies. In particular, IT departments and IT projects are considered, as their importance increases due to the digitalisation.

4.1.3.3. Understanding of IT projects and IT departments in logistics companies

In this study, the terms IT project and IT department refer to a group of employees who have the goal to develop and implement software, services or e.g. network projects (de Bakker, Boonstra and Wortmann, 2010). IT projects are limited in time as well as in many cases in budget and focus often on the development of new features (Lech, 2013), whereas IT departments are put together on a long-term basis and therefore often take care of the software maintenance. The agile approach separates less between development of new features and the maintenance of already existing software. Making agile teams responsible for the development of new software and the maintenance of the developed software often ensures a more sustainable development of new software and increases the software quality (Mishra and Otaiwi, 2020). Agile development teams who develop new software and are responsible for the software maintenance at the same time have to fix defective software themselves. That creates an incentive for the agile development teams to develop software of a higher quality that minimises the effort required for the maintenance of the software. Software products can be practical tools, the setting up of databases but also the development of websites (Corral et al., 2012). Agile methods support the continuous improvement and maintenance of the product / service through the feedback of users on their requirements (Beck et al., 2001).

IT projects and departments have been relevant in the context of the logistics industry for a long time. For example, software products can be used to deal with complex logistical processes with a high number of parties involved, but also to share information and documentations (Gleissner and Femerling, 2013). The value of IT and software products for all industries, including the logistics industry, increases (Hazen and Byrd, 2012). Logistics processes are not only supported by IT to

reduce costs but software products are used to create a competitive advantage (Sohal, Moss and Monash, 2001). The digitalisation raises the importance of IT and software products strongly. For IT departments and projects of logistics companies it is necessary to react quickly to changing requirements and satisfy the customers' needs. This is where agile methods and practices have proven to be very helpful (Cockburn and Highsmith, 2001; Cohn, 2009).

4.2. Systematic literature review

The intention of the SLR is to investigate how other studies describe the use of agile methods and practices by established logistics companies and logistics start-ups. Relevant methods and practices are based on agile software development methodologies; therefore, approaches like the agile supply chain are not the main target of this SLR study. Whether established logistics companies and start-ups use the same methods and practices is the focus of the investigation, as well as which benefits they realise with these methods and practices and what challenges they face. In this chapter, related publications as well as the results of the conducted SLR are described in detail. The SLR is conducted based on the guidelines from Kitchenham and Charters, Brereton et al. and Wohlin (Brereton et al., 2007; Kitchenham and Charters, 2007; Wohlin, 2014). Additionally, the results of the SLR lay the theoretical foundation for the framework that consolidates the findings of this study (see Section 7 – Framework, page 176).

4.2.1. Identification of associated literature reviews

In the *Related work* section in the interviews chapter (see 3.1.1. – Related work, page 56) the general interest of other researchers in the use of agile methods in start-ups and in the benefits of agility for the logistics industry are validated. To verify the need of an SLR and learn from other related literature publications in the research field of agile methods and logistics publications are analysed below.

4.2.1.1. Related work

This section describes other literature reviews and mapping studies that are relevant to this field of research. Before conducting the SLR, the research gap is verified by looking at other literature reviews and mapping studies. So far, only a few related literature reviews and mapping studies have been conducted. The next paragraphs summarise the most relevant reviews. As no study that focuses on agile methods used in IT of logistics companies is found, one mapping study that focuses only on the implementation of agile methods is included.

Perego, Perotti and Mangiaracina (2011) classify 44 studies on information and communication technology (ICT) for logistics and freight transport. They find comparatively few, but mainly fairly recent studies. The authors note that the use of ICT in the logistics industry and the organisation of IT, e.g. through agile project management, are still currently underrepresented in the literature. The study shows that most of the studies investigated are either conceptual works or empirical studies, i.e. they are mostly grounded in case studies, surveys or interviews (Perego, Perotti and Mangiaracina, 2011).

In 2012, Gligor and Holcomb published their SLR with the aim of establishing a conceptual framework that describes the relationships between capabilities of logistics companies in terms of their potential to achieve manufacturing, organisational and supply chain agility. The authors note that the literature explaining supply chain agility has mainly focused on manufacturing flexibility, supply chain speed or lean manufacturing, but logistics capabilities have not been considered to provide a more holistic view. However, the study is of practical importance as the degree of supply chain agility in a supply chain affects the efficiency and effectiveness of joint efforts (Holcomb and Gligor, 2012).

As many companies use only parts of agile methods, known as agile practices, Diebold and Dahlem conducted a mapping study to study the use of agile practices. They observe how project types, domains, and processes influence the selection of agile practices. After analysing 24 studies, the results reveal that some practices are used more often and that the process and the domain influence the selection of different practices. Additionally, the results support Ken Schwaber's theory that usually agile methods are not used "completely", but that rather certain, particular practices are applied (Schwaber, 2004; Diebold and Dahlem, 2014).

In 2014, Daniels publishes his study looking at the attributes of the agile methodology and its impact on the success of new businesses in the context of an entrepreneurial orientation. A literature review on agile attributes and strategic management serves as the foundation for a qualitative data gathering survey of agile experts in IT functions and professors of business management. Daniels finds that agile methods go further than software development and can promote the sustainability and success of start-ups. The acceptance of uncertainty, consistent communication, cooperative teams, lean organisation and development in an iterative way are particularly beneficial for start-ups (Daniels, 2014).

The main purpose of Wudhikarn et al.'s literature review is to address the limited adoption of comprehensive intellectual capital methods in logistics studies, underdevelopment of specific performance indicators and measures used, and the lack of appreciation of human capital as internal strength. The review is based on 111 studies. They disclose that most measures used are mainly related to the financial aspect, even though some consider specific components of intellectual capital, such as process efficiency and effectiveness (Wudhikarn, Chakpitak and Neubert, 2018).

4.2.2. Shortcomings of associated literature reviews

To conclude, it can be said that the related publications cover only a few aspects on the use of agile methods and practices in established logistics companies and start-ups. The following shortcomings can be observed:

- Perego, Perotti and Mangiaracina focus on ICT, but not on agile methods or practices, even though they touch slightly on the topic of agile project management;
- Gligor and Holcomb present supply chain agility but do not take agile methods and practices into account;
- Diebold and Dahlem describe which agile practices are used by companies, but they do not consider established logistics companies or logistics start-ups;
- Daniels publishes an adjustment of the Agile Manifesto for start-ups, but analyses neither the use of agile methods and practices in logistics start-ups, nor in established logistics companies. And finally,
- Wudhikarn et al. concentrate on performance indicators in the logistics industry that are based on human capital and not on traditional financial indicators. Even though human capital and its focus on resources is related to agile methods, Wudihikarn et al. do not include agile methods in their study.

Before conducting an SLR, the related work is gathered to verify the existence of a research gap. To this end, the SLR is conducted as the overview of related work shows that no SLR on the use of agile methods and practices in logistics companies and start-ups has been performed. The increasing number of research projects on logistics start-ups demonstrates the importance of further research (Holdorf, Roeder and Haasis, 2015).

4.2.3. Results of the systematic literature review

Fifteen relevant studies were ultimately included in this SLR. First, characteristics of the studies and quantitative data (e.g., publication channel, research method or quality overall) are summarised. Findings related to the RQs are presented afterwards.

4.2.3.1. Characteristics of the publications identified

The fifteen relevant papers are published in conference proceedings, scientific journals, book chapters, or as doctoral studies. Seven articles are published in scientific journals and seven are published in conference proceedings. One PhD study is included as well.

In summary, eight papers use case studies, five studies are a single case study and three papers comprise a multiple case study comparing results from different cases. Five publications present a framework that was developed. Four of the five frameworks are not validated through further research. Two papers describe the results of a survey that was conducted. Overall, it can be stated that the use of agile methods and practices in the logistics industry was investigated in real-life contexts in close proximity to existing work practices. It needs to be noted that a case study may not necessarily be generalised and applied in other contexts, which could have an impact on the interpretation of the results.

A three-point Likert scale is used to assess the quality of the identified papers (see Table 9, page 32). The results of the quality assessment are shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Results of the quality assessment

Source: Own representation

The first parameter inspects whether the scientific idea is validated through further research. Eleven papers (partially) validated the approach used through (multiple) case studies or through surveys. In the four remaining proposals found, the researchers developed a theoretical framework. QA2

examines whether the research approach is described in detail. In six papers, the approach is described in detail so that other researcher could use it directly, and in nine papers the approach is only partially described, which means that anyone who intends to use the approach must read the references. No paper missing a detailed approach was included. QA3 queries whether the publications provide a personal opinion or viewpoint: eleven of the fifteen papers are based only on research, and the other four studies included parts of personal viewpoints, because related publications are explained and the papers are set into a specific context. QA4 explores whether the study is cited by other authors. To assess this, Google Scholar is used to determine the number of times the study is cited (assessment date 19.01.2021). Eight papers are cited more than five times; seven paper are cited fewer than five times. QA5 tests whether the publication clearly states the objective of the study. Thirteen studies have a clear objective. Two studies have an objective that is described only vaguely. None of the papers lack the description of an objective.

In summary, one paper fulfilled all of the described criteria and was cited more than five times (Pijpers et al., 2012). The results may differ at the publication date of this study because the actual number of citations could change.

4.2.3.2. Results of the systematic literature review relevant to research question 1

Of the fifteen relevant studies, all focus on established logistics companies (Yusuf, Sarhadi and Gunasekaran, 1999; Marlow and Paixão Casaca, 2003; Morlok and Chang, 2004; van Oosterhout, Waarts and van Hillegersberg, 2005; Wang, 2011; Pijpers et al., 2012; Tuan and Thang, 2013; Dybå and Dingsøy, 2015; Longo and Iazzolino, 2016; Bernal et al., 2019; Genzorova, Corejova and Stalmasekova, 2019; Cichosz, Wallenburg and Knemeyer, 2020; Dunz, Werth and Breitner, 2020; Rola and Kuchta, 2020). No publication that looks at logistics start-ups and agility, agile methods or agile practices can be found. Therefore, no publication on logistics start-ups is included. Even though all studies identified target agility, only some name concrete agile methods from ASD. Six papers present data on other areas of agility such as agile supply chain (see Table 17). Since most publications show other areas of agility, such as supply chain and manufacturing agility, these are taken into account to display that the concept of agility itself is widespread in the logistics industry. However, this SLR is about agile IT project management methods, which are the centre of this study, but are only covered by a few publications so far. Agile methods/ areas are listed in order of frequency of appearance.

Table 17: Agile methods and agile areas applied within logistics companies and start-ups

Agile method/ area	Number of studies that name agile method/ area
Scrum	4
eXtreme Programming	3
Agile manufacturing	2
Agile supply chain	2
Agile organisation	1
Business agility	1
Crystal	1
Design Thinking	1

The fifteen relevant studies demonstrate that some established logistics companies use agile methods like XP and Scrum. Other established logistics companies apply different areas of agility such as business agility, agile business models, or agile supply chains.

Besides agile methods, it is also to be analysed which agile practices are used in established logistics companies and logistics start-ups (see Table 18). For established logistics companies, three studies are found that describe the use of agile practices (Cichosz, Wallenburg and Knemeyer, 2020; Dunz, Werth and Breitner, 2020; Rola and Kuchta, 2020). Besides agile methods and practices the identified papers describe guidelines that are helpful for an agile organisation, but can also be used in a setting with classical project management, e.g., a Waterfall organisation (McAvoy and Butler, 2009). For logistics start-ups no relevant studies are found. Agile practices are listed in order of frequency of appearance.

Table 18: Agile practices and guidelines mentioned in identified publications

Agile practices and guidelines	Number of papers that cover agile guideline
Regular communication between business and IT	3
Flat hierarchies	2
Customer focus	2
Retrospectives	2
Iterations, e.g. Sprints	2
Daily standup meetings	1
Empowerment of the team	1
Cross-functional teams	1
Focus on knowledge of the people not technologies	1
Continuous improvement	1

Three of the fifteen relevant studies detail the use of agile methods by explaining the use of agile guidelines and agile practices (Marlow and Paixão Casaca, 2003; Cichosz, Wallenburg and Knemeyer, 2020; Dunz, Werth and Breitner, 2020).

Upon closer inspection, it becomes clear that all the studies have somewhat differing understandings of agility. This corresponds to the statement that agility is, as already described, a multifaceted concept (see Section 4.1.1. – Agile methods and practices, page 68). Therefore, the definitions of the agile areas of the identified publications are compared. Some studies target agile methods based on ASD such as Scrum and XP while others focus on different areas of agility such as agile supply chains, agile business models, and business agility. The studies included on ASD methods do not define agile methods like Scrum and XP, but only name them. The definitions of the other areas (Agile manufacturing, supply chain agility, agile organisation and business agility) partially overlap, but are not completely consistent. For supply chain agility, only one definition is found in the included publications. Wang explains that the “agile supply chain [...] is regarded as the interchangeable terms of responsive supply chain.” (Wang, 2011). Looking at the definition of agile manufacturing, Wang and Yusuf, Sarhadi and Gunasekaran agree that agile manufacturing is based on responsiveness to social and environmental issues, the mobilisation of core competencies, and the focus on “products and services with high information and value-adding content” (Yusuf, Sarhadi and Gunasekaran, 1999; Wang, 2011). Wang adds “rapid prototyping, concurrent engineering, multi-skilled and flexible people, continuous improvement, team working, change and risk management, information technology and empowering”, and Yusuf, Sarhadi and Gunasekaran subjoin “synthesis of diverse technologies” and “intra-enterprise and inter-enterprise integration”. For business agility, only one definition is found in the fifteen studies, so no comparison is possible. Business agility is defined as “being able to swiftly and easily change businesses and business processes outside the normal level of flexibility to effectively deal with highly unpredictable external and internal changes” (van Oosterhout, Waarts and van Hillegersberg, 2005).

4.2.3.3. Results of the systematic literature review relevant to research question 2

The benefits examined by this SLR that established logistics companies aim to realise with agile methods and practices are divided into the following clusters. The clusters are developed based on the agile values that are expressed in the Agile Manifesto (Beck et al., 2001):

- Customer-related benefits
- Product-related benefits

- Communication-related benefits
- Processual and organisational benefits

The benefits that logistics start-ups want to realise with agile methods and practices are not taken into account as no paper that focuses on logistics start-ups and agile methods or practices is found.

For each cluster the benefits are stated together with the applied agile method or practice (see Table 19). Additionally, the number of employees (EMP) that work in the established logistics company is specified, if mentioned in the publications. Authors are listed in chronological order.

Established logistics companies realise customer-related benefits through the application of agile methods and practices. They are improving their ability to meet changing customer needs and learn (faster) from customer feedback. Logistics companies have a need for lower-priced products that they implement through the use of business agility. Through the application of an agile business model, established companies ameliorate the alignment between IT and business and reduce documentation to a minimal, strictly necessary amount. Looking at processual and organisational benefits, logistics companies face personnel bottlenecks, lack of resources, and intensive time pressure. Business agility and agile supply chain are used to decrease these. To reduce the number of complex processes that hinder productivity and increase the number of errors made, continuous delivery, a software engineering approach, is used in established logistics companies. The companies covered by the most recent studies found within this SLR also increasingly use agile methods to digitalise their business model and replace outdated technologies (Bernal et al., 2019; Genzorova, Corejova and Stalmasekova, 2019; Dunz, Werth and Breitner, 2020).

Table 19: Benefits that established logistics companies want to realise with agile methods, practices and areas

Cluster	Benefits	Used agile method or practice/ area to realise benefit	Company type (EMP)	Papers
Customer	Satisfy customer requirements within the agreed-upon timeframe with high quality service levels	Business agility, Agile manufacturing,	Established (n/a; > 50 employees)	van Oosterhout, Waarts and van Hillegersberg, 2005; Wang, 2011; Longo and Iazzolino, 2016; Gurahoo and Salisbury, 2018 Rola and Kuchta, 2020

Cluster	Benefits	Used agile method or practice/ area to realise benefit	Company type (EMP)	Papers
	Adapt to changing requirements faster	Business agility	Established (n/a)	van Oosterhout, Waarts and van Hillegersberg, 2005; Longo and Iazzolino, 2016
Product	Development of lower-priced products	Business agility	Established (n/a)	van Oosterhout, Waarts and van Hillegersberg, 2005;
	Digitalise business model	Design Thinking, Scrum	Established (n/a)	Bernal et al., 2019; Genzorova, Corejova and Stalmasekova, 2019; Dunz, Werth and Breitner, 2020
Communication	Alignment of IT and business	Agile business model	Established (SME; large enterprises)	Pijpers et al., 2012
Processual and organisational	Reduce personnel bottlenecks, time pressure, and lack of resources	Business agility, agile supply chain	Established (n/a)	Marlow and Paixão Casaca, 2003; Morlok and Chang, 2004; van Oosterhout, Waarts and van Hillegersberg, 2005
	Modernise outdated processes and technologies	Scrum, XP, and Crystal	Established (n/a)	Bernal et al., 2019; Genzorova, Corejova and Stalmasekova, 2019; Dunz, Werth and Breitner, 2020

4.2.3.4. Results of the systematic literature review relevant to research question 3

The difficulties that established logistics companies face when applying agile methods and practices found in this SLR are grouped into the following clusters based on the agile values that are expressed in the Agile Manifesto (Beck et al., 2001):

- Product-related difficulties
- Processual difficulties
- People-related difficulties

For each cluster, the difficulties are stated together with the applied agile method or practice (see Table 20). In addition, it is specified how many employees work in the established logistics company,

if stated in the study. For the cluster “Communication” no difficulties were stated in the identified papers.

The challenges that logistics start-ups face applying agile methods and practices are not taken into account as no paper on logistics start-ups and agile methods or practices has been found.

It needs to be noted that, even though many papers describe why logistics companies apply agile methods and practices and what benefits they plan to realise, only five out of fifteen studies describe the difficulties established companies actually face applying agile methods and practices.

Established logistics companies have difficulties designing a product that is receptive to changing requirements and allows agility. Employees working on established products have problems dealing with short-term changes. Looking at the already existing processes of established logistics companies, it is difficult to identify the drivers that would facilitate a shift towards agility. Established logistics companies face problems regarding the mindset and culture within their companies when using agile methods and practices. Agile methods stand for another organisational cultural than rather traditional project management approaches and imply a cultural shift towards collaboration within teams and with customers (see Section 3 – Interviews, page 56).

Table 20: Difficulties established logistics companies face with the use of agile methods/ areas

Cluster	Difficulties	Applied agile method/ area	Company type (EMP)	Paper
Product	Find the right design of a product that allows supply chain agility	Agile manufacturing	Established (> 50 employees)	Wang, 2011
Processual	Identify drivers that increase supply chain agility	Supply chain agility	Established (n/a)	Yusuf, Sarhadi and Gunasekaran, 1999
	Need to comply with legal requirements that prevent the implementation and use of some agile practices	Scrum	Established (n/a)	Cichosz, Wallenburg and Knemeyer, 2020
	Many management levels and rigid hierarchies	Scrum	Established (n/a)	Dunz, Werth and Breitner, 2020
	Pressure to deviate from Scrum processes in time of high	Scrum	Established (n/a)	Dunz, Werth and Breitner, 2020

Cluster	Difficulties	Applied agile method/ area	Company type (EMP)	Paper
	pressure reduces the product quality			
	Retrospective meetings are not held regularly, improvements are implemented with delay	Scrum	Established (n/a)	Dunz, Werth and Breitner, 2020
	Missing or late knowledge of customer requirements	Scrum	Established (n/a)	Dunz, Werth and Breitner, 2020
People	Existing rigid and hierarchical mindset and culture	Business agility	Established (n/a)	van Oosterhout, Waarts and van Hillegersberg, 2005

4.2.4. Discussion of the systematic literature review

In sum, fifteen relevant studies have been found and analysed according to the research protocol. Below, the findings of the SLR will be discussed in general, and as they relate to the RQs.

General findings of the systematic literature review

The results of the SLR show that agile methods and practices, and other agile areas such as supply chain agility, are implemented by established logistics companies. Since most publications do not focus on agile IT project management but on other areas of agility, such as supply chain and manufacturing agility, these are included here to show that agility itself is widespread in the logistics industry. No study is found for logistics start-ups. As the identified studies target specifically agile areas such as business agility, agile business model, and agile supply chain, this SLR could create the impression that established logistics companies are pioneers in the agile community. The opposite is the case. For the agile areas mentioned in the included studies like business agility, the definitions in the publications differ from the definitions that are rather new within the agile community (van Oosterhout, Waarts and van Hillegersberg, 2005; Narayan, 2015; Gonçalves, Ferreira and Campos, 2021; Ragas and Culp, 2021). In fact, the established logistics companies examined here have not yet made significant advancements with the agile transformation. The studies show that comparatively few agile methods and practices are used within these firms. Furthermore, it needs to be noted that established logistics companies do not see themselves as IT companies. That might be a reason for their rather late adaption of agile methods. In summary, it can be concluded that the use of agile methods and practices in established logistics companies is an important research topic and that there

is a research gap especially with regard to examining the use of agile methods and practices in logistics start-ups. In addition, the heterogeneity of the studied aspects in the relevant studies demonstrates that this is a complex research field with various influences from other fields that can and should be taken into account. Furthermore, this research field is closely related to existing work practices as most of the included studies base their research on real-life data.

Findings Research Question 1

Concerning the first RQ, in sum, XP, Scrum, and methods of other agile areas such as agile manufacturing and business agility are used by established logistics firms. No response can be given for logistics start-ups as no paper was available that focused on the use of agile methods and practices in start-ups. In terms of agile practices, established logistics companies mostly use agile guidelines such as the focus on continuous improvement, team empowerment, and customer focus. It needs to be noted that these guidelines are helpful to build a successful agile organisation but are not agile practices in a proper sense. In light of the missing studies on logistics start-ups, further research with regard to logistics start-ups and the use of agile methods and practices is required.

Findings Research Question 2

Benefits that established logistics companies aim to realise with agile methods and practices are clustered into customer-related benefits, product-related benefits, communication-related benefits, and processual and organisational benefits. As no study that focused on logistics start-ups is included, no specific benefits for logistics start-ups are identified. Through the use of agile methods and practices, established logistics companies increase their ability to satisfy changing customer requirements and reduce costs of products, as well as their speed in doing so. Other goals are to align business and IT through better communication, to reduce personnel bottlenecks and to deal with complex processes. To this end, it can be concluded that agile methods and practices can be helpful in realising these benefits.

Findings Research Question 3

The third RQ discusses difficulties that established logistics companies face when applying agile methods and practices and clusters the difficulties into product-related, processual, and people-related difficulties. No communication-related difficulties and no publications on logistics start-ups were found. Challenges when applying agile methods and practices are to find the right product

design that allows supply chain agility, to identify drivers that increase agility, and most demanding of all, creating an agile culture and introducing an agile mindset. Even though this is but one of many people-related difficulties, it should not be underestimated, as the success of agile methods and practices depends strongly upon the support and comprehension of employees.

4.2.5. Limitations of the systematic literature review

Due to the large quantity of published literature, there may be some papers that are missed even though a predefined research protocol is followed to ensure the completeness of this study and reduce the threat of systematic errors. Additionally, the completeness of the SLR strongly depends on selected keywords and limitations of the digital libraries. For the definition of the keywords an iterative approach is chosen to develop an extensive list of keywords. Keywords applied in related SLRs are used initially and enhanced if the keyword list is not able to find state-of-the-art publications in the research field of this SLR. Multiple search engines with different focuses are used to reduce limitations of the individual search engines. Moreover, the risk of incompleteness is addressed through forward and backward snowballing, which also reduces the risk of bias in the selection process. The author decided carefully which papers were relevant and should be included. Performing these selection steps might cause a certain degree of subjectivity. The chosen selection criteria are possibly another weakness of this SLR because, for example, only papers written in English language are included, meaning that other possibly relevant studies written in other languages are excluded (e.g. German publications such as Göpfert and Seeßle, 2019; Sucky and Asdecker, 2019; Fottner and Hietschold, 2018; Schwemmer, 2019; Wegner, 2019).

The results of this SLR indicate that, so far, only a few publications cover established logistics companies' and start-ups' use of agile methods and practices. Agile methods are not always applied as described in theory, which limits the analysis, as the data from different publications is difficult to compare. To overcome this, definitions of agile methods and practices are compared (see Section 4.2.3.3. - Results SLR, page 92).

Eight of the fifteen identified publications use case studies. Results of case studies may not necessarily be generalised. This limitation is reduced through the case studies themselves as they provide different perspectives and allow various insights into the application of agile methods in logistics industry.

Finally, no paper that covered the use of agile methods and practices in logistics start-ups is found.

4.3. Conclusion of the scoping study and the SLR

This chapter provides the background for understanding the concepts of logistics companies, IT and agile methods based on a scoping study. Several areas of agility are presented to enable a distinction of agile IT project management methods from other agile areas. To understand agile methods more deeply, their history and the most important agile methods are described. Furthermore, it is expressed how the logistics industry is understood in this study and what aspects distinguish established logistics companies from logistics start-ups. Finally, the relevance of software development for the logistics industry is explained to facilitate the understanding of the context of this study. The background presented creates a foundation for the discussion of the results of the studies presented in the following chapters.

The second section presents an SLR on the use of agile methods and practices by established logistics companies and logistics start-ups. The aim of the SLR is to apprehend the current state of publications related to the integrated fields of established logistics companies, logistics start-ups and agility. This review is based on guidelines provided by Kitchenham and Charters (Kitchenham and Charters, 2007). 12,090 papers are identified in the initial search without restrictions, and 112 through the snowballing technique. To reduce the number of findings, the search process is carried out in different steps. In total, only fifteen studies are classified as relevant and analysed in subsequent steps. In the first phase, a quality assessment is performed to evaluate the quality of each publication. The publications are then sorted quantitatively according to research method, publication date, and channel. All papers included are published after 1999.

Another aim of this SLR is to determine where the research fits into the current body of knowledge of researchers and practitioners. Based on a qualitative analysis of the included studies, it can be concluded that a shared understanding of the use of agile methods and practices is not very well established neither in the logistics industry nor in research. Through a deeper analysis of the relevant studies it becomes clear that only a limited number of papers explored the use of agile methods and practices in the logistics industry. No paper could be found that looks into the use of agile methods and practices in logistics start-ups. For all three RQs answers are found, but only from the perspective of established logistics companies. The RQs are appropriate and are used as well for the empirical studies that follow (see Section 6 and 7 – Delphi study and survey, page 103 and page 130). For established logistics companies, the SLR displays that only a few agile methods and practices are used. However, the concept of agility is an important factor in established logistics companies, which

is shown through the application of other agile areas and guidelines of logistics companies. Three agile methods are determined – Scrum, XP and Crystal – that are applied by some of the established logistics companies. Additionally, a range of other agile areas (business agility, supply chain agility, etc.) and guidelines (alignment of business and IT, empowerment of teams, etc.) that are used to support the concept of agility are described. Several benefits that can be realised with agile methods and practices are identified, as well as difficulties that can arise when using agile methods and practices.

Industrial practitioners can utilise these findings as guidelines to learn about the use of agile methods and practices from the experiences of other logistics companies.

To summarise, it needs to be noted that the SLR determines the need for more empirical studies that work on the use of agile methods and practices covering logistics companies and especially logistics start-ups. In addition, it can be concluded that there is heterogeneity among logistics companies regarding the use of agile methods and practices. There are publications that focus on the use of agile methods and practices in established logistics companies, but there are no publications for logistics start-ups. Seven of the fifteen papers are published between 2018 and 2020. This underlines the increase in research in this field and the relevance of future research projects.

5. Delphi study

In the previous chapters, the results of the interviews and the SLR conducted are described. To answer the research questions that are developed based on the findings of the interviews and to reduce the research gap that is validated in the SLR views of experts are gathered. A modified Delphi study is conducted based on approved guidelines (Dalkey and Helmer, 1963; Linstone and Turoff, 2002; Diamond et al., 2014). In this chapter, the selected experts and the Delphi study results are presented.

The aim of this Delphi study is to collect real life data to identify agile methods and practices used in established logistics companies and logistics start-ups. The objective is to understand the benefits logistics companies realise through the use of agile methods, but also the difficulties they face when using them. Additionally, the results of the Delphi study are used as empirical data source for the framework that will consolidate the findings of this study (see chapter 7.2. – Development of the framework, page 159).

5.1. Selection of experts

For this Delphi study participants are expected to have deep expert knowledge on the use of agile methods and practices in the IT departments of established logistics companies and logistics start-ups (Okoli and Pawlowski, 2004). As expertise is difficult to assess, a systematic classification is conducted (Sackman, 1975; Clayton, 1997). Participants are selected based on their expertise in the field of logistics and, more specifically, for their experience with agile methods and practices.

In the first round, invitations are sent to 37 experts who work in established German logistics companies and German logistics start-ups. These 37 experts are known to the researcher in different ways. Some participants from the logistics start-ups were already participating in the interviews. Other acquaintances are made at conferences or on previous project assignments.

A total of 29 experts from 29 companies with headquarters in Germany take part in the study. In the second round, 24 participants filled out the questionnaire, and in the third round, 22 questionnaires are completed. In order to achieve reliable results, a minimum number of 10-15 panellists is suggested in the literature (Dalkey, 1969; Lilja, Laakso and Palomäki, 2011).

All experts participating in the Delphi study are professionals who are presently working in the areas of logistics or agile IT consulting on projects in logistics companies and usually have several years of professional experience. The participants are mostly members of top management, project managers, agile coaches and scrum masters. Other participants are department heads, software

developers, product managers and business analysts. As a wide range of experts participate, a variety of diverse views can be integrated (Okoli and Pawlowski, 2004). The distribution of the different roles of the participants in the first round can be found in Figure 21.

Figure 21: Roles of the experts of the Delphi study in their organisations

Source: Own representation

The participating experts are also asked to assess their prior knowledge with regard to agile methods. 20 out of 29 participants, close to 70%, rated their prior knowledge on a scale from one to seven as five or higher (see Table 21). 16 of the 29 participants have three or more years of experience with the use of agile methods and practices.

Table 21: Expertise of experts of the Delphi study in agile methods rated by themselves

(1 = No know-how, 7 = Very extensive know-how)

Scale of know-how	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Number of participants (N = 29)	0	1	2	6	6	13	1

The experts are informed of the type of employing company (established logistics company; logistics start-up) of the other panel members. This ensures that the experts do not have the feeling that they can say anything, as accountability is eliminated because of the anonymity of the experts in this study (Sackman, 1975).

Approximately 45% of the companies are founded within the last 10 years and are therefore classified as start-ups (see Figure 22). In total, 15 out of 29 participants are from established logistics companies. More than 25% of all participating companies are founded within the last three years. The details can be found in the following diagram:

Figure 22: Age of the logistics companies participating in the Delphi study

Source: Own representation

14 of the participants come from companies with more than 500 employees. In comparison, eight of the participants come from companies with fewer than 30 employees (see Figure 23). Although all start-ups have less than 500 employees, the Delphi study aims not to compare large and small companies. Besides age, the start-ups examined are also (highly) innovative in relation to their technology and/or their business model. The innovativeness of logistics start-ups is evaluated based on services/ products offered during the preliminary interviews, through conversations on logistics conferences or through personal conversations.

Figure 23: Number of employees of the companies participating in the Delphi study

Source: Own representation

Participants indicated that only a minority of projects are carried out purely in accordance with the conventional waterfall model; often a hybrid approach is taken, or even work is carried out entirely in an agile manner (see Figure 24).

Figure 24: Team organisation of the companies participating in the Delphi study
Source: Own representation

5.2. Results of the Delphi study

During the three complementary rounds of the Delphi study, answers for the three RQs are discovered which are described in the following. For the RQs, results of all three rounds are presented.

5.2.1. Results of the Delphi study relevant to research question 1

To address the first RQ, the experts are inquired what agile methods and practices are used in their teams. In the following, the results of the three rounds are presented successively.

Results of the first round of the Delphi study

The agile method used most frequently by established logistics companies and by logistics start-ups is Scrum (see Figure 25). This is succeeded by: Kanban, Lean startup, XP and FDD. It is noteworthy that start-ups appear to apply older agile methods such as XP and FDD more regularly than established logistics companies. More than 80% of the participants stated that they prepare to use additional agile methods, especially methods for scaling Scrum such as SAFe (Ebert and Paasivaara, 2017) and LeSS (Larman and Vodde, 2016). It seems that logistics companies, especially the start-ups, are planning to scale their agile (IT) teams.

These findings can be contrasted with the results of the *13th State of Agile Report* (VersionOne, 2019). The *State of Agile Report* is carried out by CollabNet VersionOne and gathers answers from more than 1,000 participants across the world, from different industries and company sizes, on the use of agile methods. According to the results of the *State of Agile Report*, Scrum is the most widely applied method as well. However, in the *State of Agile Report* this is succeeded by Scrumban and a number of other hybrid approaches. The agile methods Lean startup and XP are only mentioned in 2% and 1% of the cases in the *State of Agile Report*. For scaling agile teams, the *State of Agile Report* states that most companies use SAFe, Scrum of Scrum or LeSS (VersionOne, 2019).

Figure 25: Agile methods used by the companies participating in the Delphi study

Source: Own representation

As “Other methods” participants state in free text boxes that they use “Scrumban”, where “practices from both methods (Scrum and Kanban) are combined” or “other mixed forms of methods to address the specific needs of the company's situation or the skills/strengths of the employees”. Additionally, one participant states that they use parts of the classical Waterfall approach.

Focusing on agile practices, “Daily Standups” succeeded by “Close exchange within the team”, “Reviews” and “Retrospectives” are overall employed most frequently. For logistics start-ups “Creation of minimum viable products” as well as “Joint team planning” through “Daily Standups” and “Sprint Planning” meetings are very important. For established logistics companies “Use of task boards like Kanban boards”, “Close exchange within the team” and “Feedback from the customer” are the agile practices applied most frequently (see Appendix A.6.1., page 255).

If this is compared with the results of the 13th *State of Agile Report*, it becomes clear that “Daily Standups”, “Sprint Planning”, “Retrospective” and “Iterative collection of customer feedback” are the most common practices (VersionOne, 2019). The logistics industry appears to use agile methods in a similar way to other industries.

In the free text boxes, experts add that they apply further agile practices such as “Definitions of ready” and “Mob programming”. The comment below clarifies how “Definitions of ready” are applied in a participant's established logistics company: “We host a daily meeting for the Definition of ready,

which means we discuss upcoming stories/tasks, which can then be prioritised and implemented. We usually take 15 minutes for this.”

From a theoretical point of view, agile practices are a subset of agile methods (see Section 4.1.1. – Agile methods and practices, page 68). The findings of this Delphi study demonstrate that individual practices are applied frequently instead of a whole agile method. For example, in all participating companies “Daily Standups” take place. However, only 92% of logistics start-ups and 87% of established logistics companies work with the linked agile method Scrum. Looking at more technical agile practices such as “Refactoring” and “Pair Programming” the effect becomes even stronger: They are applied more often separately than the entire agile method XP. Other studies covering different industries validate this finding (Pikkarainen et al., 2008; Jalali and Wohlin, 2010; Diebold and Dahlem, 2014).

The participants who state that the top management had taken the initiative to use agile methods work in logistics start-ups in ten out of 14 cases (see Figure 26). Eight of these participants are members of the top management of the logistics start-ups themselves. About 50% of the participants from logistics start-ups and established logistics companies express that the original impulse for the application of agile methods comes from team colleagues, the team lead or was their own initiative.

Figure 26: Origin of the initiative for the use of agile methods in logistics companies of the Delphi study

Source: Own representation

In most of all cases, the team itself decides what agile methods they want to use. In some cases, the top management, the head of department or the team leader decide (see Figure 27). In half of the cases of logistics start-ups (seven out of 14 start-ups), the top management has a say in the selection

of agile methods. In established companies, top management is involved in only one case. This could be due to the fact that start-ups are often smaller and the top management is closer to the agile teams in terms of hierarchy. When looking at the results, it must be considered that this question allowed a multiple selection of answers.

The fact that in most cases the team (co-)decides what agile methods are used shows that principles from the Agile Manifesto are followed (Beck et al., 2001). The following two principles of the Agile Manifesto underline the importance of the self-organised team:

- *“Build projects around motivated individuals. Give them the environment and support they need, and trust them to get the job done.*
- *At regular intervals, the team reflects on how to become more effective, then tunes and adjusts its behaviour accordingly.”*

Figure 27: Decision makers when choosing the agile method in the companies participating in the Delphi study

Source: Own representation

Results of the second round of the Delphi study

In the second round, 25 of the 29 experts participate. To better understand why certain agile methods and practices are chosen for implementation in established logistics companies or logistics start-ups, experts are questioned about their selection criteria in the second round, which are set into quotation marks in the following. Participants can select multiple answers.

The criterion used most often for the selection of agile methods is “Previous experience”. Other criteria that experts apply are “Fit of the agile method to existing requirements”, “Applicability to the team size” and “Previous knowledge of employees”.

All eleven experts of the logistics start-ups state that they select agile methods based on their “Previous experience”. In established logistics companies, ten of the 14 experts confirm this. Of the four remaining experts from established logistics companies, three participants are supported in the selection of the method by external consultants or an agile coach. The fact that the criterion "Previous experience" is chosen most often is of special interest, as in the literature so far it is rather assumed that "Existing requirements" and "Goals of the team" are the most important selection criteria (Campanelli and Parreiras, 2015).

One expert of a logistics start-up expresses that in most cases the way they work develops over time. Once he completed the questionnaires of the Delphi study, he discovered that they really used FDD. Another experts specifies: “Although trying new things (“Inspect and Adapt”) is not a criterion for the selection [of agile methods], it determines my everyday life.” This approach is supported by the three core elements of the agile method Scrum which are “Inspect”, “Adapt” and “Transparency” (Schwaber, 2004).

More rarely, agile methods are selected on the basis of the “Image of the agile method” and their “Implementation costs”. However, in eight out of ten cases in which “Company guidelines” are applied to choose agile methods, Scrum is selected.

Figure 28 shows the division of selection criteria used by established logistics companies and logistics start-ups. It can be seen that these two types of companies use different selection criteria.

Figure 28: Selection criteria of established logistics companies and logistics start-ups participating in the Delphi study
Source: Own representation

Although the majority of decisions in both types of companies are made on the basis of “Previous experience”, established logistics companies follow more often the “Advice from external consultants and colleagues” and “Company guidelines”. Logistics start-ups select agile methods with a stronger focus on their “Fit to existing requirements” and “Applicability to team size”.

No specific connection between the role of the participant and his/ her hierarchical level and the selection criteria is identified.

In the Appendix (see A.6.2., page 264), a visualisation of the selection criteria clustered for the individual agile methods can be found. Additionally, an assessment of selection criteria of the participants is provided.

Results of the third round of the Delphi study

Participants are asked to what extent, on a scale of *one* to *seven*, they adapt agile methods and practices to their own circumstances (see Figure 29). *Seven* corresponds to following the pure form of the agile theory and *one* means maximum adaptation to one's own circumstances.

Figure 29: Adaption of agile methods of participants of the Delphi study

Source: Own representation

The bar chart shows that established logistics companies and logistics start-ups adapt agile methods to a comparable extent. This results in nearly similar values of the statistical evaluation (see Appendix A.6.3., page 280). On average, participants of established logistics companies tend to adapt agile methods a bit more than logistics start-ups.

In the literature, some studies show that especially when introducing agile methods, companies are more successful if they adhere strongly to the original guidelines of the agile methods (Campanelli and Parreiras, 2015). In these cases, the agile approach will only be adapted later, when experience has been gained in using the agile methods (Moreira, 2013; Dingsoeyr, Falessi and Power, 2019).

In the Delphi study, many of the participants state that they adapt the agile methods. This could be due to the experience of the participants in this study. Only participants with great expertise in agile methods are surveyed. It is possible that the experts surveyed adapt agile methods directly as they know which parameter matter. Especially participants who rank their own experience with agile methods higher adapt agile methods stronger.

5.2.2. Results of the Delphi study relevant to research question 2

To address the second question, participants are questioned on the reasons why they apply agile methods and practices. In the following, the results of the three rounds are presented successively.

Results of the first round of the Delphi study

The findings indicate that the reasons for using agile methods in logistics start-ups and established logistics companies are largely identical. It is primarily about responsiveness to changing priorities and requirements, acceleration of (product) delivery and more in-depth coordination between business and IT departments (see Figure 30).

The benefits of using agile methods seem to be very similar regardless of the size of the company. This is compared to the 13th *State of Agile Report*. It turns out that these benefits do not only apply to the logistics industry. In other industries, too, the most important benefits of using agile methods are the ability to react to changing requirements, the fast delivery of products/software, the increase in quality and the improved coordination between IT and the business (VersionOne, 2019).

Figure 30: Top reasons for the use of agile methods and practices in the Delphi study

Source: Own representation

Participants can choose up to four answers. One expert states the following: *“I think almost everything can be checked above, because there are so many dependencies. In our case it's mostly the experience the team made in the past with non-agile methodologies that led to low quality of a product and essentially development of the product nobody actually needs. So, team spirit and employee satisfaction is also there, because with agile methodologies less things go to waste.”*

This emphasises that the agile approach does not only focus on the customer value created and responsiveness - even though these answers come first in Figure 30 - in addition, it also concentrates on the satisfaction and motivation of the development team. This quote also stands for the approach of the Agile Manifesto, which emphasises the importance of the employees (Beck et al., 2001).

Results of the second round of the Delphi study

In the second round, questions are posed to deepen the insights from the first round. The findings show what agile practices are applied to realise specific benefits. The detailed analysis of these results is presented in the Appendix (see A.6.2., page 264).

Participants are asked to rank the effectiveness of agile practices used in realising benefits. Participants use a scale between “One” which represents a low effectiveness and “Seven” which stands for the highest effectiveness possible. For logistics start-ups “Applicability” and “Fit of agile

methods” are more important as selection criteria than for established logistics companies (see Figure 28, page 108). Nevertheless, established logistics companies rank the effectiveness of the agile practice chosen higher than logistics start-ups. For example, established logistics companies rate the effectiveness of their chosen practices for increasing responsiveness to external priorities on average at 5.6 whereas logistics start-ups rate the effectiveness of the practices at 5.3. However, this means that there is no convincing difference in evaluating the effectiveness of agile practices between participants from established logistics companies and logistics start-ups. The number of participants in the Delphi study is too small for extensive statistical analysis. In Table 22, the benefits are presented in order of their effectiveness for established logistics companies.

Table 22: Effectiveness of agile practices on realising benefits rated by the participants of the Delphi study

Benefits of the use of agile methods	Established logistics companies	Logistics start-ups
Respond to changing internal priorities	5.8	4.9
Respond to changing priorities / requirements by the customer	5.6	5.3
Increase product quality	5.6	5.6
Increase productivity	5.6	5.1
Increase transparency on status and impediments	5.4	5.1
Accelerate product delivery	5.4	5.1
Reduce project risk	5.4	5.0
Improve communication between the customer and the IT department	5.1	4.8
Average	5.5	5.1

Overall, across all agile practices and objectives, agile coaches and scrum master rate the effectiveness of the agile practices used quite high compared to other study participants. At this point, a future study could question the reason for this. Do the agile coaches and scrum masters have a different view on the use of agile practices? Or does their support of the team ensure that appropriate practices are used effectively by the team? Do agile coaches and scrum master want to appear effective or even necessary for the support of the team?

Results of the third round of the Delphi study

In the second round, the effectiveness of the agile practices used is rated lowest for the four benefits below (see Table 22). The lowest ratings combined from established logistics companies and logistics start-ups were taken into account here.

- Accelerated product delivery
- Improved communication between the customer and the IT department
- Transparency on impediments and status
- Reduced project risk

Therefore, in the third round participants are asked whether they think they are using the right practices to achieve the four benefits stated above. Participants are asked if they believe that they apply the agile practices correctly, whether they plan to replace the agile practice used with another practice or plan to introduce additional practice(s). The detailed findings can be found in the Appendix (see A.6.3., page 280).

A total of ten participants state that they used the most effective practice for each of the four benefits stated above. Four of the 22 participants stated not to use the most effective practice for each of the four objectives. The remaining eight participants indicated to use the correct practices for some of the four benefits. Future studies could observe the application of agile methods and practices in companies to interrogate whether these self-assessments of the participants are valid. It could be investigated whether, for example, practices such as regular “Retrospectives” help to select the most effective practice and adjust the application of the practice if necessary.

5.2.3. Results of the Delphi study relevant to research question 3

To address the third RQ, the experts are asked what challenges and difficulties occur applying and adapting and using agile methods and practices. In the following, the results of the three rounds are presented successively.

Results of the first round of the Delphi study

Overall, the distribution of challenges faced by logistics start-ups and established logistics companies in applying agile methods is quite similar. Looking at established logistics companies in more detail, they face stronger problems regarding the organisational culture and lack of willingness to embrace change than employees from logistics start-ups who seem to be more familiar with change.

Participants from logistics start-ups describe that their IT teams struggle with unbalanced distribution of knowledge. Both types of companies see the (partial) lack of knowledge about agile methods as a challenge.

Figure 31: Challenges of start-ups and established logistics companies using agile methods and practices in the Delphi study

Source: Own representation

One expert complements his answer with the following text: “I marked “lack of skills or knowledge in relation to agile methods” because being agile is more than following the Scrum ceremonies, it has to be a mindset, the way a person works every day - and this is hard to achieve, because a lot of people don't even understand the meaning behind agile. Hiring a scrum master doesn't make a team agile, having sprints doesn't make a team agile. Understanding of minimal viable product does.” Another expert notes that users have trouble in defining small requirements. This impedes the expert's team in developing minimal viable products. A further expert explains that, his/ her team does “not have a dedicated product owner and the executive management has the final say, especially on prioritisation issues”.

These responses reinforce the importance of the agile mindset and agile values. Implementing e.g. Scrum events does not lead to an agile organisation with self-organised teams, but the right mindset can make a difference in the way problems are addressed and customer value is provided.

Considering the different roles of the participants, agile coaches and scrum masters rate the organisational culture, especially the lack of knowledge about agile methods and the resistance to change as challenging. Comparatively, the unbalanced distribution of knowledge within the teams, the lack of product owners and the lack of customer feedback are the perceived challenges of top management and department heads in relation to the use of agile methods. This demonstrates that, in most cases, these roles have different educational and professional backgrounds and significantly different objectives with regard to the introduction and use of agile methods.

Results of the second round of the Delphi study

The second round of the Delphi study focuses on the way agile methods are introduced in logistics organisations and the challenges that occur during the introduction. Twelve participants were or are still taking part in an agile transformation. In contrast, eleven out of the 23 participants state, that they used agile methods right from the beginning of project or company foundation itself (see Figure 32). More than 50% of the participants from logistics start-ups state that they have already used agile methods directly from the beginning. In this study, start-ups are defined as being younger than ten years. Many agile methods originated in the 1990s. That means, that many agile methods already existed when the start-ups were founded. Possibly, it was easier for logistics start-ups than for established logistics companies to use agile methods right from the start instead of introducing them and going through a transformation. Additionally, it may also be that start-ups are under more time pressure, especially at the beginning, to establish themselves on the market in order to earn money. One principle of agile methods is the fast delivery of products to enable direct feedback. This approach could be of high relevance especially for start-ups.

Figure 32: Number and status of agile transformations in logistics companies in the Delphi study

Source: Own representation

Only the twelve participants who state that they have experienced an agile transformation are asked the following questions about the process of the transformation. Of these twelve participants, nine work in established logistics companies, while three come from logistics start-ups.

Two of three participants from logistics start-ups describe that their agile transformation has been driven by people who only work part time on the transformation as they also have to fulfil other tasks. This reflects an approach that is often used and necessary in start-ups. Responsibilities, which are often spread more widely among individuals in larger companies, have to be bundled in start-ups into fewer employees due to a lower number of staff. In three established logistics companies, a dedicated team with team members that only work on the agile transformation is formed. Only one participant from an established logistics company states that they were supported by external consultants during the transformation.

Figure 33: Different types of transformation teams were used by the experts in the Delphi study

Source: Own representation

In total, agile transformations were planned step by step in an iterative way in ten of twelve companies. This means that there was a pre-planned transformation roadmap in only two of the twelve companies. In all three logistics start-ups, the transition to agile methods was carried out iteratively. This could be related to the fact that especially young (logistics) start-ups have to react very quickly and with a smaller number of employees to changes in order to find their position in the market. This makes it more difficult to follow a pre-planned roadmap. 78% of established logistics companies have taken a step-by-step approach to agile transformation, 22% have followed a transformation roadmap.

Figure 34: The transformation was planned either iteratively or as a fixed plan in advance by the experts of the Delphi study
Source: Own representation

The results show, that all participants from logistics start-ups answered that they have started their agile transformation with a small pilot. This reflects the results of the previous question, which showed that logistics start-ups prefer to perform a step-by-step agile transformation.

Figure 35: Different approaches used in the transformation by the experts of the Delphi study
Source: Own representation

In most of the cases, established logistics companies start with a small pilot project as well. In one case, the small pilot was also a strategically important project at the same time. This means that one participant has selected two answer options which is why there are 13 instead of twelve answers for

this multiple choice question. Three participants from established logistics companies describe that they changed the entire IT department from day X and did not start with smaller pilot projects. A reason might be that it is often difficult when small pilots follow the agile approach but are surrounded by an environment and overall processes that are based on a classical Waterfall approach.

In addition, one participant states that the general approach and guidelines are predefined from the management, but that the concrete introduction of agile methods is decided on team level.

Looking at the recommended guidelines and lessons learned from agile transformation, management support is most important in established logistics companies as well as in logistics start-ups. It is interesting to note that even though teams aim to work in a self-organised manner, especially after the agile transformation, full support of the management is still needed for the transformation. It is not only important that the transformation is approved, but also that the necessary resources (time, coaches, trainings, new office space, etc.) are made available. For established logistics companies, a promotion of a new organisational culture and the early involvement of employees is crucial. For logistics start-ups, the focus on agile principles instead of processes is essential.

Figure 36: Recommendations for the agile transformation by the experts of the Delphi study

Source: Own representation

Results of the third round of the Delphi study

In the third round, participants are asked to answer multiple choice questions to describe the effects on the organisation of the following five challenges. These five challenges are selected as they are ranked as most critical in the first round of the Delphi study.

- Unequal distribution of knowledge
- Strict organisational culture
- Fear of change
- Incomplete knowledge of agile methods
- Availability of the product owner

In the following effects of the individual difficulties are presented. Effects are gathered based on the results of other publications (Pikkarainen et al., 2008; Jovanović et al., 2017; VersionOne, 2019). The first challenge analysed is the unequal distribution of knowledge. The participants' replies are quite similarly spread over the different effects of unequal distribution of knowledge, regardless of whether they work in an established logistics company or a logistics start-up.

Figure 37: Effects of an uneven distribution of knowledge in the team on the use of agile methods assessed by the experts of the Delphi study

Source: Own representation

In four established logistics companies, the lack of T-Shaping, i.e. the improvement of the skills of the team members and their ability to work across disciplines, is a problem. No participant from a logistics start-up claims this to be a problem. Overall participants from both types of companies describe that an uneven distribution of knowledge hinders the cooperation within the team and the distribution of tasks.

With regard to organisational culture, the participants explain that in most cases strict hierarchies limit the advantages of the agile approach. In established logistics companies, the aspect of responsibility of the team is limited through a strict organisational culture. On the one hand, participants articulate a lack of individual responsibility of team members. On the other hand, the participants express that the team's independent way of working is disrespected by supervisors. In logistics start-ups, the organisational culture has a particularly strong influence on the ability to talk openly about mistakes and on the agile mindset in general.

Figure 38: Effects of a strict organisational culture on the use of agile methods assessed by the experts of the Delphi study
Source: Own representation

With regard to the fear of change of employees, the participants have very different opinions. Participants from established logistics companies confirm that due to fear of change, teams are not able to develop in the best possible way, do not adopt the agile approach quickly enough and do not react flexible to changes. Participants from logistics start-ups describe that the teams do not deepen their knowledge as much as possible and cannot deliver the greatest possible value added for the customer.

Figure 39: Effects of fear of change on the use of agile methods assessed by the experts of the Delphi study

Source: Own representation

Clustering the effects that result from fear of change, it becomes clear that established logistics companies tend to have an internal problem with the fear of changes regarding the agile transformation. On the other hand, employees in logistics start-ups cannot serve customers in the best possible way due to the fear of change of the product. One participant says that they have no problem at all with fear of change as their team that is staffed with young employees deals with change on a daily basis.

Figure 40: Effects of incomplete knowledge of agile methods on the use of agile methods assessed by the experts of the Delphi study

Source: Own representation

Given the incomplete knowledge of agile methods, established logistics companies and logistics start-ups agree on the effects: incomplete knowledge of agile methods can prevent that the greatest

possible value added is generated for the customer when the agile methods are not used correctly. In addition, the incorrect use of agile methods can limit the responsibility agile teams assume.

Figure 41: Effects of the lack of product owners on the use of agile methods assessed by the experts of the Delphi study

Source: Own representation

If the product owner is missing, participants describe that the agile team is blocked as a clear prioritisation of tasks is missing. Additionally, the lack of the product owner possibly reduces the responsibility the whole team has for the success of the product. The product owner needs to be available to answer functional questions at short notice. Participants from established logistics companies and logistics start-ups assent with another on these consequences.

5.3. Implication of the findings

In the following, the results and their implications are discussed more closely.

General findings of the Delphi study

Comparing the findings of the Delphi study with the identified benefits of other (modified) Delphi Studies (see Section 2.5.3. – Identification of related work, page 36), it can be verified that by using the iterative approach of Delphi studies and taking advantage of the benefits of Delphi studies, the RQs can be addressed. The purpose of this Delphi study is to reduce the identified research gap. The SLR (see Section 4.2. – SLR, page 88) which was conducted previously confirmed that no studies could be identified that examined the use of agile project management methods in the IT departments of established logistics companies or in logistics start-ups. This Delphi study has the ability to identify agile methods and practices used in the IT departments of established logistics companies and logistics start-ups. The findings of the Delphi study contribute significantly to the development of

the framework (see Section 7 – Framework, page 155). Furthermore, the experts are asked in successive rounds about the advantages of using agile methods and the difficulties in introducing and applying them. The iterative nature of the Delphi study made it possible to scrutinise the experts' statements in greater depth and also to respond to unexpected findings. The meanings of the results of the three RQs are explained below.

Findings Research Question 1

Summarising the first RQ, Scrum, and Kanban are the agile methods used most frequently in both established logistics companies and logistics start-ups. Looking at agile practices, “Daily Standups” succeeded by a “Close exchange within the team”, “Reviews” and “Retrospectives” are most common. Additionally, several logistics start-ups create “Minimum viable products”. Choosing these agile methods and practices is mainly done on the basis of the following criteria: “Previous experience”, “Fit to special company requirements” and “Team size”. Established logistics companies also frequently take “Company guidelines” and the “Advice of external consultants” into account.

Findings Research Question 2

The most relevant benefits that established logistics companies and logistics start-ups aim to realise with agile methods and practices are the responsiveness to changing internal and external requirements, acceleration of product delivery, and optimisation of the alignment between the customers/ users and the IT departments. “Sprint Plannings”, “Regular feedback cycles with the customers” and “Regular (software) delivery” are widely used to achieve these benefits.

Findings Research Question 3

Fear and resistance to change and organisational culture hinder the introduction and use of agile methods. Especially in established logistics companies, these mindset-related matters appear to be a significant problem. Logistics start-ups frequently fight with a lack of knowledge distribution in their agile teams and the absence of product owners.

5.4. Limitations of the Delphi study

Since the design of a questionnaire is crucial for the data gathering process, several pre-tests were performed with researchers and company experts for all three rounds. Yet, it is impossible to eliminate the possibility that nuances in the answers are lost in this type of online questionnaire. For

this reason, the experts had the opportunity to complete their answers to closed questions in free-text fields. After each round of the questionnaire, a report of the results was generated and sent to the participants for feedback. In these reports, subjective decisions about the selected aspects were made. This can lead to biases in the panel's opinion-forming process in subsequent rounds. Through a precise data analysis and the involvement of two additional researchers, an attempt was made to ensure that this effect was minimised. The number of participants decreased from 29 to 22 participants over the three rounds of the Delphi study. This could possibly have led to selection effects. For example, it is conceivable that especially participants with a positive reference to agile methods participated in all three rounds and thus the assessments of agile methods are more positive than they are in reality. In addition, there are limitations to validity due to the uneven distribution of the roles of the participants, which is particularly significant with the rather low number of participants. 13 of the 29 experts in the first round belong to top management or are project managers. More widely distributed, but much closer to the team, are a total of ten experts who are either agile coaches or scrum master, developers, business analysts or architects. Due to their proximity to the development teams, these ten experts provide a good counterbalance to the 13 managers (see Figure 21, page 102). In the Delphi study, only participants from German logistics companies are surveyed. Finally, it should be pointed out that a survey (see Section 6 – Survey, page 130) is applied to gain deeper knowledge into the use of agile methods of established logistics companies and logistics start-ups. For a deeper exploration, case studies could also be beneficial to understand what established logistics companies and start-up logistics companies can learn from each other.

5.5. Assessment of the methodological approach

The Delphi approach is chosen for several reasons which are explained in the following. In addition, for each reason, an evaluation based on the experiences made in this study is carried out to determine whether the Delphi approach proves its value in this study.

Gather the opinion of experts on an unexplored research field

This Delphi study is not primarily used to reach a consensus within the expert group on the research topic but to collect information on the actual use of agile methods and practices in established logistics companies and logistics start-ups. A modified Delphi approach is used that allows the adaption of the questionnaire between the individual rounds based on the findings of the previous rounds (Dalkey and Helmer, 1963; Linstone and Turoff, 2002; Diamond et al., 2014). An iterative

expert assessment process (Dalkey, 1969) is carried out to gather insights on the use of agile methods and practices in established logistics companies and logistics start-ups.

The collection of information in the rather unexplored field of research (use of agile methods in logistics companies) is successful (for Limitations see 5.4., page 125). Among other things, in-depth information about the agile methods and practices used, the reasons for their use, selection criteria and challenges are obtained.

Iterative Approach

The Delphi approach makes it possible to deal with unexpected results directly in the next round, as the questionnaire is only created after the results of the previous round(s) are evaluated and discussed. Consequently, previously unexpected results can be addressed directly. This allows finding answers on the RQs in greater depth.

In this research, the questionnaires of the second and third round are developed based on the results of the previous round(s). Therefore, it is possible to address e.g. rather unexpected facts such as logistics start-ups using older agile methods like Crystal and XP besides more common methods like Scrum. In the next round, it was possible to question how and why the methods are selected and in which situations these methods are used. In this study, the use of an iterative approach allows to answer the RQs and elaborate on unexpected findings.

Quantitative and qualitative results

Using the Delphi approach mainly qualitative questions are asked in the first round to gather knowledge especially on so far rather unexplored research topics (Goodman, 1987; Lummus, Vokurka and Duclos, 2005). In the following rounds qualitative results of the first round are normally quantified or, if necessary, qualitatively elaborated further (Lilja, Laakso and Palomäki, 2011; Brady, 2015).

In this study, in order to build up knowledge about the so far unexplored research topic of the use of agile methods in logistics companies, qualitative questions are asked in the first round. Additionally, organisational questions about e.g. origin and previous experience of the experts with regard to agile methods and a few quantitative questions are asked. Through the qualitative questions the participants have the chance to communicate knowledge and opinions. The qualitative results are quantified in the following rounds and if necessary qualitative questions are asked to question different topics more deeply. Even though the amount of quantitative questions increased in the second and third round, in

each round there was the opportunity to give qualitative feedback on the quantitative questions. The mixture of open and closed questions is considered helpful to answer the RQs in depth.

Anonymity

In general, the Delphi approach is used as an anonymous approach. The idea is to ensure anonymity of the experts to decrease the risk of group opinion and restrict the influence of dominant experts (Dalkey and Helmer, 1963; Sackman, 1975). Experts can view the perspectives of their colleagues anonymously e.g. through anonymous discussion groups or the results that are sent to the experts in between the round as a report (Dalkey and Helmer, 1963; Linstone and Turoff, 2002). This gives the experts the possibility to rethink their own answers.

Anonymity of experts is particularly important for this research to prevent individual participants from presenting their company differently from how it is in reality. In this study, the anonymity of the individual participants and their logistics companies can be preserved. In the reports it is only described how many participants come from established logistics companies and how many come from logistics start-ups. The advantage of anonymity is used to receive answers from the participants that reflect reality.

Structure group communication

Delphi is characterised as a method that structures group communication processes effectively so that a group of individuals, as a whole, can deal with complex problems (Linstone and Turoff, 2002). Through consecutive rounds and results that are sent to the experts or discussion panels, communication can be structured.

In this study, the subsequent rounds 2 and 3 of the Delphi study are used to deepen the results of the first round. The results of the all rounds are sent to the participants as preparation for the next round. This allows the experts to compare their responses with the responses of other experts and gives them feedback on how their own answers fit into the group. Participants have the chance to comment on the results of each round including the final third round. The report with the results is the basis for the participation in the following Delphi rounds and allows a gradual assessment of the research problem. It was important that the participants continue to participate in the individual question rounds. With the help of the structured Delphi approach more and more detailed results are found step by step. By dividing the study into three consecutive rounds it was possible to refer to individual answers from the preliminary rounds to examine them.

Realistic picture of “the truth”

In social research there are several reasons to rely on the Delphi approach to create valuable insights (Dalkey and Helmer, 1963; Linstone and Turoff, 2002; Diamond et al., 2014). To understand social phenomena it is helpful to collect the opinions of the actors and experts themselves. Delphi is described as a useful approach to gather the judgement of a large group of experts.

Given the ambiguous interpretation and application of agile methods and practices, which are socially oriented methods (Beck, 2000; Schwaber and Beedle, 2002), advantages described above are highly relevant in the context of this study.

Overall, the central goal of this study is to conduct a controlled, iterative, expert-based, qualitative communication procedure that attempts to arrive at a coherent body of opinions on a particular research topic (Deschene, Don Gottwald and Clifford, 2016).

5.6. Conclusion

This Delphi study identifies the agile methods and practices used by established logistics companies and logistics start-ups as well as the benefits and challenges of agile methods. For this reason, an iterative expert judgement process was conducted. This process comprised three complementary Delphi rounds. Based on the views of 29 experts working in 15 established logistics companies and 14 logistics start-ups, the panel is familiar with the application of agile methods and practices. Through the identification of the most relevant methods and practices, benefits and challenges, the study adds to the body of knowledge in the field of logistics. Scrum and Kanban are rated as the most essential methods, “Daily Standups”, “Use of task boards such as Kanban boards”, and “Close exchange within the team and with the customer” are identified as the most widespread practices. The main reasons for using agile methods are to be responsive to change and to reduce time-to-market. The main challenges are organisational cultures that contradict agile values and an imbalanced distribution of knowledge in agile teams. In the next chapter a survey is conducted to deepen the findings of the Delphi study with participants from logistics start-ups worldwide.

6. Survey

In the previous chapter, the results of the Delphi study, which begins the work of closing the research gap identified through the SLR, are described. To further reduce the research gap, a survey is sent to experts from logistics start-ups worldwide to deepen the findings of the Delphi study. In this chapter, the survey results are presented.

The goal of the survey is to expand the findings from the Delphi study with a broader group of employees from logistics start-ups. Fundamental questions are asked about the application of agile methods and practices and about the benefits and challenges of using said methods. Further questions are derived based on the results of the Delphi study, which are tested by the broad-based survey. Additionally, the results of the survey are used as another empirical data source for the framework that consolidates the findings of this study (see Section 7 – Framework, page 155). The survey is conducted based on established guidelines (Kitchenham et al., 2002; Molléri, Petersen and Mendes, 2016).

6.1. Sample size

Potential survey participants work for logistics start-ups around the world. The researcher identified potential participants in databases such as Crunchbase but also through an e-mailing list from the “Logistik-Initiative Hamburg”. If the e-mail addresses of the identified participants could not be found they were assumed to be based on the following set phrase: givenname.surname@start-upname.com. The first and last names of potential participants for whom no final address was available were included in the set, together with the name of the logistics company. In total, the four-page questionnaire was e-mailed to 4,176 potential participants: 2,183 e-mails could not be successfully served by the e-mail service providers. A reminder was subsequently dispatched to those who did not respond and to those who only began to fill out the questionnaire but did not finish it. Overall, 95 participants filled out the questionnaire completely and provided utilisable answers. 228 participants began filling out the questionnaire but did not finish it.

The survey primarily involved members of top management, department heads, product managers and product owners. Participants who selected "Other" either work as business process managers, agile mastery leaders, account managers, strategy managers or data scientists; thus experts in different roles in logistics start-ups took part in the survey. Through these different roles, a variety of different

perspectives can be incorporated (Passmore et al., 2002). In Figure 42, the distribution of different roles can be seen.

Figure 42: Roles of the survey participants

Source: Own representation

Participants were questioned since when they had been using agile methods in order to assess their experience with them: more than 50% the participants have more than three years of experience using agile methods.

Figure 43: Years of experience of the survey participants with the use of agile methods

Source: Own representation

The participating experts were questioned about their prior knowledge with regard to agile methods. 37 out of the 77 participants who answered the question rated their prior knowledge on a scale from “One” to “Seven” as “Five” or higher (see Table 23), i.e. nearly 50% rate their experience as “Five” or higher.

Table 23: Expertise of the survey participants

(1 = No know-how, 7 = Very extensive know-how)

Scale of know-how	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Number of participants (N = 77)	6	12	9	13	16	12	9

The participants knew in which type of company (logistics start-ups) the other participants were currently working. This avoids the participants from feeling that they can say anything, as the experts' anonymity in this study precludes accountability (Sackman, 1975).

Out of the 95 participants, the country of origin could only be identified for 54 as the other participants did not state their e-mail addresses which were used to identify the countries of origin. The participants come from 13 different countries, 37 of them from Germany (see Figure 44).

Figure 44: Origin of logistics start-ups of the survey participants

Source: Own representation

Approximately 74% of participants' companies were founded within the last five years (see Figure 45) and 94% of the start-ups were founded within the last ten years, which is one of the criteria for the classification as a start-up in this study. Answers from six participants from logistics companies older than ten years are included as well, as the participants still classified their companies as "start-ups". The details can be found in the following diagram:

Figure 45: Ages of the logistics start-ups employing the survey participants

Source: Own representation

About 79% of the participants come from companies with fewer than 50 employees. About 65% of the participants come from companies with fewer than 30 employees (see Figure 46). All logistics start-ups that have more than 250 employees were founded at least five years ago. Even though the survey data shows that older logistics start-ups tend to have more employees, three participants from logistics start-ups younger than three years but with more than 100 employees took part in the survey.

Figure 46: Number of employees at survey participants' logistics start-ups

Source: Own representation

Only 11% of the participants work in accordance with the traditional waterfall model; often a hybrid approach is used or the participants work in a fully agile way (see Figure 47).

Figure 47: Distribution of project management approaches applied by the survey participants

Source: Own representation

More than 62% of the participants work in teams of more than two but fewer than nine people (see Figure 48), which is the prescribed size for teams according to most agile methods (Schwaber, 2004).

Figure 48: Size of the team of the survey participants

Source: Own representation

6.2. Division of data into clusters

When analysing the data, the results are either clustered according to the age of the start-ups or displayed without further clustering. As can be seen from the analysis of the data, there are some variations in the use of agile methods in start-ups of different ages. To guarantee completeness, other possible categories are also examined to explore whether another type of classification might also be of interest. Other categories examined are the country of origin of the start-up, the number of employees, whether the start-up is asset-based or asset-light, the roles of the stakeholders, the roles of the initiators and the choice of agile methods. Significant differences that were found are described

below. Chi-square tests with $p = 0.05$ were applied to determine significance. An overview of the categories tested can be seen in A.8. (see page 295).

Looking at the logistics start-ups based in Germany and comparing them to the start-ups from the rest of the world, it is noticeable that in Germany, the prevalence of agile methods other than Scrum is higher. Participants that come from a German start-up use Kanban more often than the participants from other countries and more often than participants who did not specify their e-mail address and for whom, therefore, the country of origin could not be determined.

Comparing the logistics start-ups based on their size, it is clear that start-ups with between 100 and 250 employees and start-ups with 500 or more employees use many support measures when introducing agile methods. The start-ups in these groups also encounter a particularly large number of challenges when using the agile methods. This is comparable to the volume of support measures and challenges of start-ups between three and five years old and those older than ten years.

Analysing the roles of the participants, it is noticeable that agile coaches and scrum masters use agile practices more often and follow the guidelines more closely. Agile coaches state more frequently than participants with other roles that scaling methods such as SAFe and LeSS are used. Furthermore, agile coaches and scrum masters rate the realisation of benefits through the use of agile methods higher than top managers or department heads do.

No significant differences are discovered when the data is clustered according to the categories “asset-based” or “asset-light”, or “initiators” and “selectors” of the agile methods. As no fundamental differences could be found, the results are presented in clusters based on the ages of the start-ups.

6.3. Results of the survey

Summarising the results of the questionnaire, deepening answers for all three RQs are found. They are described in the following.

6.3.1. Results of the survey relevant to research question 1

To address the first RQ, the participants are asked which agile methods and practices are applied in their teams. It was possible for the participants to select multiple answers.

Survey results show that Scrum is the agile method used most by logistics start-ups (see Figure 49). This is followed by Kanban, Lean startup, FDD, XP, and agile scaling methods such as LeSS and SAFe. Participants are also asked which agile methods they plan to implement in the future.

Interestingly, fewer than 10% of the participants state that they are preparing to use further agile methods. The results show that only very few logistics start-ups use scaling methods like LeSS and SAFe, and that only few start-ups plan to use these scaling methods in the future. These scaling methods enable the coordination and communication of several software teams that work on the same product or project (Larman and Vodde, 2016). This differs from the findings of the Delphi study, which was conducted with participants from German logistics start-ups and established logistics companies in 2020 (see Section 5 – Delphi study, page 103). In the Delphi study, more than 80% of the participants are planning the implementation of additional agile methods. However, similar to the findings of the Delphi study, the agile scaling method that is planned to be implemented most is SAFe. Comparing the findings of this survey to the findings of related work shows that, in the study of Azizyan et al. and Laanti et al., mostly Scrum, XP and Kanban are used (Azizyan, Magarian and Kajko-Mattson, 2011; Laanti, Salo and Abrahamsson, 2011). In the study of Salo and Abrahamsson, XP is even applied in 54% of the cases, whereas Scrum is only used by 27% of the participants; this might be due to the fact that the study of Salo and Abrahamsson is from 2008 and thus more than thirteen years old, however.

Figure 49: Agile Methods used in logistics start-ups surveyed

Source: Own representation

In logistics start-ups of all ages, Scrum and Kanban are used most often. Logistics start-ups between one and five years old use Lean startup more often than start-ups of other age groups. Scaling methods are used especially by logistics start-ups that are between three and five years old. Participants describe in the free text fields that other methods used are: “Double Diamond”, “Design Thinking”,

“Enterprise Kanban”, and “Objectives and Key Results”. In Figure 50, agile methods used by the participants are shown with regard to the age of the start-up. Participants from German start-ups express more often than other participants that they use Kanban.

Figure 50: Five most used agile methods among different age groups of surveyed logistics start-ups

Source: Own representation

Looking at the way agile methods are used shows that most teams adjust agile methods to their own team specific requirements. Only 17 participants (17,8%) confirm to use agile methods according to the original guidelines, such as the Scrum Guide (Schwaber, 1997). The participants had the possibility to describe their use of multiple agile methods as well, which is why more than 95 answers have been analysed. For example, one participant may state that she/he uses Scrum and closely follows the theoretical guidelines, while she/he may have also stated that their team uses Kanban and has adopted it to team specifics.

Figure 51: Adjustment of agile methods used in surveyed logistics start-ups of the survey

Source: Own representation

An agile method consists of a subset of agile practices. Nearly 50% of the participants describe in the survey that they pick single practices out of the whole agile method and that they do not use all practices included in it. On the other hand, 38% of the participants use the complete agile method in its entirety.

Figure 52: Ways of using agile methods and practices by surveyed logistics start-ups

Source: Own representation

The findings presented in Figure 52 correspond to Figure 47 (Page 134), where in total 87% of the participants stated that they use either an agile (54%) or a hybrid approach (33%). This corresponds to the 87% of participants who use a complete agile method (38%) or selected practices (49%), even if the distributions between the two figures differ. As more participants (54%) use an agile approach

(see Figure 53) as compared to participants who use the complete agile method, it becomes visible that some participants use selected agile practices, not the complete method. The findings of this survey show that often individual practices are used rather than a whole agile method. For instance, 77 of the 95 participants use "Daily (Standups)". However, only 68 participants apply the related agile method Scrum. The aspect is even stronger for more technical agile practices such as "Refactoring" and "Pair Programming": they are applied separately more frequently than the entire agile method XP. Results of the Delphi study (see Section 5 – Delphi study, page 103) and other related studies support this finding (Pikkarainen et al., 2008; Jalali and Wohlin, 2010; Diebold and Dahlem, 2014).

Looking at the agile practices, “Close exchanges within the agile teams”, “Update of task (Kanban) board”, “Daily (standups)”, and “Reviews” are used most frequently. In the Delphi study participants from logistics start-ups answered that “Sprint Planning” sessions, “Retrospectives”, and regular “Delivery of the software” were among the agile practices used most: thus, this survey shows a slightly different ranking of the agile practices. Nevertheless, the results show that close communication within the development team and frequent feedback from customers are important for logistics start-ups in both studies. Figure 53 presents the agile practices used by the survey participants.

Figure 53: Use of agile practices of surveyed logistics start-ups

Source: Own representation

To understand where the interest for the use of agile methods comes from, participants are asked who first initiated the use of agile methods. Participants could select multiple answers, which is why more than 95 answers are given in total. In most cases, the initiative for the introduction of agile methods comes from team leads, the team itself, or agile coaches.

Figure 54: Origin of the initiative for the use of agile methods in surveyed logistics start-ups

Source: Own representation

Other additional answers given are “External Consultant”; “Product Manager”, “Founder” and “IT expert”. Over the lifespans of the start-ups it becomes visible that in start-ups younger than five years, mostly the team itself or the team lead initiate the use of agile methods. In start-ups older than five years, the use of agile methods is initiated more often by external consultants, agile coaches, product managers, or the head of department.

Figure 55: Decision makers when choosing the agile method in surveyed logistics start-ups

Source: Own representation

To understand who drives the interest in the application of agile methods, participants are asked who selected the agile methods applied (see Figure 55). This question is also a multiple choice question,

and again more than 95 answers are given. With the help of the answers, initial conclusions can be drawn about the hierarchical structure in the start-up. In logistics start-ups younger than one year, the team or the team leader decides which agile methods are used. Especially in start-ups between one and five years of age, agile coaches, but also the team itself, are part of the decision-making process. As the start-ups become older, more decisions are made by senior management, and the heads of department. Over the time, fewer decision are made by the team or the team leader. The data collected shows a relationship with the size of the start-up as well: older start-ups tend to be larger in terms of the number of employees, and it is possible that more hierarchy levels are the reason why more decisions are being made by the heads of department and top management. In the study of Azizyan et al., which is one of the studies described in the “Related work” section but does not differentiate between the different ages of the companies (see Section 2.6.3. – Identification of related surveys, page 47), mostly managers and developers decide on the use of agile methods (Azizyan, Magarian and Kajko-Mattson, 2011).

Looking at the criteria applied for the selection of agile methods shows that most start-ups younger than three years choose their methods based on their own previous experience, and based on existing knowledge of the employees regarding agile methods (see Figure 56). Start-ups between three and five years base their decisions on recommendations of colleagues and the project requirements in addition to the former reasons. For logistics start-ups older than five years, company guidelines and the recommendations of external consultants also have an impact. Image of the agile methods and cost implementation play a negligible role.

Figure 56: Selection criteria for the use of agile methods in surveyed logistics start-ups

Source: Own representation

Overall, the results of the survey reflect the results of the Delphi study, which is that one’s own previous experience, existing knowledge of the employees, and project requirements are also the selection criteria chosen most often. Similarly again to the Delphi study, criteria such as implementation costs and the image of the agile methods are selection criteria that are less important. It is interesting that logistics start-ups that are five years and older base their decisions on the agile method used more often on company guidelines, which for example are aligned with the company strategy. This corresponds to the responses of the experts of established logistics companies in the Delphi study, who more frequently make their decision on agile methods based on company guidelines.

6.3.2. Results of the survey relevant to research question 2

To address the second RQ, the participants are surveyed on the reasons for and benefits of the use of agile methods and practices.

Findings demonstrate that the reasons why participants apply agile methods change over the lifespan of the logistics start-up. The survey participants coming from start-ups younger than one year named five benefits that are generated through the use of agile methods:

- Increased employee satisfaction

- Increased business value
- Increased project transparency for the team and the customer
- Increased flexibility of the product scope
- Improved communication in the team

Especially in start-ups younger than one year, agile methods are applied to increase employee satisfaction and business value. As logistics start-ups become older, participants described that they apply agile methods less to increase project transparency for the customer, but more to increase communication within the development team. This might be because, over time and increases in the size of the start-up, the customer is less attached to the development team. Additionally, logistics start-ups build up a broader customer base and might rely less on the feedback of one single customer. Start-ups older than five years use agile methods to improve internal processes and the productivity of the development team. This could be related to the fact that the need for process improvements increases with the age and size of a start-up. For start-ups older than ten years, flexibility of the product scope seems to be especially important. Here it is necessary to mention that the group of start-ups older than ten years includes only seven participants in total. Communication in the participants' teams is improved through the use of agile methods in logistics start-ups of all ages.

In the following, the highest-ranked benefits of the Delphi study and the survey are compared. Looking at the results, it becomes clear that in both studies, responsiveness to changing requirements is an important benefit of the use of agile methods for both the logistics start-ups and the established logistics companies that participated in the Delphi study. In the Delphi study, the alignment between the IT departments and the business departments is also an important benefit; the results of the survey show that this importance increases with the age of the logistics start-ups. The increase of project transparency is important for participants of both studies. In other industries, start-ups use more speed-related agile methods and practices, such as delivery pipelines, than agile methods that increase internal productivity (Pantiuchina et al., 2017).

The findings of this survey correspond to the findings of Laanti et al. (Laanti, Salo and Abrahamsson, 2011). In their study, respondents agree with the claimed benefits of agile methods such as increased product quality and transparency, earlier detection of defects, higher satisfaction of the customer, greater effectiveness of the processes, and increased autonomy and happiness within the team.

To deepen the findings of the benefits of agile methods, participants are asked which agile methods they use to realise specific benefits. Agile methods applied to attain all thirteen benefits that were

part of the survey are presented in the following (see Figure 57). The thirteen benefits were selected to be part of the survey based on their importance, which was ranked by the participants of the Delphi study. It becomes visible that Scrum, followed by Kanban, is the agile method chosen most often by the survey participants for all benefits. This matches the results of the Delphi study, where mostly agile practices that belong to the agile method Scrum are selected to attain the benefits.

Looking more closely, Scrum is mostly used for the increase of transparency and productivity, optimisation of processes in general, and technical software development processes. This might be due to the fact that Scrum prescribes a very structured approach to team organisation and its processes. Scrum is also used to increase reactivity to changing external requirements, whereas Kanban is used more for reactivity to internal changes. Lean startup is used mostly to reduce risk and costs, and to react to external changes. Lean startup focuses on short feedback cycles with the customer, and might therefore be helpful in reducing risks and cost and in reacting to changes.

Figure 57: Agile methods for the realisation of specific benefits in surveyed logistics start-ups

Source: Own representation

The following figure describes the effectiveness of the agile methods selected for the realisation of benefits. Effectiveness was ranked on a scale from “One” to “Five”. “One” stands for low effectiveness, whereas “Five” stands for the highest effectiveness possible. Overall, none of the

methods is the most effective method for the realisation of all benefits. Overall, Scrumban, followed by Kanban and Scrum, are ranked the highest. Looking at specific benefits, Scrumban also had the highest rankings for specific benefits, namely “React to changing customer requirements” and “Improve communication between and the customer”. In the following, the effectiveness of the three agile methods ranked highest, Scrumban, Scrum and Kanban, are presented. Details can be seen in Table 24. Benefits are sorted according to their ranking in the Scrum method.

Table 24: Presentation of effectiveness scores of agile methods

Benefits	Scrum	Kanban	Scrumban
React to changing internal requirements	4,2	4,2	4,6
React to changing customer requirements	4,2	4,4	5,0
Optimisation of team collaboration	4,2	3,9	4,7
Increase transparency on status	4,2	4,4	4,8
Improve communication between customer and the IT	4,1	4,0	5,0
Technical optimisation of software development	4,1	3,5	3,7
Optimisation of processes	4,0	4,4	4,7
Accelerate product delivery	4,0	4,5	5,0
Scaling of the team	4,0	4,0	4,7
Increase product quality	3,8	4,4	4,6
Reduce project risk	3,8	3,8	4,8
Increase productivity	3,7	4,2	4,5
Reduce costs	3,0	4,5	3,7

In the Delphi study, three complementary rounds are conducted. The researcher had more time to query the participants: instead of asking which agile method participants use to realise a specific benefit, they are asked which agile practices which are smaller subsets of the agile method are used. Practices used most often for the realisation of the benefits according to the participants of logistics start-ups of the Delphi study are:

- Practices all agile methods prescribe: close exchange within the team, feedback cycles with the customer
- Scrum: sprint planning, daily standups, reviews, retrospectives
- XP: regular software delivery, regular builds of the software
- Kanban: Kanban board

These practices are clustered with the subordinated agile method to compare the findings of the Delphi study to the findings of the survey. In the Delphi study, looking at agile methods, Scrum, Kanban, and XP are used the most and have the highest efficacy. This corresponds to the findings of this survey, in which Scrum was by far used most, followed by Kanban and XP. Lean startup is also

applied by some logistics start-ups in the survey and seems to be more important than for the companies of the Delphi study. Even though Scrumban is rated as most effective, it is by a wide margin not one of the agile methods used most (see Section 6.3.1. – Results of the survey RQ1, page 135).

6.3.3. Results of the survey relevant to research question 3

To answer the third RQ, the participants are questioned on the challenges and difficulties they encounter applying agile methods and practices.

Participants rate the intensity of five challenges that occur during the application of agile methods on a scale of “One” to “Five”: “One” represents a very small challenge, and “Five” the biggest challenge. The five challenges are selected based on the findings of the Delphi study conducted previously. Survey results show that, on average “(Non) availability of the product owner” and “Incomplete knowledge on the use of agile methods” are ranked highest (see Figure 58). Other publications describe the implementation of a delivery strategy, the use of agile software engineering techniques, the capabilities of agile teams, and management support as the most critical success factors for the successful use of agile methods in start-ups (Chow and Cao, 2008; Kamil, 2018). Opposed to that are resistance to change, scepticism towards the new way of working, and a top-down approach rated as the challenges most difficult in the SLR of Dikert et al., which mainly included the findings of studies in large companies (Dikert, Paasivaara and Lassenius, 2016).

Figure 58: Average ranking of the challenges using agile methods in surveyed logistics start-ups

Source: Own representation

To collect data for a reference measurement, the participants had the chance to confirm when a challenge was no challenge at all within their own start-ups. The number of participants in the survey who expressed that they had no problems with a respective challenge corresponds to the average rating of the severity of the challenges (see Figure 58 and 59). “(Non) availability of the product owner” is rated as most severe challenge, and only 19 participants (20% of all participants) claim to

face no challenge regarding the missing product owner. Compared to that, “Unequal distribution of knowledge” is rated as least severe, and 30 participants (32% of all participants) from start-ups affirm that they face no challenge at all with the knowledge distribution.

Figure 59: Number of survey participants who did not face the challenges specified
Source: Own representation

Clustering the answers of the participants according to the different ages of the logistics start-ups shows that the challenges faced by the logistics start-ups change over time (see Figure 60): “Incomplete knowledge of agile methods” is the biggest challenges for logistics start-ups between three and five years of age; employees’ “Fear of change”, “Strict organisational culture”, and “Lack of product owner” are challenges especially encountered in start-ups older than five years; and “Unequal distribution of knowledge” seems to be a challenge for all start-ups. Interestingly, the data from the survey shows that challenges are ranked as less intense when the team decides itself which agile methods are used. This has been confirmed by correlation tests.

Figure 60: Challenges using agile methods clustered by age of the surveyed logistics start-ups
Source: Own representation

In the study of Chow and Cao, three critical success factors for ASD projects are identified: delivery strategy, agile software engineering techniques, and team capability (Chow and Cao, 2008). Only the factor team capability corresponds partly to the challenges “Lack of product owner” and “Incomplete knowledge of agile methods”, from this study.

Challenges appear not only during the implementation of agile methods but also during the first introduction of these methods. Participants are interrogated on support measures that can be taken during their introduction. Participants from logistics start-ups of all age groups described that the early involvement of employees and the support of the senior management is important (see Figure 61). The focus on agile principles instead of processes is especially important in all logistics start-ups younger than ten years. The support of an agile coach and the creation of a new organisational culture are rated more important the older the start-up becomes.

Similarly, in the Delphi study, support of the senior management and focus on agile principles instead of processes are ranked as most important measures by the participants (see Figure 36, page 118).

Figure 61: Support measures for the introduction of agile methods in the surveyed logistics start-ups

Source: Own representation

Additionally, the measures that support the introduction of agile methods are clustered based on the headcount of the start-ups. It would have been conceivable that the number of employees would also influence the necessary support measures. Start-ups with between 100 and 250 employees and start-ups with 500 or more employees especially use many support measures when introducing agile methods. However, start-ups with 250 to 500 employees use fewer measures to support the introduction of agile methods. Therefore, no direct connection between the headcount and the number of measures has been discovered.

6.4. Discussion of the survey results

In the following, the results found and their implications are discussed more closely.

General findings of the survey

Comparing the survey results with the identified benefits of other surveys (see Section 2.6.3. – Identification of related surveys, page 47), it can be confirmed that surveys are a suitable tool to collect data. By gathering data from 95 participants, the RQs can be answered, and the findings of the Delphi study can be extended. The presented survey helps to fill the identified research gap (see Section 4.2. – SLR, page 88). Based on the Delphi study, the presented survey collected data from participants from logistics start-ups worldwide and provides data for the framework developed in this study (see Section 7 – Framework, page 155). The implications of the results of the three RQs are discussed below.

Findings Research Question 1

Results of the survey data show that Scrum and Kanban are the agile methods applied most frequently in logistics start-ups. Most participants from the logistics start-ups adjust agile practices to their needs. In terms of agile practices, “Close exchange within the team”, “Update of the Kanban board” and “Daily Standups” are used most often. In start-ups younger than one year, team leaders or the team itself decides what agile methods to implement. As start-ups become older, fewer decisions are taken by the team and the team leaders, while more decisions are made by agile coaches, external consultants, or the heads of department.

Findings Research Question 2

The most important benefits that logistics start-ups aim to achieve with agile methods and practices are increased customer and employee satisfaction, increased flexibility of the product scope and

improved communication. Scrum is mostly used for the optimisation of processes and the increase of productivity. Lean startup is used mostly to reduce risk and costs and to react to external changes. Looking at the effectiveness of the agile methods, Scrumban followed by Kanban and Scrum, are ranked the highest.

Findings Research Question 3

The data from the survey shows that “Unequal distribution of knowledge” and “Incomplete knowledge of agile methods” are the biggest challenges when introducing agile methods. The participants’ answers show that, as the logistics start-ups become older, strict “Organisational culture” and the “Lack of a product owner” become growing challenges.

6.5. Limitations of the survey

Since the design of a questionnaire is central to data collection, multiple pre-tests were performed with company experts and researchers. However, it cannot be discounted that the answers may lose some of their nuances due to the type of online survey being used here. To mitigate this limitation, the participants had the opportunity to complete their answers to closed questions in free-text fields.

Another limitations arises, as 37 of 95 survey participants are employees of German logistics start-ups. This could lead to a single-sided view, even though the logistics industry does play an important role in Germany (Wenwen, Shuo and Dachuan, 2020). In the future, a comparative study with additional participants from other countries could be conducted. Further, as just one employee per logistics start-up was surveyed, a one-sided perspective could have been created. The author of this survey aimed to reduce this limitation by gathering answers from participants with different roles. The participants' answers did not show any statistically significant, role-specific characteristics, but were homogeneous across the roles. Future research could quantify the impact of agility and the use of agile methods on the success of logistics start-ups by interviewing more employees with different roles. A further limitation is the high non-response rate: 4,176 possible participants were approached, 2,183 e-mails could not be served, leaving 1,993 e-mails delivered. Overall, only 95 (4.7%) finished the survey and 228 (11.4%) only began to fill out the questionnaire. It must be presumed that the participants who finished the questionnaire have a positive perception of agile methods and practices and that an NRB exists (see section 2.6.5. - Non-response bias, page 51). When evaluating the results, the NRB must be taken into account. It is a possibility that primarily participants with a positive

relationship to agile methods participated in the survey and therefore the views on agile methods are presented here more positively than they are in reality.

In order to reduce subjectivity in the evaluation of the collected data, a detailed data analysis was carried out independently by two researchers. Finally, it should be pointed out that, through using a similar survey, further insights into the use of agile methods in established logistics companies could be gained. In addition, a more qualitative investigation of the way agile methods are applied could be conducted in the context of case studies to explore what established logistics companies and logistics start-ups could learn from one another.

6.6. Assessment of the methodological approach

For several reasons an online survey was chosen to deepen the findings of the Delphi study, which is reflected upon in the following. An assessment based on the experiences made in this study is carried out to determine whether the survey approach has proven its value in this study.

Access to a larger population

In order to extend the findings of the Delphi study on the use of agile methods in German logistics start-ups, quantitative questions are asked to participants from logistics start-ups worldwide. Additionally, organisational questions about e.g. origin and previous experience of the experts with regard to agile methods as well as a few quantitative questions are posed. Through the use of the internet it was possible to access participants globally and gain a broader data foundation to analyse. The use of closed questions together with the option to extend the answers in free-text fields was considered helpful to answering the RQs in depth.

Saving time and money

Online surveys eliminate the need for paper resources. Time is saved both by the participant, as he or she can fill out the survey whenever and wherever he or she wants to. The researcher saves time as he or she does not need to schedule personal interviews with the participants. Data analysis becomes easier and faster, and data is already available in a digital format and does not need to be transcribed. These benefits of the survey approach facilitated the response of the RQs. The statistical analysis of the results took a total of four weeks.

Deepening the findings of previous research

A survey approach can be used to expand and test the findings of the previous Delphi study. This online survey allowed for the global extension of data, as in the Delphi study only data from Germany is gathered. Within this survey, data is collected successfully from 95 logistics start-ups from more than 13 countries. The exact number cannot be determined due to the anonymity of many participants. Through the participation of 95 employees from logistics start-ups, the results from the Delphi study could be questioned and verified.

Anonymity

The online survey guarantees the anonymity of the participants. Enabling participants to give realistic answers without being afraid of competitors gaining too much knowledge on company specifics is helpful for this field of research. In addition, the anonymity of the participants reduces the number of socially desirable answers: as the participants' answers cannot be linked directly to them, the pressure to give answers that are in alignment with society is reduced. Participants had the opportunity to voluntarily share their e-mail addresses in order to be notified about the results of the survey: 55 of the 95 participants, around 58%, left their e-mail address. This confirms the interest of the participants in the results and their relevance for practitioners.

Realistic picture of “the truth”

In social research, data collection from the actors and experts themselves is a valuable approach to understand social phenomena. Surveys are described as a valuable approach to gathering the judgements of a large group of experts (Sheehan and Hoy, 2006).

As agile methods and practices are socially-oriented methods (Beck, 2000; Schwaber and Beedle, 2002), surveys are helpful in gaining a realistic picture of the truth based on the views of the actors themselves.

6.7. Conclusion

This survey deepens the results of the Delphi study by involving participants from logistics start-ups worldwide. In addition to agile methods and practices used by logistics start-ups worldwide, the benefits and challenges of using agile methods are analysed. For this purpose, an online survey is completed by 95 participants working at logistics start-ups. The panel includes the perspectives of 95 participants working in 95 logistics start-ups, who are familiar with the use of agile methods and

practices. By identifying the methods and practices used most, as well as the benefits and challenges, the survey results contribute to the body of knowledge in the field of logistics and in the field of IT project management. Scrum and Kanban are identified as agile methods applied most, "Close exchange within the (development) team", "Use of task boards such as Kanban boards" and "Daily Standups" are discovered to be the practices that are most common. Over time, the focus of the logistics start-ups moves from customer- and product-focused to being more strongly concentrated on internal processes and communication. The results show that younger start-ups use agile methods that concentrate on product development. As logistics start-ups become older, participants describe that they use agile methods to increase productivity and optimise internal processes. To introduce organisational changes, older start-ups rely more often on the help of agile coaches, as employees tend to have greater fear of change. In publications focusing on the theory of start-up evolution, findings show similarities to this survey with regard to different phases of start-ups and their needs. Degl'innocenti developed a definition of the phases of organisational development of start-ups (Degl'innocenti, 2019): in the first phase, it is necessary to understand the organisation's values, such as the product, and maximise them; the strategy of the start-up is then adjusted so that the organisation's success can be maximised; next the focus moves to the employees and the improvement of internal processes. Her findings correspond to the findings of this survey. Based on the framework of Sekliuckiene et al., product design is the goal of start-ups in their first life cycle stage (Sekliuckiene, Vaitkienė and Vestinaaainauskiene, 2018). This matches the reasons why participants in this study use agile methods. As the start-ups mature, Sekliuckiene et al. show that scaling, internal processes and strategic planning become more relevant for the start-ups. This aligns with the answers of the participants of the survey, as they focus increasingly on the improvement of internal processes and the implementation of agile scaling methods over time. In the next chapter, the results of the survey and also of the results of the Delphi study, the SLR, and the interviews are consolidated into one framework that can be applied by practitioners in the logistics industry to deal with complexity and digitalisation.

7. Consolidation of the findings into one framework

In the previous chapters, research approaches and results of the interviews, the SLR, the Delphi study, and the survey are described in detail to understand how participants from various logistics companies assess their use of agile methods. In this chapter, the framework development, its design, and its application are presented. Beforehand, a research gap was identified in which no publication presenting a framework on the use of agile methods in (logistics) start-ups could be found. At the end of the chapter, the validity of this new framework is confirmed by comparing it to frameworks that focus on the evolution of start-ups. This analysis enables a comparison between the developed framework, which deals with different reasons for and challenges of the use of agile methods in logistics start-ups of different ages, and existing frameworks that describe the characteristics of start-ups of different ages.

The goal of this framework is to consolidate the findings from the SLR, the Delphi study, and the survey. This consolidation presents the most important aspects of all data gathered into one framework to support the application of agile methods in logistics start-ups and to map them according to the different ages of the logistics start-ups. For researchers, the framework reduces the identified research gap in the use of agile methods in the logistics industry and lays a foundation for future research. The framework illustrates how agile methods are applied in an increasingly complex environment.

The framework is primarily aimed at practitioners from logistics start-ups but also from more established logistics companies. It is intended to support practitioners selecting suitable agile methods and practices and applying them based on the experiences of other practitioners.

This chapter is structured as follows: section 8.1. describes related frameworks that provide assessment criteria for the optimal implementation of agile methods and identifies a research gap. Section 8.2. shows the development of the framework within this study, and section 8.3. describes the framework itself. Then, section 8.4. outlines the application of the framework. In section 8.5, the developed framework is compared to related frameworks that detail the evolution of start-ups and their needs, and in section 8.6, the framework developed within and put into context with the related frameworks. Finally, in section 8.7., the impact and limitations of the framework are presented.

7.1. Identification of related frameworks

To validate the need for a framework, related publications that describe frameworks structuring assessment criteria for the optimal use of agile methods are analysed.

7.1.1. Related work

To prepare the consolidation of the findings into one framework, a closer look at other frameworks that assess agile methods is taken. This section presents publications that have the objective of classifying assessment criteria for the implementation of agile methods/ practices and are therefore related to this field of research. To the best of my knowledge only a few publications that present frameworks for the selection of suitable agile methods exist. No publication with a framework specifically for logistics companies could be identified. The following sections briefly summarise the most important frameworks (see Table 25). Authors are listed in chronological order.

Table 25: Related frameworks on the assessment of agile methods

Author, Year	Aim of the study	Assessment criteria to classify/ select agile methods
Strode, 2005	Creation of a comparative analytical framework	Philosophy and values perspective, objectives and scope, size of project, type of problem, type of organisation, size of organisation, type of development, type of application, roles and responsibilities, difficulties with the methodology, skill level needed, tailorability of agile method
Iacovelli and Souveyet, 2008	Classify agile methods to measure their impact on requirement engineering processes	Usage view, capability to agility view, applicability view, processes and products view
Fernandes and Almeida, 2010	Comparisons of agile methods, based on a set of relevant features and attributes	Software Requirements, software construction, software testing, software engineering management
Soundararajan and Arthur, 2011	Assessing the “Goodness” of Agile Methods	Adequacy – Sufficiency of the method with respect to meeting stated objectives Capability – Ability of the organisation to provide the supporting environment conducive to the implementation of the method Effectiveness – Producing the intended or expected results which are dependent upon process and product characteristics
Bosch et al., 2013	A framework for operationalising	Ability to work on multiple project ideas in parallel, guidance on when to abandon a product idea, guidance on when to move a

Author, Year	Aim of the study	Assessment criteria to classify/ select agile methods
	lean principles in early stage software start-ups	product idea forward, guidance on techniques to use when validating the product idea
Lee and Yong, 2013	Agile Software Development Framework in a Small Project Environment	Risk-based agility factors, agility of the adopted practices, agile adoption levels, degree of the agile small project success

Strode (2005) gives an overview of the agile methods, but also describes other comparative studies of agile methods (Strode, 2005). Strode creates a comparative analytical framework and uses it to compare the Dynamic Systems Development Method (DSDM), XP, Scrum, Crystal and ASD. The analysis of the characteristics of the agile method shows what the agile methods have in common and how they differ. The framework also presents where the agile methods have unique characteristics and how agile methods can be combined.

Iacovelli and Souveyet (2008) assess agile methods with a focus on requirement engineering (Iacovelli and Souveyet, 2008). In the first step, a framework is built to classify and compare agile methods. In the second step, a component-based approach is presented to extract best agile practices for classical plan driven methods.

Fernandes and Almeida (2010) describe a technique that can be used to compare agile methods, based on multiple relevant attributes. These parameters include Knowledge Areas (KA) from IEEE's Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK) and the agile principles defined in the Agile Manifesto. Fernandes and Almeida use these parameters to analyse the practices proposed by each agile method (Fernandes and Almeida, 2010). They evaluate the so-called coverage degree for the considered KAs and the agility degree. In this publication, the assessment is performed for XP and Scrum.

Soundararajan and Arthur (2011) question whether and to what extent agile practices and methods correspond to the principles of the Agile Manifesto (Soundararajan and Arthur, 2011). The aim is to assess the "goodness" of the agile methods and practices adopted and whether they support organisational objectives.

Bosch et al. (2013) investigated typical challenges that appear when finding a product idea that is worth scaling and solutions to address these challenges and developed the “Early Stage Software Start-up Development Model”, which enhances already existing lean and agile principles (Bosch et al., 2013).

Lee and Yong (2013) created the Agile Framework for Small Projects (AFSP) and applied it to four industry cases (Lee and Yong, 2013). The AFSP creates a structured way for software organisations to introduce agile practices and evaluate their success of the adoption. The AFSP covers agile practices that are included in agile methods like Scrum, XP, FDD, DSDM and Crystal Clear.

7.1.2. Classification of the related frameworks

To sum up the overview of related work, it can be said that no publication presenting a framework focusing on the application of agile methods in logistics companies could be found. Furthermore, no scientific framework that relates or compares the use of agile methods with the ages of logistics start-ups could be found. The following shortcomings can be observed:

- Strode (2006) focuses on the commonalities and differences of agile methods in order to compare them. A clear link to the field of logistics is missing. Additionally, the framework does not allow for the derivation of clear recommendations for the selection of agile methods;
- Iacovelli and Souveyet (2008) present a framework and show how best practices from agile methods can be used in plan-driven environments. Nevertheless, it remains difficult to find out which agile method is suitable for concrete application in different logistics companies as no exemplary case is presented;
- Fernandes and Almeida (2010) compare which agile methods can be applied in requirement engineering. Therefore, no comprehensive assessment of the use of agile methods for the complete software development process is performed;
- Soundararajan and Arthur (2011) present a framework that mainly focuses on the adequacy and effectiveness of agile methods with regard to improving organisational processes. They do not consider the applicability of agile methods for different scenarios and companies;
- Bosch et al. (2013) focus on challenges software start-ups face when developing product ideas. Bosch et al.’s framework deepens existing lean principles to help software start-ups e.g. on deciding when to abandon a product idea and when to move forward. Bosch et al. do not include logistics start-ups. And finally,

- Lee and Yong (2013) concentrate on small projects. There may be similarities between small projects and start-ups, but it is obvious that small projects have a different background in terms of the business environment and job security in the absence of success. No link to the logistics industry is made.

To conclude, before developing a framework, related work has been reviewed and no framework focusing on the field of logistics has been identified.

7.2. Objective of the framework

Practical frameworks have the objective to support especially practitioners in their work (Ekins et al., 2003; Smith and Colgate, 2014). The collected data for logistics start-ups was assigned to the different life cycles stages of the start-ups based on their age. It should be noted that the age of the start-ups is only an indicator and that the characteristics of the start-ups change gradually. There are no hard boundaries between the age groups of the logistics start-ups. For the following seven different dimensions the characteristics of the logistics start-ups are presented.

The aim of the framework is the consolidation of the previously gathered data to present agile methods (first dimension) and practices (second dimension) currently used by logistic start-ups of different ages (see Section 7 – Framework, page 155). Additionally, benefits (third dimension) logistics start-ups realise through the implementation of agile methods are shown. It is described what challenges (fourth dimension) the logistics start-ups face and who decided initially (fifth dimension) that agile methods should be applied. The framework presents who selected (sixth dimension) the agile methods and how the introduction and first application of agile methods can be facilitated (seventh dimension). As the data in these seven dimensions is ordered according to the age of the logistics start-ups it allows a comparison of the use of agile methods in logistics start-ups.

This framework seeks to use the data collected to provide a representation of the current reality regarding the use of agile methods. Both practitioners and researchers profit from the use of this framework. Practitioners of logistics start-ups can compare their approach with that of other logistics start-ups and learn from the challenges faced by other logistics start-ups. Practitioners from established logistics companies can potentially use the framework to break down their often rather rigid approach and keep up with the innovation capacity of logistics start-ups. Researchers can apply the framework for further research in the previously rather unexplored area of agile methods in the logistics industry.

7.3. Development of the framework

The framework is closely linked to each of the four studies conducted.

- The interviews enabled the development of the RQs from which the seven dimensions of the framework are derived. Research questions were answered from different perspectives through the SLR, the Delphi study, and the survey.
- The SLR provides the theoretical background for the questionnaires of the Delphi study and the survey and some specifications in the framework are based on the SLR.
- The main contribution to the framework comes from the Delphi study and the survey. The Delphi study, through its iterative approach, provided a first orientation in the unexplored research field and allowed for a precise development of the survey questionnaire. The questions from the questionnaire of the Delphi study were checked for their applicability within the survey and further questions were generated.
- Owing to the high number of responses from survey participants employed in logistics start-ups worldwide, it was possible to derive a framework. The data of the survey was analysed extensively and a relationship between the ages of the start-ups and their uses of agile methods was found.

Based on this, the start-ups were compared in their respective age groups in seven dimensions (see Section 8.4 - Description of the framework, page 159). It is important to point out that the age groups do not constitute a strict division according to age, but rather gradual transitions between the different age groups of the start-ups.

Additionally, the resulting framework is compared to existing literature (see Section 7.7. – Comparison to other frameworks, page 172). Concluding, it can be said that in young, newly founded start-ups, agile methods are mainly applied to create product ideas and to produce added value for the customer. Older start-ups are increasingly using agile methods to provide structure to internal processes and are struggling with cultural difficulties within the organisation and employees' fears of change. This is consistent with some of the findings of the Delphi study. The Delphi study revealed that, in contrast to start-ups in general, established logistics companies increasingly struggle with organisational culture and employee resistance to change. The development process of the framework is visualised in Figure 62:

Figure 62: Development of the framework

Source: Own representation

7.4. Description of the framework

The descriptive framework is visualised in one diagram (see Figure 63) that shows the ages of the logistics start-ups on the horizontal axis. In terms of contingency theory, there are further explanatory organisational and environmental variables that may have affected participants' situations and their choice of agile methods and practices (Luthans and Stewart, 1977; Birkinshaw, Nobel and Ridderstrale, 2002). An age limit, e.g. three years, is not a sharp boundary but rather constitutes a smooth transition. The following seven different dimensions can be seen on the vertical axis:

- Benefits of agile methods
- Support measures when introducing agile methods
- Challenges faced when introducing and using agile methods
- Agile methods used
- Agile practices used
- Initiator (Role) of the use of agile methods
- Selector (Role) of agile methods

These seven dimensions were developed based on the RQs; answers that were given most often in the survey are shown (see Section 6.3. – Results of the survey, page 135). For the logistics start-ups of different ages, the framework describes which agile methods and practices they use, what benefits they want to realise with agile methods, what challenges the logistics start-ups encounter when

applying agile methods, and who decided to use agile methods. The framework outlines who selected the agile methods and what was done to facilitate the adoption of agile methods. The seven dimensions allow a comparison of the use of agile methods in logistics start-ups over time. The data presented is a representation of the current state of the use of agile methods.

¹Des Thinking, ²Double Diamond, ³Close feedback cycles with the customer, ⁴Incomplete knowledge of agile methods, ⁵Increase on-time delivery, ⁶Increase transparency, ⁷Support from an agile coach, ⁸Head of department, ⁹Senior management

Figure 63: Framework on the use of agile methods and practices in logistics start-ups and the realised benefits and challenges
Source: Own representation

Two categories of reasons for the use of agile methods are presented in Figure 64: the darker fields represent advantages of agile methods for the customer, and the light blue fields describe the internal benefits for the corresponding start-up itself and for its development team (see Figure 64). Younger start-ups focus especially on the increase of customer value, customer satisfaction and the increase of flexibility of the product scope. Over the life cycle of the start-ups, the focus moves to more internal, team-specific benefits, such as process optimisation, which are at least as relevant as customer-centred benefits.

Looking at Figure 64, for start-ups that are around three years old or older, the gap in external benefits is striking. Between three and five years old, the focus of the logistics start-ups is no longer on customer satisfaction or on-time delivery, but rather on the productivity of their teams. Older start-ups that are around five years old focus again on customer satisfaction and on-time delivery. This could be due to the fact that about three years after the first successful product launches, internal processes have to be optimised to allow for further growth, and then later, at about the five-year mark, start-ups concentrate again on external benefits.

Overall, it has to be stated that all benefits, whether they improve relationships with customers or bring improvements within the organisation, are connected. The benefits are also closely related to the challenges that arise. In the Delphi study, when asked about the advantages of agile methods, one participant adds the following quote to the response options: all the possible answers could in fact be selected, *“because there are so many dependencies. In our case it's mostly the experience the team has had in the past with non-agile methodologies that led to low quality of a product and essentially development of a product nobody actually needed. So, team spirit and employee satisfaction is also there, because with agile methodologies fewer things go to waste.”* A challenge that is mentioned by another participant is that *“all customer communication must currently run through the CEO”*. The framework illustrates that agile methods are applied by start-ups of all ages to improve communication within the team. More direct communication flows between the development team and the customer can help enhance customer satisfaction. More direct communication with the customer supports e.g. the aim of one participant, to *“perform user research to understand and solve the customers' problem 100% instead of taking many of the customers' ideas as solutions”*.

⁵Increase on-time delivery, ⁶Increase transparency

Figure 64: Overview of benefits of the use of agile methods

Source: Own representation

Figure 65 shows measures that can be taken to support the use of agile methods. For start-ups of all ages, the early involvement of employees is an important factor for the implementation of agile methods. For logistics start-ups up to the age of five years, employees concentrate on agile principles instead of processes to facilitate the implementation of agile methods. For instance, this implies that teams concentrate on collaboration within the team and only use the processes that are really needed. Start-ups often introduce agile methods from the very beginning and do not, as is more often the case in established companies, move from a classic to an agile approach (VersionOne, 2021). This can help start-ups to centre on the agile principles rather than on the processes and their implementation. For start-ups older than one year, senior management support is needed for the transition. For start-ups older than three years, it is important to create a new organisational culture that involves self-organised teams and an open attitude of employees towards change. Interestingly, employees' fear of change considerably grows in logistics start-ups that are older than three years (see Figure 65).

⁷Support of the transformation and the management from an agile coach

Figure 65: Overview of measures that can be taken to support the introduction of agile methods

Source: Own representation

While start-ups younger than five years have to deal with an uneven distribution of knowledge within the team and/or incomplete knowledge about the application of agile methods, start-ups older than five years experience difficulties regarding the mindset of their employees: in start-ups older than five years, employees have a tendency to fear change. Projects are often surrounded by a strict organisational structure, which leads to an environment where it is more challenging to implement

new methods because employees seem to have a harder time adapting to the new processes. A strict organisational structure often implies rigid hierarchies that first have to be removed, both officially and in the minds of the employees, to allow for self-organised teams that make decisions independently. Start-ups of almost any age also experience challenges when the product owner is missing. One participant explained that this situation leads to “*too few requirements and incomplete information about the customer needs*”.

⁴Incomplete knowledge of agile methods

Figure 66: Overview of challenges of the use of agile methods
Source: Own representation

In the early years of the start-up life cycle, logistics start-ups are more likely to use agile methods such as Design Thinking and Lean Startup, which concentrate on product development. As the start-ups get older, the framework demonstrates that logistics start-ups apply more different agile methods, mainly Scrum and Kanban.

¹Des Thinking, ²Double Diamond

Figure 67: Overview of agile methods used

Source: Own representation

Since Scrum is the most frequently used agile method across all lifecycle phases in the logistics start-ups for which the survey participants work, a more detailed look is taken at the agile practices used: "Daily Standups" are most commonly used in all start-ups, regardless of age. "Daily standups" are a popular agile practice to enable exchange within the (development) team. In addition to "Daily Standups", logistics start-ups of all lifecycle phases generally emphasise close exchange within the team. The older the start-ups get, the more agile practices like a Kanban board are used to visualise current and upcoming tasks in order to organise and plan the next tasks of the development team.

Organisational meetings such as "Sprint Plannings" and "Reviews" to structure the software development process are also used, especially in logistics start-ups older than five years. In the survey, participants from start-ups more than five years old state that they use agile methods and practices to increase productivity and streamline processes (see Figure 57 – Agile methods for the realisation of specific benefits, page 145). The findings of the Delphi study affect the development of the framework as well: experts of the Delphi study working in start-ups that are older than five years declare that they apply agile methods to enhance productivity (see Section 5.3. – Implications of the findings, page 124). Younger start-ups are more likely to concentrate on gathering customer feedback and delivering products quickly.

Participants of the interviews and the Delphi study indicate in many cases that they do not have the time to look for the most suitable agile approach and that they simply begin to work in the manner that suits them best. The employees of these start-ups do not necessarily pursue a particular approach, but often only later realise that the way of working in their start-up resembles a particular agile method. A quote from a participant in the Delphi study, translated from German into English, reads as follows: *“Often the way we work results implicitly from what we consider useful, rather than from a specific model that has been implemented.”*

³Close Feedback Cycles with the Customer

Figure 68: Overview of agile practices used

Source: Own representation

Figure 69 and 70 show who first initiated the use of agile methods and who selected the applied agile methods. For logistics start-ups younger than ten years, the responses were quite homogenous. In most cases, the initiative for the use of agile methods originates from the team lead, the team itself, or an agile coach.

⁸Head of department

Figure 69: Overview on the initiators (role) of agile methods

Source: Own representation

The pattern of the people who chose the agile method that is to be used it is rather similar to the initiators (see Figure 70). In younger start-ups the selection is made by the team itself, the team lead, and/or the agile coach. As the start-ups age, external consultants or roles higher up in the hierarchy, such as the head of department, are involved.

⁸Head of department, ⁹Senior management

Figure 70: Overview on the selectors (role) of agile methods

Source: Own representation

7.5. Application of the framework

The framework is intended for both practitioners and researchers. Practitioners from logistics start-ups can apply the framework for the aspects below:

- Comparison of own start-up with other logistics start-ups with regard to the agile methods and practices applied. Practitioners can assess the reason and motivation of other start-ups for using agile methods and benefit from this knowledge to refine their approach to creating value for the customer and the organisation of their internal processes.
- Gain knowledge of the challenges encountered by other logistics start-ups. Practitioners can acquire insights into the challenges faced by logistics start-ups of the same age, but also older ones. This can be beneficial to anticipate and prepare for, and quickly resolve or even avoid challenges.

Practitioners from established logistics companies profit from the framework in the following aspects:

- Learning from the approach of logistics start-ups and the use of agile methods by logistics start-ups to become better in areas such as innovation capability, where start-ups have a tendency to be better than established companies.
- Comparing their total implementation of agile methods with the approach of logistics start-ups and evaluating the differences in application based on data provided by other companies in the same industry. On the basis of these differences, practitioners from established logistics companies can take action to optimise their processes and achieve the benefits of using agile methods.

For researchers, the framework provided can be useful due to the following aspects:

- Collecting data in a so far barely researched area of agility in logistics companies and especially in logistics start-ups.
- Using the outcomes shown of logistics start-ups around the world for follow-up studies. Researchers could compare the data collected in this PhD study and the framework developed with start-ups from other industries or take a closer look at logistics start-ups from specific regions.

Both researchers and practitioner profit from the following aspect:

- Improving processes in logistics companies and developing best practices that are useful not only for logistics start-ups but also for established logistics companies that potentially experience comparable challenges as older, more mature logistics start-ups.

7.6. Classification of frameworks

In section 8.1., related frameworks that describe criteria for the use of agile methods are presented. Since no framework looking into the use of agile methods in logistics start-ups could be found, a framework has been developed based on the research data gathered here. To situate the developed framework in the research context, it is subsequently compared with other frameworks that detail the development of start-ups and the evolution of their needs as they grow older.

Identification of related publications

This section describes other publications that focus on the evolution of start-ups and their characteristics over time. Those frameworks are consulted to verify the developed framework, as all of them concentrate on the development of start-ups and their requirements over time. The relevant papers use qualitative methods such as case studies and interviews, but also evaluate larger samples

of more than 300 start-ups. No publication with a framework specifically for logistics companies was found. The following sections concludes the most important publications (see Table 26). Publications are listed in chronological order.

Table 26: Publications related to the framework developed

Author, Year	Methodology	Aim of the study	Dimensions evaluated to describe the evolution of start-ups
Ho Park and Hwang, 2006	Quantitative analysis of 346 biotech firms	Evaluate the evolution of strategic alliances in start-ups over their life cycles	Alliances
Giardino, Wang and Abrahamsson, 2014	Literature review, multiple case study	Understand which dimensions affect failure in software start-ups	Product, team, market, and business
Sekliuckiene, Vaitkienė and Vestinainauskienė, 2018	Literature review	Assess organisational learning levels emerging in specific life cycle stages of a global start-up	Organisation, product, market, funding
Gralha et al., 2018	Grounded Theory	Describe the evolution of needs of software start-ups over their life cycles	Product quality, technical debt, planning, requirement related roles, knowledge management, requirements artefacts
Degl'innocenti, 2019	Qualitative interviews	Analyse the ways service design contributes to a better understanding of organisational development	Organisational development, collaboration

In the following, the developed framework is compared to other publications that address the evolution of start-ups with regard to various aspects.

Hwang and Ho Park (2006) assess the evolutionary importance of alliances over the life cycle of biotech start-ups, and those studied enter into different alliances. Many companies appear to form them directly in the so-called "birth phase of the organisational life cycle" (Ho Park and Hwang, 2006) to decrease costs, especially in R&D activities. Start-ups in the birth and growth phase enter into alliances with partners who have a common strategic orientation in order to expand their knowledge in their specific niche. Mature start-ups, on the other hand, attempt to form alliances with partners with complementary resources in order to increase their market share.

Giardino et al. (2014) analyse which factors affect the success of software start-ups. Although it is advisable to first comprehend the problem/solution fit of the product (Ries, 2017), start-ups often

give priority to product development in order to bring a product to market as quickly as possible. Neglect of customer feedback and thus lack of problem-solution fit is the reason for failure on the part of the start-ups studied within the study of Giardino et al. (Giardino, Wang and Abrahamsson, 2014). By examining the performance of the two start-ups, which faced similar hurdles during their evolution, Giardino et al. built a framework that comprises four phases. In the first phase, the fit between problem and solution must be identified. After adding functionality and improving the design in the second phase, the framework recommends growing the team in the third phase. In the final stage, the framework suggests the development of a strategic business model and a sales roadmap.

Sekliuckiene et al. (2018) show that, at different life cycle stages, organisational learning processes in global start-ups vary. Furthermore, the results of the literature review show that "learning processes of cyclical entrepreneurial learning" are necessary to enter the next life cycle phase (Sekliuckiene, Vaitkienė and Vestinaainauskiene, 2018). This implies that start-up employees need to learn from their successes and failures in one life-cycle phase in order to progress to the next. Sekliuckiene et al. show that as start-ups mature, strategic planning, internal processes and scaling become increasingly important to them.

Gralha et al. (2018) describe requirements evolution in software start-ups along six dimensions: Requirements artefacts, knowledge management, requirements-related roles, planning, technical debt and product quality. The start-ups' advances along these six dimensions reflect their respective ability to satisfy customer needs, respond more effectively to changing requirements, and allocate resources effectively (Gralha et al., 2018). Even if the six dimensions are not essential for success, they contribute to the maturation and growth of start-ups.

Degl'innocenti (2019) describes the history of organisational development in companies and the difficulties companies experience at the time of this research. She assessed whether service design can enhance the current perception of organisational development, summarised the most important publications and created a definition of organisational development (Degl'innocenti, 2019). In the first step of organisational development, it is necessary to understand the organisation's values and maximise them. After this, the company's strategy is aligned with them so that the organisation's success can be maximised. Thirdly, the focus moves to the employees and the optimisation of internal processes.

7.7. Comparison to other frameworks on the evolution of start-ups

To sum up the overview of related frameworks (see Section 7.6. – Classification of frameworks, page 169), it can first be noted that no scientific framework that looked at the evolution of logistics start-ups has been found. Overall, the following scientific value can be determined:

- Hwang and Park (2006) present results on biotech start-ups, which appear to be more technology-oriented than logistics start-ups. Biotech start-ups depend heavily on R&D activities and require alliances to expand their market shares. For this reason, Hwang and Park focus on alliances in their description of the development of biotech start-ups and do not examine the internal organisation and processes of start-ups, which are the main focus of this study. Nevertheless, Hwang and Park's data show that younger start-ups focus on developing knowledge in their specific niches to improve product development. These results have similarities with the findings of this study, as described above: The focus of young start-ups is indeed on developing business value and customer satisfaction (see Figure 64, page 165). The findings of this study indicate that younger start-ups are strongly focused on developing the right products and delivering products quickly.
- Giardino et al. (2014) describe the factors that can cause software start-ups to fail. Although addressing these factors can extend the life of a start-up, Giardino et al. do not explicitly define start-up evolution, which is the focus of the scope of this study. However, Giardino et al. outline that product development is one of the most important aspects of the first life cycle, which is consistent with the use of agile methods by the start-ups participating in the survey conducted here. In the Delphi study and the survey, the participants indicated that they mainly use agile methods for the development of their products.
- Sekliuckiene et al. (2018) explain organisational learning during the start-up lifecycle. They emphasise the importance of cyclical learning and the use of iterations to learn from customer feedback. Sekliuckiene et al. do not concentrate on agile methods and practices or the logistics industry, but the framework they developed has similarities to the framework of this study. In Sekliuckiene et al.'s framework, product design is the goal of start-ups in their first lifecycle phase, which is consistent with the use of agile methods by the start-ups studied here. Sekliuckiene et al. state that more mature start-ups shift their focus to internal processes and strategies. This is also consistent with the responses of the survey participants in this study,

as they concentrate more and more on improving internal processes and adopting agile scaling methods.

- Gralha et al. (2018) describe in detail how to deal with changing requirements in software start-ups. Although they do not present agile methods, their holistic approach is related to the framework presented in this study, as agile methods are mainly used in software departments to deal with recurring, shifting requirements. This publication is advantageous for this study as it illustrates the relationship between different dimensions and emphasises the importance of focusing not only on the product, its design and customer benefits, but also on the needs of the organisation. Similar to this study, Gralha et al. describe that start-ups need to be flexible in terms of their product development and implementation of customer requirements, but they also need to meet the needs of their employees in order to develop.
- Degl'innocenti (2019) describes a generic approach to organisational development for companies, and her approach does not specifically address logistics start-ups. However, her study provides a valuable basis for understanding organisational development in general and can also be applied to logistics start-ups. For the present study, her description of organisational development proves to be very valuable. Degl'innocenti's findings have similarities with the framework developed in this study: she articulates that companies first concentrate on the value they create for their customers through their products. Accordingly, the younger start-ups in this study focus on developing customer value. As start-ups get older, both Degl'innocenti and the framework of this study describe that they focus more on organisational structures.

The framework developed in this study is built on the collection of qualitative and quantitative data from the practice. It outlines knowledge that is verified by other studies. However, no framework could be identified that explicitly relates to logistics start-ups and their use of agile methods.

7.8. Utility of the framework and limitations

An essential advantage of the proposed framework is the focus on practitioners. Agile methods put people at the centre and aim to quickly maximise the value created by products. To become a value-driven logistics start-up, it is necessary to constantly challenge and improve all processes in place with a view to quickly creating customer value. The framework created here facilitates this approach by enabling logistics companies to compare themselves with the current application of agile methods

of other logistics start-ups of different ages and lifecycle stages. A closer look at the agile practices applied can be particularly helpful for practitioners to better comprehend why numerous experts and departments in logistics start-ups apply agile methods. Established logistics companies can also learn from the way logistics start-ups work: start-ups have to deal with the pressure to build innovative products and apply appropriate working methods, such as agile methods. Digitalisation is putting increased pressure on some established logistics companies to innovate as well. Therefore, these incumbents need to adapt their ways of working and implement agile methods. The framework presented illustrates what motivates participants to use agile methods (i.e. their benefits), what challenges they face and how and by whom the use of agile methods can be supported. In addition, practitioners can apply this framework during retrospectives to broaden the view of development teams to other potential advantages and challenges, as the goal of retrospectives is to examine and adjust the existing organisational environment. Practitioners could profit from these results and discover why other companies may be faster in developing new innovative products. The framework can be utilised by researchers to evaluate which agile methods are used by logistics companies and why these methods are selected. Researchers can also use the framework to elaborate on the findings through case studies, e.g. in different types of logistics companies or in different cultural contexts.

It must be noted that the framework represents the current status of the application of agile methods as it is presently handled in logistics start-ups. Future studies such as case studies could examine whether this current status can also be understood as a recommendation.

It can be reasoned that using a framework in the field of ASD in the logistics industry might be too inflexible and/or increase the overall effort required to apply agile methods. For this reason, however, the framework concentrates on areas that have a strong effect on the success of start-ups. Many participants in the interviews, Delphi study and survey stated that start-ups need to be agile to be successful. For this reason, the framework seeks to facilitate the adoption of agile methods for logistics start-ups.

As the design of a framework determines the outcomes for practitioners and researchers, several discussions with researchers and business experts were held during the development of the framework. Nevertheless, it cannot be ruled out that personal subjective ideas have been incorporated into the design. The framework is based on the findings of an SLR, a Delphi study and a survey conducted worldwide to collect different perspectives from logistics incumbents and logistics start-ups.

It needs to be mentioned that not only time and age influence the development of logistics start-ups with regard to the use of agile methods and practices; other environmental and organisational variables have potentially impacted the selection and use of agile methods and practices.

Finally, for a more in-depth investigation, case studies can be beneficial to enhance the current understanding. The insights gathered in this framework, which concentrate on logistics start-ups, can be compared with the application of agile methods in more established logistics companies or in other industries. It could also be of interest to consider specifically older start-ups and compare them with established logistics companies to identify the differences and outline the transition from logistics start-up to established logistics company in terms of the use of agile methods.

7.9. Conclusion

The goal of this chapter is to consolidate the results of the interviews, the SLR, the Delphi study, and the survey. No framework could be identified that evaluated or structured the use of agile methods in the logistics industry. Results of the performed studies of this PhD study are consolidated to develop a framework that shows which agile methods and practices are used, what benefits logistics start-ups aim to realise through their use, and what challenges they face. The framework contributes to the work of practitioners in logistics start-ups, as they can compare themselves with other logistics start-ups. Practitioners from established logistics companies can use the framework to comprehend how logistics start-ups work differently, and how they cope with the digitalisation. Researchers benefit from the framework as it starts to close the identified research gaps. Further studies can be conducted based on the findings consolidated in the framework as well. In the next chapter, the overall results of this study, its main contributions, and its limitations are presented. An outlook for further research is given.

8. Conclusion and further research

In the previous chapter, the framework that has been developed within this study is presented. It is based on the results of the interviews, the SLR, the Delphi study, and the survey, and therefore based on the real-life experiences of employees from established logistics companies and logistics start-ups. The aim of the framework is to support practitioners in the logistics industry in their use of agile methods in order to deal with the increasing complexity of products and processes. The framework supports practitioners in improving organisational processes through the application of agile methods and practices and in adapting to an ever-more digital environment. This framework optimises the process of value delivery in agile IT projects to satisfy individual customer requirements flexibly. It is based on an inductive research approach in which findings from the conducted research studies are used to develop the individual elements of the framework. A particular focus is set on agile methods and practices used by logistics start-ups, the benefits of their application, the challenges that arise during their application and supporting measures for their introduction. In this chapter, the research design is explained and the results of the study are summarised. Contributions and limitations are covered and a future outlook is given. To conclude, final remarks are made.

8.1. Applied research design

The research design consists of explorative interviews, an SLR, a Delphi study, and a survey. In the first step, the use of agile methods in logistics start-ups was examined through the interviews. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with employees of 12 logistics start-ups. Specifically, it was evaluated to what extent agile methods are used, whether they offer a competitive advantage, and whether they have an impact on the success of the start-up. These interviews provide deep insights into the field of agile methods in logistics start-ups, with a particular focus on:

- Understanding of agility and agile methods
- Use of agile methods and practices
- Impact on the success of the logistics start-ups
- Ways to measure success in logistics start-ups

The interviews validate the relevance of the research topic. The participants confirmed the use of agile methods in logistics start-ups and emphasised that agility is a prerequisite for the success of start-ups in general. Furthermore, the interviews allow the development of the following three research questions, or RQs (see Section 3.3.1. - Interviews, page 64):

Research Question 1: Which agile methods and practices do established logistics companies and logistics start-ups use?

Research Question 2: What challenges do established logistics companies and logistics start-ups solve with agile methods?

Research Question 3: What difficulties do established logistics companies and logistics start-ups face concerning the adoption of agile methods and practices?

In the second step, the use of agile methods in the logistics industry was analysed based on the literature using an SLR. For this purpose, the most relevant related publications regarding agility in the logistics industry in general, and with a special focus on the use of agile methods in established logistics companies as well as in logistics start-ups, were presented. The SLR consolidates the results of other publications in the field of agile methods in the logistics industry, with a particular focus on:

- Identification of the need for further research and validation of the research gap
- Answers in the literature for the three RQs (see Section 4.2.3.2. - Results SLR, page 92)

Based on the SLR, gaps in the existing research could be identified: very few publications present findings on the use of agile management methods in (established) logistics companies, and no publication focusing on logistics start-ups could be found.

In the next step, an iterative Delphi study was conducted. The Delphi study aimed to collect information on the current use of agile methods by questioning 29 experts from established logistics companies as well as from logistics start-ups on agile methods. Within three complementary rounds, data to answer the three RQs (see above) was collected. In contrast to the explorative interviews, not only employees of logistics start-ups were questioned, but also employees of established logistics companies. This allowed for a broader impression of the logistics industry in general. It also helped to identify whether characteristics of logistics start-ups are based on specifics of the logistics industry. Comparing the results of the Delphi study to larger studies such as the *State of Agile Report*, differences as compared with other industries can be detected (VersionOne, 2019).

In the fourth step, an international survey was performed. The aim of this survey was to validate the findings of the Delphi study and collect a wider set of data on the current use of agile methods by questioning 95 employees from logistics start-ups worldwide. In contrast to the Delphi study, only employees of logistics start-ups were surveyed, to focus the analysis on logistics start-ups and to gather a solid data set for the development of the framework. Overall, the results of the interviews,

the SLR, the Delphi study and the survey data can be used to describe the current use of agile methods in established logistic companies and logistic start-ups.

In the final step, a framework that consolidates the findings of the interviews, the SLR, the Delphi study, and the survey was created. The consolidation of the findings presents the most important aspects of all data gathered into one framework to support the application of agile methods in logistics start-ups and established logistics companies and map them to the life cycle stages of the logistics start-ups. For researchers the framework reduces the identified research gap in the use of agile methods in the logistics industry and lays a foundation for future research. Practitioners benefit from the framework, as it aids them in selecting suitable agile methods and in using agile methods in the most optimal way.

An essential advantage of the developed framework is the concentration on practitioners. Agile methods are human-centred and aim to quickly maximise the value generated by products in complex environments. To become a value-based logistics company, it is necessary to constantly optimise and improve all processes used with a focus on creating customer value quickly. The framework created in this study supports logistics companies by enabling them to compare themselves with logistics start-ups of different ages and life cycle phases. In particular, a closer look at the agile practices being implemented can be useful for practitioners to better understand why many logistics start-ups use agile methods, and which ones they choose. The presented framework shows what motivates practitioners to use agile methods, what challenges they encounter, and how and by whom the use of agile methods can be supported. The framework can also be used during retrospectives to change existing processes and find solutions for existing challenges. Practitioners can benefit from the results presented in the framework and learn why other companies are faster at developing new innovative products and are better at meeting customer needs. Additionally, the framework can be used by researchers to evaluate which agile methods are applied by logistics companies and why these methods are selected. Researchers can use the framework to deepen the findings through case studies, e.g. in different regions of the world. Furthermore, best practices can be derived from the framework with the help of further in-depth studies. It is conceivable, for example, that employees of logistics start-ups could be supported by the framework in the selection and introduction of agile methods in line with their requirements. Further contributions are shown in section 8.7. (page 171).

8.2. Answers to the three research questions

In the following, answers to the three RQs which were derived based on the interview results are summarised.

Results Research Question 1: What agile methods and practices do established logistics companies and logistics start-ups use?

The SLR showed that XP, Scrum, and other agile areas such as agile manufacturing and business agility are used by established logistics firms. The publications that focus on the other areas of agility, such as supply chain agility, are included in the SLR to show that agility itself is widespread within the logistics industry. However, the focus of the SLR is on agile IT project management methods, which are only covered by a few publications so far. As of January 2021, no paper that focused on the use of agile methods and practices in logistics start-ups was available. Therefore, no response can be given for logistics start-ups. In terms of agile practices, established logistics companies mostly use guidelines such as continuous improvement, team empowerment, and customer focus. It needs to be noted that these guidelines are helpful to build a successful agile organisation but are not agile practices in an academic sense.

The results of the Delphi study demonstrate that Scrum and Kanban are the agile methods most commonly applied in both established logistics companies and logistics start-ups. As for the agile practices, “Daily Standup” followed by a “Close exchange within the team”, “Reviews” and “Retrospectives” are applied most frequently (see Section 5.3. – Implications of the findings, page 124). Many logistics start-ups use the “Creation of minimum viable products”. Decisions to select these agile methods and practices are mainly guided by the following criteria: “Previous experience”, on the “Fit to special company requirements”, and “Team size”. Established logistics companies often also take “Company guidelines” and the “Advice of external consultants” into account.

Similar to the Delphi study, findings of the survey demonstrate that Scrum and Kanban are the agile methods used most frequently by logistics start-ups. Most participants from the logistics start-ups adjust agile methods and practices to their individual needs. In terms of agile practices, “Close exchange within the team”, “Update of the Kanban board”, and “Daily Standups” are used most often (see Section 6.3. – Results of the survey, page 135). In start-ups younger than one year, team leaders or the team itself decide which agile methods to implement. As start-ups become older, fewer

decisions are taken by the team and the team leaders and more are made by agile coaches, external consultants, or the head of department.

Overall Scrum, XP, Lean startup and Kanban are the agile methods applied most often by companies within the logistics industry. The agile practices applied most frequently are “Daily (Standup)”, “Close exchange within the team” and the “Update of the Kanban board”. There is hardly any noteworthy difference in the results between logistics start-ups and established logistics companies; the only major difference is the greater use of Lean startup in logistics start-ups.

Results Research Question 2: What challenges do established logistics companies and logistics start-ups solve with agile methods?

The results for the second RQ of the SLR can be clustered into customer-related benefits, product-related benefits, communication-related benefits, and processual and organisational benefits. As no study that focused on logistics start-ups could be found, no specific challenges for logistics start-ups are identified. Through the use of agile methods and practices, established logistics companies increase their ability to satisfy changing customer requirements and reduce costs and speed of product adjustments. Another goal is to align business and IT through communication, to reduce personnel bottlenecks, and to deal with complex processes.

The Delphi study shows that established logistics companies and logistics start-ups aim to increase their responsiveness to changing internal and external requirements, accelerate their product delivery, and optimise the alignment between the customers/users and IT departments. “Sprint Plannings”, “Regular feedback cycles with the customers” and “Regular (software) delivery” are commonly used agile practices to realise these benefits (see Section 5.3. – Implications of the findings, page 124).

The findings of the survey reveal that the most important benefits that logistics start-ups aim to achieve with agile methods and practices are an increased customer and employee satisfaction, increased flexibility of the product scope, and improved communication. Scrum is mostly used for the optimisation of processes and the increase of productivity (see Section 6.3. – Results of the survey, page 135). Lean startup is applied to reduce risks and costs and to react to external changes. Looking at the effectiveness of the agile methods, Scrumban, followed by Kanban and Scrum, are ranked the highest.

Overall, satisfying customer requirements, responsiveness to changing requirements, improved communication with the customer and within the development teams, and employee satisfaction are

the main benefits of the use of agile methods. Whereas established logistics companies tend to focus more on customer-related benefits, the findings show that logistics start-ups weigh internal benefits such as employee satisfaction a similarly to customer satisfaction.

Results Research Question 3: What difficulties do established logistics companies and logistics start-ups face concerning the adoption of agile methods and practices?

The third RQ discussed difficulties that established logistics companies and logistics start-ups face when applying agile methods and practices. The results of the SLR could be clustered into product-related, processual, and people-related difficulties. The most common challenges when applying agile methods and practices are finding the right product design that allows for supply chain agility, identifying drivers that increase agility, and most demanding of all, creating an agile culture and introduce an agile mindset. Even though this is but one of many people-related difficulties, it should not be underestimated, as the success of agile methods and practices depends heavily upon the support and comprehension of employees.

Results of the Delphi study demonstrate that challenges affected, in particular, the organisational culture, as well as fear and resistance to change (see Section 5.3. – Implications of the findings, page 124). Especially in established logistics companies, these mindset-related issues appear to be a big issue. Start-ups in logistics tend to encounter difficulties with a lack of knowledge distribution in their agile teams and a lack of product owners.

The data of the survey shows that unequal distribution of knowledge and incomplete knowledge of agile methods are the biggest challenges when introducing them (see Section 6.3. – Results of the survey, page 135). Over the life cycles of the logistics start-ups the participant's answers show that more and more a strict organisational culture and the lack of a product owner become an increasing challenge.

Overall, existing legal structures of the company, strict hierarchies, and organisational culture, but also the lack of human resources and knowledge within the development team, are the biggest challenges according to the conducted studies. It becomes apparent that in established companies, hierarchies and strict organisational structure limit the use of agile methods. Logistics start-ups face greater challenges regarding the distribution of knowledge within the development team and missing knowledge on the use of agile methods.

Summarising the implications of this study, it can be stated that by identifying the applicability of agile methods in the logistics industry, evidence for the benefits of agile methods in the logistics industry was identified. Which agile methods are used most, what benefits they bring, and what needs to be considered when introducing and applying agile methods were investigated. Finally, these aspects were consolidated into a framework for practitioners and researchers. Practitioners of logistics start-ups can compare their own approach with start-ups of the same age range but can also learn from more experienced and older start-ups. Equally, practitioners of established logistics companies can learn from the way logistics start-ups use agile methods. Furthermore, the framework is helpful for practitioners of established logistics companies, as they possibly benefit from the innovation approach of logistics start-ups. Researchers can use the framework as a basis for understanding the use of agile methods in the logistics industry, and to deepen research based on it to further narrow the research gap.

8.3. Main and complementary research findings

By questioning practitioners, it was validated that the use of agile methods is increasing in logistics companies. In the same way, it is also apparent that the number of publications on logistics start-ups and on the use of agile methods in the logistics industry is growing. Only a few publications that cover both topics, agile methods and logistics companies, could be identified. The identified publications and the results of the studies of this study describe how agile methods and practices are used in logistics start-ups and established logistics companies. Scrum, XP, and Kanban are the agile methods that are most common. Increased customer and employee satisfaction and faster communication cycles are the most relevant benefits that can be realised through the use of agile methods. Unequal distribution of knowledge, fear of change, and incomplete knowledge on the use of agile methods are the biggest challenges. By looking at the differences between logistics start-ups and established logistics companies, several differences could be identified. Logistics start-ups are often faster at bringing innovations to the market and at increasing customer value through customer feedback than established logistics companies are. Some of the reasons for the higher innovation speed of logistics start-ups are, among others, the organisational culture and the mindset of the employees. The realisation of benefits from the use of agile methods depends heavily on internal structures and the commitment of employees. In more established logistics companies, some employees tend to be afraid of change or are trapped in rigid organisational hierarchies. All in all, the employees of logistics start-ups seem to be more open to change and working in more self-organised ways than those of established logistics companies.

In summary, the following activities have been conducted to obtain results that are described below:

- Validation of the need for research and development of the RQs.
- Performance of an SLR to present the state of research in the field of the application of agile methods by logistics start-ups and established logistics companies.
- Execution of a qualitative Delphi study to determine which agile methods and practices are used in established logistics company and logistics start-ups.
- Realisation of an international survey to deepen the results of the Delphi study focusing on logistics start-ups.
- Description of the use of agile methods and practices by established logistics companies and logistics start-ups based on the findings in the literature and in real life.
- Creation of a framework that supports practitioners in their current use of agile methods and helps practitioners prepare for the selection and introduction of appropriate agile methods in their own logistics start-ups.

The framework is based on data from logistics companies of different ages and thus shows which characteristics the companies tend to have at different points in time. The seven dimensions of the framework that is the main contribution of this study, which support logistics start-ups and established logistics companies using agile methods, are as follows:

- Agile methods used
- Agile practices used
- Benefits of agile methods
- Challenges faced using agile methods
- Support measures when introducing agile methods
- Initiator (role) of the use of agile methods
- Selector (role) of agile methods

The framework offers several advantages for logistics start-ups and established logistics companies. The results it presents based on the ages of logistics start-ups are also helpful for established logistics companies that aim to or already use agile methods, e.g. to handle complexity. The framework can also be used to increase the innovativeness and speed to market of new products. Logistics start-ups and established logistics companies can apply it to benefit from the experience of others in order to

improve their value creation process and increase satisfaction of customer needs by optimising the use of agile methods. Additionally, the framework can also be used to optimise internal processes by comparing already-used approaches with the agile approaches of other logistics start-ups. The optimisation of internal processes could make the everyday work more productive and satisfying for employees.

The framework presented enables practitioners to improve their value creation process, increase customer satisfaction, and optimise internal processes. Researchers benefit from the framework as it starts to close the identified research gap and can be used to develop best practices for the use of agile methods in the logistics industry.

8.4. Contribution to knowledge

This study makes multiple contributions to theory and practice that can be drawn from the research results. Contributions are made in the following two areas:

- Managerial implications and real-life applications
- Research implications and methodology

Contributions are interesting for management practice and real-life application, some add knowledge to the existing theory of IT project management, product design and development processes in IT. As contribution to research a methodological approach is presented for so far rather unexplored research areas. In the following sections both contributions, for practice and for theory, are presented and discussed separately.

8.4.1. Managerial implications

The purpose of this applied research study is to provide answers for practitioners in the logistics industry, to influence the way projects are managed and the way software is developed to increase productivity and added value for customers. This work contributes a conceptual approach for the use of agile methods and practices in the logistics industry in the form of a framework. The framework presents the current application of agile methods in logistics start-ups and is created based on the findings of the SLR, the Delphi study, and the survey. It can be used to compare individual use of agile methods to that of other logistics start-ups but also to adjust the use of agile methods for future challenges and benefits presented in the framework. Three main implications for employees of established logistics companies and logistics start-ups can be derived from the results of this study.

First, the framework provides an overview of the most commonly used agile methods in logistics start-ups across the different life cycle stages of the start-ups. Employees from established logistics companies and logistics start-ups can use it to understand what agile methods are used by other firms and evaluate which agile methods they want to use. The presentation of agile methods for logistics start-ups of different age ranges shows that agile methods are used for various objectives, e.g. to speed up product development, but also to increase productivity. Particularly, in the context of increasing complexity (see Section 1 – Introduction, page 1) and the rising level of digitalisation, agile methods support companies in reacting quickly to changes. The importance of software development only continues to grow in the logistics industry, and as agile methods are used to support an efficient software development process, it is helpful for practitioners in the logistics industry to gain an understanding of how, and which, agile methods are applied by other logistics companies. It needs to be noted that the different age ranges of start-ups do not constitute hard delineating limits, but rather describe a smooth transition from one range to the next.

The second implication for managers to be derived from the framework is an overview of the benefits and challenges that arise when applying agile methods. Knowing the benefits and potential challenges is essential for the successful implementation and use of these methods. Through the presentation in the framework, practitioners can recognise which goals other logistics companies want to achieve through the use of agile methods, and which of them are then used for the achievement of these goals. It is also possible to see how the focus of the logistics companies changes with regard to their set goals over the age ranges of the start-ups. According to the framework, product development and meeting customer needs are the main focus for younger start-ups that are less than three years old; start-ups older than three years concentrate more and more on internal aspects, such as the optimisation of productivity and the improvement of communication. The framework also supports practitioners in circumventing challenges by outlining which challenges are becoming more prevalent over time, which can help them to prepare for challenges in advance.

In the discussions with the employees of logistics start-ups, it became clear that start-ups cannot function without agility, and that the degree of agility of the organisation and their product can bring a decisive competitive advantage. From the framework, practitioners can understand what the employees of start-ups in the same industry have experienced. For practitioners, the pieces of information that are consolidated into the framework can result in competitive advantages. Looking at the research topic on a larger scale, the framework not only supports the use of agile methods but

also enables companies to shorten waiting times, optimise the use of transport locations and minimise transport routes. These potential optimisations could make the logistics industry more innovative, sustainable and reduce CO2 emissions. This can massively increase competitive sustainability. The results and the framework also support companies in responding better to the changes of globalisation through the iterative approach of agile methods.

Numerous participants in the interviews and survey confirm that the use of agile methods is necessary to be successful. Thus, the investigation of the research topic and the presentation of the results increases the survivability of logistics companies. The customers of logistics companies also benefit from this study, as the use of agile methods focuses on understanding customer needs and maximising customer added value. In addition, this study creates added value because not only the use of external resources but also the use of employee resources can be improved through agile methods. Overall, this can generate a competitive advantage for logistics companies in times of resource scarcity.

8.4.2. Contribution to research

In addition to the managerial implications, this study contributes to the theory of agile IT project management in the logistics industry and provides a methodology to approach rather unexplored research fields. Researchers benefit from this study and investigation, which aim to diminish the research gap identified. Researchers can use this study as a basis for conducting further studies, e.g. large scale surveys, to expand findings. Overall, three contributions were identified, which are presented in the following subsection.

The first contribution to research is the finding that agile methods are being used in the logistics industry. It has been validated that agile methods are therefore not only used in purely software development companies, but also in other industries and their (IT) projects and (IT) departments. The interviews, the SLR, the Delphi study, and the survey show that different types of agility play a role in supply chains as well as in the IT departments of established logistics companies as well as those of logistics start-ups. Agile methods are increasingly used in IT departments and IT projects in order for companies to be able to react more flexibly to customer needs and to cope with growing complexity that arises due to increasing digitalisation, among other things. These findings can be further used by science and researchers as follows:

- Analyse the various areas in the logistics industry where agility plays an important role to understand how the different types of agility (see Section 4.1.1 – Background, page 68) are related to and interact with each other.
- Evaluate agile approaches in different types of companies, such as established companies and logistics start-ups, to find out what differentiates the companies and what they can learn from each other.

For researchers, that the way IT projects and IT departments are managed might give a competitive advantage in the logistics industry has been confirmed. Not only project management itself is important, but also the way that project management fits the needs of the project, the development team, and the product. In the complex environment of the logistics industry, the use of agile methods supports the success of logistics companies. The fact that the employees of logistics start-ups have emphasised in numerous cases that agility and the use of agile methods are relevant to be capable of competing confirms that there is a connection between success and agility of logistics start-ups. This connection could be quantified in the future.

In this study, a hitherto largely unexplored research topic was addressed with a specific methodology that was designed to find answers in this similarly comparatively unexplored research field. After confirming the relevance of the research topic through interviews and a SLR, data was collected through the iterative Delphi study to answer the RQs. The iterative approach of the three successive rounds of the Delphi study made it possible to deepen the participants' answers bit by bit, and to react to their unexpected answers. The subsequent international survey allowed for the collection of a broader set of data from international participants and allowed the results of the Delphi study to be tested and confirmed. This methodological approach contributes to science, as it is exemplary for other so far unexplored research fields, especially in those research areas in which qualitative data is collected; the applied research methodology can be adopted as a prototype for similar situations.

For other researchers, this study adds scientific value due to the high quality level. The quality is ensured by the number of different studies conducted, which are combined in a multi-method approach. So far, no study has been found on the use of agile methods in the logistics industry that takes into account the literature as well as from a practice perspective. This study presents knowledge from a rather unexplored area. The publication of the study results in several recognised scientific

journals and conferences confirms the recognition and importance of these studies and approaches in the scientific community.

8.5. Limitations of the PhD study

The limitations of this study are discussed in this section. The first is that the framework is mainly based on the opinion of the participants of the Delphi study and the survey: overall, it can be assumed that participants in both have a positive attitude towards agile methods and practices. This may have led to a distortion of industry practitioners' general opinions and their prevalence. The framework might include faults and external influences, such as the Covid-19 pandemic, which has caused challenges that may have resulted in a stronger incentive to implement agile methods. Even though the participants were asked about their expertise in agile methods in the Delphi study and the survey, the assessment of one's own expertise is subjective. In order to reduce these limitations, as many participants as possible with different roles, level of experience, and perspectives were interviewed. Additionally, it needs to be remembered that the framework is not necessarily based on the perspectives of practitioners in companies that are successful. They are only successful in the sense that they exist, which is one of several criteria to measure success. A third limitation is the evaluation of the answers by the researcher. The researcher evaluated the participants' answers quantitatively and qualitatively and may have included subjective perspectives that possibly influenced the creation of the framework. Particular attention should be paid to the professional role of the author. She works as a scrum master and agile coach for an IT consultancy and has therefore experienced positive as well as negative examples of application of agile methods in projects, and also in logistics companies as a whole. In general, however, her role demonstrates a positive attitude towards agile methods. Several researchers regularly reviewed the evaluation process of the studies and the framework to mitigate these potential biases, which ensured that their likelihood in the results was reduced. Fourthly, it would also have been possible to use other/additional research methods, which could be critiqued for collecting answers mostly online. However, the Delphi study as a method for collecting knowledge in an unexplored area, as well as the survey for a broader gathering of answers at the time of Covid-19, were found to be the best approach. The methods were compared with other methods and carefully selected. The fifth limitation of this study is that the final framework was not tested, but only discussed with practitioners. The framework ultimately needs to be applied and tested over time to evaluate whether it is useful. Conducting a longitudinal study was not possible in the context of this research, but would be something that could be done in future contexts.

8.6. Outlook for further research

This study has opened up new possibilities for future research, which are outlined in the next sections. A framework was developed to support the use of agile methods in logistics start-ups and established logistics companies; it presents the use of agile methods in logistics start-ups. Following this study, one way to deepen research in this area would be to conduct a survey with employees from established logistics companies worldwide. Through this questioning via an (online) survey, data could be obtained to create a dedicated framework for established logistics companies. In addition to this, data from established companies could be compared with the data from the survey conducted within this study, which could result in a combined framework for logistics start-ups and established logistics companies. Additionally, a detailed comparison of the survey data from logistics start-ups and established logistics companies could be conducted to find areas in which start-ups and established companies could learn from each other. Differences and similarities in the application of agile methods in established logistics companies and logistics start-ups could be compared and evaluated in detail, employees and experts could learn from the experiences of others, and this could in turn help those in the industry to prepare for upcoming and future challenges. After collecting data in the logistics industry, it would be interesting to apply the framework to other industries as well, since this would be useful in terms of learning more about the boundaries of the framework in a real-world context, as well as about and its industry specifics. A next step could also be to deepen the framework and make it more marketable for practitioners, for example by collecting more user data in surveys or conducting longitudinal studies; a clearer quantitative relationship could be drawn between the hoped-for benefits of using agile methods and the actual benefits. Alternatively, practitioners could be supported in selecting the appropriate method based on the goal they want to achieve with agile methods with the help of the framework. Through this quantitative link between benefits and agile methods, patterns could be derived. More gathered data could also help to link the challenges and benefits that arise using agile methods more strongly to the ages, sizes and agile methods being used by logistics companies. In total, there are three future activities that could build on each other:

- Conducting an international survey with employees of established logistics companies worldwide;
- Testing the framework in other industries; and

- Deriving quantitative links or patterns between the achieved benefits, encountered challenges, the characteristics of the logistics companies and the agile methods applied.

Another way of assessing the use and added value of agile methods is to consider at customer satisfaction, the cost of agile methods, and the amount of time spent on them. A survey of failed start-ups, regarding their use of agile methods, could also reveal interesting aspects. However, it is often difficult to get hold of the contact data of failed companies.

Focusing more on specific agile methods, the Scrumban method could be studied more in the future. In this study, Scrumban was rated highest by the survey participants (see Section 6.3.2. – Results of the survey: round 2, page 143). This leads to the question why it is not more widespread and used. This could be another aspect for future research.

Taking a broader view of the research field and going back to the increasing complexity that most industries are currently facing, especially with regard to digitalisation, one could investigate what other approaches exist to cope with this increasing complexity in terms of offering more digital products and maximising customer value. Another topic for future research could be the iterative methodology that was used to approach the comparatively unexplored research fields: within this study it became clear that a methodological approach based on empirical and iterative research is a good way to bridge the gap between science and practice. Methodologically, it could be valuable to investigate and test further methodological iterative approaches aside from the Delphi study and the survey.

8.7. Final remarks

This study offers several contributions in the context of the use of agile methods in the logistics industry. The relevance of the research topic for the logistics industry was first identified through interviews, and, the study subsequently identified an existing research gap in the area of agile project management methods in the logistics industry. In the SLR, several publications that deal with agility in the logistics industry were found; however, there were only a few publications that referred to agile project management methods. The Delphi study and the survey start to close this research gap. The empirical data collected was consolidated into a framework that enables agile practitioners — especially in logistics companies — and researchers to introduce agile methods and optimise their use of said methods. Using the framework helps practitioners to achieve their goals of developing products with maximal customer value and increased productivity. The empirical methodological

approach and the collection of perspectives from employees of logistics companies ensures that the results are very close to the situations and conditions of existing working practices in these logistics companies. Overall, the research area of agile methods in the logistics industry is closely intertwined with practice. The use of agile methods in the IT departments of companies is related to other departments: the successful use of agile methods depends on the support of other departments within the logistics, such as sales, human resources, and finance, for the agile approaches.

Furthermore, it needs to be stated that agility and agile methods can be understood differently within and in the context of (logistics) companies. The Delphi study and the survey showed that many companies apply specific agile practices that are most suited to their needs but do not use the whole range of agile methods that comprise the overall frameworks for agile practices. This finding validated the application of agile methods and practices in logistics companies and shows that they are adapted to the needs of the individual logistics companies. Logistics firms use agile methods and practices in order to be able to react to changes in customer requirements, to increase customer value, and for internal productivity and communication. These companies face challenges using agile methods when employees fear change, or existing organisational structures are too rigid or hierarchical. With the framework created within this study, logistics companies can use dedicated agile methods in a systematic manner. It can be used to select agile methods and practices that are used by other logistics start-ups that have the same goals. The framework can be used worldwide as well, as it is based on the survey data from international logistics start-ups and no significant differences between start-ups from various countries were identified.

This study presented the managerial implications of the results and the framework. Practitioners, especially from logistics companies, can compare their use of agile methods with the ways other logistics companies apply them. Practitioners can evaluate whether they have the same motivation for the application of agile methods and whether they face the same challenges as other companies, and can learn from the experiences the other employees from logistics companies had during the implementation of these methods. The findings of the Delphi study and survey present the consequences of the challenges that the participants faced: a strict organisational culture makes employees more likely to hide mistakes they made rather than proactively informing their colleagues and searching for solutions. The framework assists practitioners in comparing their use of agile methods to other logistics start-ups of the same age. Additionally, practitioners can learn from

challenges older start-ups encountered and use the information to prevent the same types of challenges beforehand.

Research benefits from this study in two ways: firstly, the empirically conducted studies, the Delphi study, and the survey begin to close the identified research gap. The framework consolidates the results into an easily understandable construct that can quickly be further expanded and thus enable further in-depth research. Secondly, this study dealt with a rather unexplored research area and deepened the initial findings of the SLR with an iterative methodology. This approach could be exemplary for other similarly unexplored research areas. Finally, it should be mentioned that most of the contributions made here have already been published and have received very appreciative feedback from the scientific community.

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A. Appendix

A.1. Interview guidelines of the case studies

In the following the interview guidelines of the case studies are presented. The original answers of the participants are available and can be handed out on request.

Introduction and motivation of the interview

- Introduction Mrs. Zielske and Mr. Held
- Introduction of the interviewee
- In the context of my PhD thesis, the correlation of agility and success of logistic start-ups is to be analysed
- This is the first round of exploratory interviews
- It's about:
 - Understanding how start-ups work
 - Getting to know processes and procedures in start-ups
 - The importance of agility for start-ups
 - The measurement of success in start-ups
 - Correlation between agility and success of logistics start-ups
- Motivation for the participation of start-ups:
 - Documentation of this interview as food for thought
 - Anonymous documentation and evaluation of all interviews, comparison possible with other logistics start-ups
 - Possibly a (final) workshop together with other logistic start-ups to deepen the understanding of the correlation of agility and success

General part

- a. Company Name
- b. Year of foundation
- c. Location(s)
- d. Current number of employees in FTE (number of full-time equivalents)
- e. Name of the interviewee
- f. How long have you been part of this start-up?
- g. How many years of experience have you gained in the field of start-ups?
- h. In what other forms of company and how long have you gained experience?
- i. Role of the interviewee
- j. Daily tasks of the interviewee

(i. and j.) To what extent does the interviewee take on tasks requiring an agile approach, or how closely is he actually involved in the processes he describes (see following questions).

Questions about the term agility

1. What do you understand by corporate agility?

Understand what the interviewee means when he uses the term agility. With this knowledge the answers of the interviewee can be better classified. Agility is defined by Conboy and Fitzgerald as "the continued willingness of an entity to accept change through high quality, simple and economic

components and relationships with the environment, fast or inherent, proactive or reactive". So a company is agile if it can accept change and prepare for it.

2. To what extent do you think logistics start-ups should be agile in general?

*It's about understanding whether and why agility is important for start-ups. From this it can be derived how start-ups organise themselves and what they have to do to be able to react agilely. If the respondent's answer is that start-ups **do not** need to be agile, proceed to **question 8.1**.*

3. How do logistics start-ups use agility in general?

Description of how agility is used in the start-up, in which areas it is or isn't important or not used today.

4. Do you have examples of agility in your start-up?

Concretisation of question 4: Description of what agility means in concrete terms in everyday start-up life and in which situations agility was used.

5. How do you ensure the agility of your start-up?

Create an understanding whether the start-up actually works consciously with agile methods or whether it just classifies itself as agile e.g. due to adaptation to changing market situations.

6. Which of the following agile practices are applied by your start-up:

- Working in a cross-functional team (*employees with different skills*)
- Self-organised teams
- Use of short iteration cycles (*the "product" is regularly provided to the customer with small improvements*)
- Transparent progress monitoring (*employees have an overview of the progress of the product*)
- Informal description of the requirements as user stories (*the requirements are NOT planned in advance down to the smallest detail*)
- Application of a prioritised backlog (*new To Dos are systematically processed*)
- Hypothesis testing (*solutions are tested with the customer*)
- Lean startup (*application of short product development cycles to check if the targeted business model is applicable*)

Check whether the start-up uses agile practices. By applying the practices, a start-up is not automatically agile, but the practices are helpful to achieve agility.

7. How do the meanings of the terms "agility", "flexibility" and "responsiveness" differ?

Deepening Question 1, helps to understand whether the interviewee differentiates between the terms and has an explanation for the different meanings. Agility includes more than just the ability to react to unforeseen events and the flexibility to make quick decisions. It is also a matter of delivering the product that meets the customer's requirements in short iterations.

8. To what extent does agility influence the interaction and relationship between colleagues in your start-up?

Allows conclusions to be drawn as to the extent to which the start-up is actually agile. If it is agile, on the one hand interpersonal conflicts become known much more quickly and can be solved. On the

other hand, the agile principles encourage self-organisation and independent assurance of a respectful working atmosphere. Continue with question 9.

8.1. Why don't logistics start-ups generally have to be agile?

Only to be answered if the interviewee said for question 2 that start-ups don't have to be agile. Detailed answer of question 2 for a better understanding.

9. How often does your start-up hold retrospectives or similar meetings to reflect e.g. internal processes or the current market situation?

If there is no regular reflection, there is a lack of transparency about current internal or external improvement potentials, which are therefore not resolved promptly.

10. Can your start-up react to the aspects found from the Retrospectives and find and apply solutions?

Determination of the ability of the start-up company to accept and implement changes at relatively short notice. Agility is defined by Conboy and Fitzgerald as "the continued willingness of an entity to accept change through high quality, simple and economic components and relationships with the environment, fast or inherent, proactive or reactive".

11. Would you describe yourself as more successful than your competitors and why?

In addition to measuring the success of the start-up itself, it is also interesting to understand to what extent they are more successful on the market than their competitors.

12. What are you currently working on with your product and to what extent does this increase the added value for the customer?

The aim of the agile approach is to increase the added value of the product for the customer and at the same time to maximise the amount of work not done. The question is intended to find out to what extent the start-up is aware of whether, for example, it carries out superfluous activities and does something about them.

13. In your opinion, how does agility influence the success of logistics start-ups in general?

The question is intended to clarify how start-ups assess the relationship between agility and success. Is agility something that all start-ups today have to take into account, or can agility be a competitive factor? It should also be understood on which success factors agility has an influence.

14. How is success measured in your start-up?

It should be understood which goals are set in the interviewed start-up and when it considered to be successful. This question is also intended to find out whether the start-ups have different or largely similar goals.

15. Do you consider your start-up to be more agile than your direct competitors and if so, why?

Today, many companies describe themselves as agile. It is interesting to understand how one's own agility is assessed in direct competition with the competition and whether this is a competitive advantage.

16. How has the number of internal and external employees and other cooperation partners developed in the last two years?

Measurement of the resource growth of the start-up. This allows conclusions to be drawn about the prospects for success and the growth of the start-up.

17. How has turnover developed in the last two years?

Measurement of the sales growth / sales figures of the start-up. This allows conclusions to be drawn about the success in the market and the growth of the start-up.

Outro

- k. From your point of view, what question should I have asked in order to explore the correlation between agility of logistics start-ups and success?
- l. Is there anything else you would like to tell me?
- m. Who else could I interview from this start-up?
- n. May I ask you later on for a second interview?
- o. May I afterwards send you an e-mail with a transcript of this interview that you can check for accuracy?
- p. Optional: questionnaire on agile practices

A.2. Research protocol systematic literature review

In the following the research protocol that was applied to perform the SLR is presented. Some paragraphs and figures are already presented in the PhD thesis. They are not removed from this section in the Appendix to guarantee the understandability of the research protocol of the SLR.

Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften Hamburg
Hamburg University of Applied Sciences

Agile methods and practices used by logistic start-ups and traditional logistic companies

Protocol of a systematic literature review
(V1.0, August 2018)

Malena Zielske
Hamburg University of Applied Science

Objectives

The use of agile methods and practices increased in importance especially in software companies in the last years. They are used to cope with rising complexity, rapidly changing customer expectations, business model insecurities, complex technological decisions or other shifting external influences occurring e.g. within cooperations with suppliers. Since agility also depends heavily on the mindset of all employees and promotes the rapid implementation of user-centric solutions, it is particularly appealing to find out how the conservative logistics industry, which is known as a slow adapter (Kupp, Marval and Borchers, 2017), copes with agility. The intention of this systematic literature review is to investigate how other studies describe the use of agile methods and practices by traditional logistic companies and logistic start-ups. It should be investigated if logistic start-ups and traditional companies use the same methods and practices, which problems they want to solve with these methods and practices and what challenges they face.

The aim of this systematic literature review is to:

- clarify the state of the art in the field of the application of agile methods by logistic start-ups and traditional logistic companies
- identify the existing basis for the research of a PhD thesis
- find out where the research fits into the current body of knowledge

The systematic literature review is conducted based on the guidelines from Kitchenham and Charters (Kitchenham and Charters, 2007).

Based on the findings from the systematic literature review a theoretical framework that explains when and how logistic start-ups and traditional logistic companies use agile methods and practices will be deduced.

Research questions

This systematic literature review aims to answer on the following research questions:

Research Question 1: What agile methods and practices do logistic start-ups and traditional logistic companies use?

This question is about finding out which agile methods and practices are actually used by logistics start-ups and traditional logistics companies. On the one hand, it was compared whether logistics start-ups and the traditional companies use the same or similar methods and practices and on the other hand, to what extent the use of agile methods is related to the size of the companies

Research Question 2: What problems do logistic start-ups and traditional logistic companies solve with agile methods?

The goal is to find out for which problems within the organisation, agile methods are used for. I plan to find out which objectives and improvements the start-ups as well as the traditional companies hope for with the use of agile methods and practice.

Research Question 3: What challenges do logistic start-ups and traditional logistic companies face?

For this question, the obstacles logistics start-ups as well as traditional logistics companies encounter when using agile methods are consolidated. I plan to compare whether the obstacles differ between the two forms of company.

Search process

The systematic literature review is based on a manual search with a search string that is adapted for every digital library. Additionally, a reference search is used to find papers that cited the selected paper (forward snowballing) and papers that are in the reference list of the selected paper (backward snowballing). The search is divided into six steps as shown in Figure 71:

Figure 71: Search process of the systematic literature review

Search space

For the systematic literature review, the following digital libraries are taken into account. The digital libraries are listed alphabetically.

Table 27: Used digital libraries

Digital library	Search strategy	Scope
ACM	abstract and keywords	Computing and information technology
Emerald	abstract and keywords	Business, management, real estate economics and finance
Google scholar	full text	As it is unclear which publishers are included in Google Scholar, it is used as a comprehensive addition to the other databases

Digital library	Search strategy	Scope
IEEEExplore	abstract and keywords	Electrical engineering and computer science
Science direct	abstract, title and keywords	Sciences, economic and social science, and some arts and humanities titles
SpringerLink	abstract and keywords	Sciences, economic and social science, and some arts and humanities titles
Wiley	abstract and keywords	Sciences, economic and social science, and some arts and humanities titles

Search keywords

To find keywords as criteria for the search I take an iterative approach. After the first definition of keywords, I add keywords from relevant papers I already read. Afterwards I identify alternative spellings and synonyms. To optimise the search process I optimise the keywords after testing them in digital libraries and finding additional keywords in relevant papers.

Table 28: Overview of the search keywords

#	Topic	Sub Topic	Search Keyword
1	Agile	Agile approach	agile, agile development, agile software development, agile method*, agile practice, agile approach, agile project, agile lifecycle, agile software engineering
		Agile methods	Agile method, agile process, Scrum, Kanban, extreme programming, lean startup, lean development, feature driven development, feature-driven development, dynamic systems development method, adaptive software development, agile unified process, rational unified process, Crystal Clear
2	Logistic	Service	Freight, transport, logistic service, shipping, cargo, distribution, delivery, supply
		Logistic service industry	2PL, 3PL, 4PL, Second party logistic, Third party logistic, Fourth party logistic, Logistic service provider, LSP, Road freight, Road freight hauler, Shipping, Shipper
3	Companies	Traditional companies	Compan*, Firm*, corporation, enterprise, large scale, large organization
		Start-ups	Start-up, start-up, small medium enterprise, SME, venture, early stage firm, early-stage-firm, early stage compan*, early-stage-compan*, entrepreneur*

In a first step, I plan to focus on agile methods and exclude “*agile practices*” because I first wanted to see how many papers there already with focusing on agile methods before I go into more detail.

Search string

Every digital library uses a different search engine, which results in unique characteristics for every search engine. Therefore, different search strings are created. The digital libraries are listed alphabetically.

Search string: ST = [Agile] + [Logistic] + [Companies]

Table 29: Overview of used search string per digital library

Digital library	Search string	Comment
ACM	(agile OR scrum OR kanban OR "Lean startup") AND (freight OR transport OR "logistic service provider" OR "fourth party logistic" OR "Third party logistic" OR "Logistic service") AND (company OR firm OR start-up OR start-up)	No adjustments at the standard search string
Emerald	(agile OR scrum OR kanban OR "Lean startup") AND (freight OR transport OR "logistic service provider" OR "fourth party logistic" OR "Third party logistic" OR "Logistic service") AND (company OR firm OR start-up OR start-up)	No adjustments at the standard search string
IEEEXplore	(agile OR scrum OR kanban OR " extreme programming " OR "Lean startup") AND (freight OR transport OR "logistic service provider" OR "fourth party logistic" OR "Third party logistic" OR "Logistic service" OR " supply chain ") AND (company OR firm OR start-up OR start-up OR venture OR " small medium enterprise ")	Extension of all three components to increase the number of results: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The term "extreme programming" was added to the [Agile] component • The term "supply chain" was added to the [Logistic] component The terms "venture" and "small medium enterprise" was added to the [Companies] component
Google scholar	(agile OR scrum OR "Lean startup") AND (" logistic service provider " OR " fourth party logistic " OR " Third party logistic ") AND (company OR firm OR start-up OR start-up)	Reduction of the [Logistic] component of the SLR, the terms "freight", "transport" and "logistic service" were removed due to too many search results.
Science direct	(agile OR scrum OR kanban OR "Lean startup") AND (freight OR transport OR "logistic service provider" OR "fourth party logistic" OR "Third party logistic" OR "Logistic service") AND (company OR firm OR start-up OR start-up)	No adjustments at the standard search string

Digital library	Search string	Comment
SpringerLink	(agile OR scrum OR kanban OR "Lean startup") AND (freight OR transport OR "logistic service provider" OR "fourth party logistic" OR "Third party logistic" OR "Logistic service") AND (company OR firm OR start-up OR start-up)	No adjustments at the standard search string
Wiley	(agile OR scrum OR kanban OR "Lean startup") AND (freight OR transport OR "logistic service provider" OR "fourth party logistic" OR "Third party logistic" OR "Logistic service") AND (company OR firm OR start-up OR start-up)	No adjustments at the standard search string

Study selection criteria

Studies are selected passed on the following search criteria. The selection criteria are applied as follows:

4. The first three inclusion criteria have to be fulfilled
5. The selection criteria 4-6 are used as guideline whether the studies should be selected
6. Studies should be excluded if any exclusion criteria can be applied

Table 30: Inclusion and exclusion criteria

#	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
1	Papers written in English	No full books, no master thesis
2	Papers published between 1999-2019	Papers with results that had been already published
3	Specific book chapter (published between 1999-2019)	Papers that were not focused on agile methodologies or whose focus moved away from agile methodologies
4	Papers presenting agile methods used in the logistics industry	
5	Papers presenting benefits logistics companies aim to realise through the use of agile methods	
6	Papers associated with challenges of the application of agile methods in the logistics industry	

Quality assessment

The quality of the selected relevant studies is evaluated based on the criteria shown in Table 31 (Schön, Thomaschewski and Escalona, 2017). A three point Likert scale is used.

Table 31: Quality assessment criteria

Item	Assessment criteria	Score	Description
QA1	Is the scientific idea validated?	-1	No, it is not validated
		0	Partially, it is validated in a laboratory or only parts of the proposal are validated
		+1	Yes, by a case study/survey/etc.
QA2	Does the publication present a detailed description of the approach?	-1	No, details are missing
		0	Partially, if you want to use the approach, you need to read the references
		+1	Yes, the approach can be used with presented details
QA3	Does the publication include a personal opinion piece or viewpoint?	-1	Yes, it does.
		0	Partially, since related work is explained and paper is set into a specific context
		+1	No, the paper is based on research
QA4	Has the publication been cited by other authors?	-1	No, no one cited the study
		0	Partially, between 1-5 articles cited the study
		+1	Yes, more than 5 articles cited the study
QA5	Has the publication a clear statement of the objective of the study?	-1	No, aims are not described
		0	Partially, aims are described but unclearly
		+1	Yes, aims are well described and clear

Data collection

For the data analysis an excel sheet containing the following information is used.

Table 32: Overview over the data collection parameters

Attribute cluster	Attributes
General information	Title, Authors, Publication date, DOI
Publication data	Journal/ conference, (conference date) publisher, volume, issue, pages, keywords, abstract

Attribute cluster	Attributes
Research type	Research method (Development of a framework, case study, survey, systematic literature review, other)
Agile method	e.g. Scrum, XP, Kanban, Agile Manufacturing
Type of company	Start-up, established
Company size	e.g. 250 employees
Type of logistic	Supply chain, internal logistic, freight, inventory management, logistic service provider, urban logistic
Company assets	Asset-based, asset-light
Problems of companies	e.g. 'Change, uncertainty and unpredictability within business environment and necessity of appropriate responses to changes'
Aims of optimisation	e.g. 'Cope with the high levels of uncertainty', 'Increase efficiency and effectiveness through communication'
Challenges with agile methods	e.g. 'Longer gestation periods with higher technical risk', 'Difficulty to gather customer feedback'
Quality assessment criteria	Idea validation, detailed approach, personal opinion, cited by others, clear objective
Personal assessment	Comments, selection status (included/excluded)

Data analysis

In the following, I describe how the research questions will be answered (see Research questions).

Research Question 1: What agile methods and practices do logistic start-ups and traditional logistic companies use?

An overview with the agile methods and practices used by traditional logistic companies and logistic start-ups will be presented. Additionally, it will be compared if the authors/ companies/ start-ups have the same understanding of agile methods and practices described in the studies and if a connection between the size of the company and the chosen agile methods is recognisable. In addition, a list of all relevant agile methods and practices will be provided.

Research Question 2: What problems do logistic start-ups and traditional logistic companies solve with agile methods?

A table with the problems that logistic start-ups and traditional companies face will be presented. The table will include the type and size of the company, a description of the problem they want to solve and the agile method/ practice they chose will be presented. Additionally, an overview over common problems that agile methods and practices are used for will be presented.

Research Question 3: What challenges do logistic start-ups and traditional logistic companies face?

A table with challenges that companies face using agile methods/ practices will be provided. The table will include the type and size of the company, a description of the challenge they faced and the agile method/ practice they chose.

A.3. Details of the identified publications of the systematic literature review

In the following, details of the publications that were identified as relevant during the SLR are shown in four parts. Papers are presented in the order they were found during the SLR.

Details Part 1

Table 33: Details on the title, type of publication and publisher of the identified publications

Author, Year	Title	Type of publication	Publisher
Morlok and Chang, 2004	Measuring capacity flexibility of a transportation system	Journal article	Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice
Tuan and Thang, 2013	Combining maturity with agility: lessons learnt from a case study	Conference Paper	SoICT '13 Proceedings of the Fourth Symposium on Information and Communication Technology
Marlow and Paixão Casaca, 2003	Measuring lean ports performance	Journal article	International Journal of Transport Management
Dybå and Dingsøy, 2015	Agile project management: from self-managing teams to large-scale development	Conference Paper	ICSE '15 Proceedings of the 37th International Conference on Software Engineering
Pijpers et al., 2012	Using conceptual models to explore business-ICT alignment in networked value constellations	Journal article	Requirements Engineering
van Oosterhout, Waarts and van Hillegersberg, 2005	Assessing Business Agility: A Multi-Industry Study in The Netherlands in Business Agility and Information Technology Diffusion	Conference Paper	International Working Conference
Wang, 2011	A Taxonomical Study of Agility Strategies and Supporting Supply Chain Management Practices	PhD Thesis	University of Exeter
Yusuf, Sarhadi and Gunasekaran, 1999	Agile manufacturing: the drivers, concepts and attributes	Journal article	International Journal of Production Economics
Gurahoo and Salisbury, 2018	Lean and agile in small- and medium-sized enterprises: Complementary or incompatible?	Journal article	South African Journal of Business Management
Bernal et al., 2019	Developing Logistic Software Platforms: E-Market Place, a Case Study	Conference Paper	International Conference on Computational Logistics
Cichosz, Wallenburg and Knemeyer, 2020	Digital transformation at logistics service providers: barriers, success factors and leading practices	Journal article	The International Journal of Logistics Management

Author, Year	Title	Type of publication	Publisher
Genzorova, Corejova and Stalmasekova, 2019	How digital transformation can influence business model, Case study for transport industry	Journal article	Transportation Research Procedia
Dunz, Werth and Breitner, 2020	Critical Success Factors for the Development and Adoption of Mobile Applications in Logistics	Conference Paper	IWI Discussion Series
Longo and Iazzolino, 2016	Agile Software Development: A Modeling and Simulation Showcase in Military Logistics	Conference Paper	International Conference in Software Engineering for Defence Applications
Rola and Kuchta, 2020	Implementation of Scrum Retrospective in the Process of Improving Logistics Organization	Conference Paper	International Conference on Information Systems Architecture and Technology

Details Part 2

Table 34: Details on the research methods of the identified relevant papers and agile methods and practices considered in the publications

Author, Year	Research method	Agile methods considered in the publication
Morlok and Chang, 2004	Development of a framework	None specified
Tuan and Thang, 2013	Case study	Scrum, XP
Marlow and Paixão Casaca, 2003	Development of a framework	Agile supply chain, empowerment of actors, flat less rigid hierarchies, Focus on knowledge of the people not technologies, development of networks and partnerships, Customer centred, Continuous improvement
Dybå and Dingsøyr, 2015	Development of a framework	Scrum
Pijpers et al., 2012	Multiple case study	Alignment of ICT and organisation
van Oosterhout, Waarts and van Hillegersberg, 2005	Survey	Business agility
Wang, 2011	Survey	Agile manufacturing
Yusuf, Sarhadi and Gunasekaran, 1999	Development of a framework	Agile supply chain
Gurahoo and Salisbury, 2018	Semi structured interviews	Agile supply chain
Bernal et al., 2019	Framework	Scrum, XP, and Crystal
Cichosz, Wallenburg and Knemeyer, 2020	Multiple case study	Small cross-functional teams, MVP, flexible processes, people's openness to collaboration and change

Author, Year	Research method	Agile methods considered in the publication
Genzorova, Corejova and Stalmasekova, 2019	Case study	Design Thinking, Scrum
Dunz, Werth and Breitner, 2020	Case study	Scrum, sprints, daily standups, retrospective
Longo and Iazzolino, 2016	Case study	XP, pair programming, unit testing, and refactoring
Rola and Kuchta, 2020	Case study	Retrospectives

Details Part 3

Table 35: Details on the companies that were in the focus of the identified relevant papers

Author, Year	Type of logistics	Type of company	Asset-light or asset-based?	Reasons to implement agile methods
Morlok and Chang, 2004	Freight	No specific company	Asset-based	Demand or traffic changes
Tuan and Thang, 2013	Software for supply chain management and realisation of SaaS	Established	Asset-light	Apply agile and maturity methods and practices
Marlow and Paixão Casaca, 2003	Port	No specific company	Asset-based	Measure and increase port performance and quality of service
Dybå and Dingsøyr, 2015	n/a	Established	n/a	Educe upfront planning and strict control to enhance customer focus
Pijpers et al., 2012	Software, advertisement, aviation	Established/ Start-up	Asset-based	Reducing inter-organisational business-ICT alignment issues
van Oosterhout, Waarts and van Hillegersberg, 2005	Logistic service provider	Established	Asset-based	Reduce product price, adapt changes faster, reduce organisational challenges
Wang, 2011	Manufacturing, internal logistic	Established	Asset-based	Adapt to structural changes in manufacturing industry
Yusuf, Sarhadi and Gunasekaran, 1999	Supply chain	Established	Asset based	Satisfy customer orders, introduce new products frequently, get in and out of its strategic alliances speedily
Gurahoo and Salisbury, 2018	Supply chain	Established	Asset-based	Achieve just-in-time purchasing, reduce stock-outs and lead times
Bernal et al., 2019	Logistic software platforms	Established	Asset-light	Integration of emerging technologies

Author, Year	Type of logistics	Type of company	Asset-light or asset-based?	Reasons to implement agile methods
Cichosz, Wallenburg and Knemeyer, 2020	Transport companies and couriers	Established	Asset-based	High fragmentation, low transparency, underutilised assets, costly manual processes and in many instances outdated customer interfaces
Genzorova, Corejova and Stalmasekova, 2019	Logistic software platforms	Established	Asset-light	Need to change business model according to digitalisation
Dunz, Werth and Breitner, 2020	Logistic service provider	Established	Asset-based	Problems with digital transformation
Longo and Iazzolino, 2016	Military	Established	Asset-based	Complex and non-deterministic software development
Rola and Kuchta, 2020	Transport sector	Established	Asset-based	Improve internal processes

Details Part 4

Table 36: Details on benefits and challenges using agile methods presented in the identified relevant papers

Author, Year	Benefits of agile methods	Challenges with the agile methods
Morlok and Chang, 2004	Provide greater latitude for demand changes, as from shifts in the location of production or consumption patterns	n/a
Tuan and Thang, 2013	n/a	n/a
Marlow and Paixão Casaca, 2003	Controlling trade routes in ports and being proactive rather than reactive	n/a
Dybå and Dingsøy, 2015	n/a	n/a
Pijpers et al., 2012	n/a	n/a
van Oosterhout, Waarts and van Hillegersberg, 2005	n/a	ICT and the maintenance cost, mindset, culture
Wang, 2011	Increase the success of a firm through the right design of the supply chain	n/a
Yusuf, Sarhadi and Gunasekaran, 1999	Find drivers that increase competitiveness through manufacturing/supply chain agility	n/a
Gurahoo and Salisbury, 2018	n/a	n/a
Bernal et al., 2019	Quick response for new requirements, achieve the required quality for the process and the user interface, improve the software engineering process	n/a

Author, Year	Benefits of agile methods	Challenges with the agile methods
Cichosz, Wallenburg and Knemeyer, 2020	Alignment between business and IT, embraces quick deployment, responsiveness to change, emphasis on customer needs, high-quality service within the agreed timetable collaboration with start-ups	Legal and regulatory requirements prevent the implementation of agile approaches
Genzorova, Corejova and Stalmasekova, 2019	Create customer value while encouraging and responding to change in its environment	n/a
Dunz, Werth and Breitner, 2020	Faster overall development, keep up the performance of the employees, short-term decisions and flexible adaptation, opportunity for the team members to contribute ideas to the project team, the contact with other team members through daily meetings, working more purposefully through an agile way of thinking	Missing concrete requirements or the late knowledge of it, overall view of the project is missing, many management levels between the project team and the users, time pressure
Longo and Iazzolino, 2016	Customer involvement, multidisciplinary and cohesive team, knowledge exchange, effective communications, software reliability, shorter testing, and debugging times, capability of making changes	n/a
Rola and Kuchta, 2020	Support collaborative problem solving	Introduction of agile methods, transformation phase

A.4. Quality assessment of the identified publications

In the following the performance of the relevant publications of the SLR during the quality assessment are shown. Papers are presented in the order they were found during the SLR. QA4 explores whether the study is cited by other authors. To assess this, Google Scholar is used to determine the number of times the study is cited (assessment date 19.01.2021).

Table 37: Quality assessment of identified relevant papers

Title	Authors, Year	QA1	QA2	QA3	QA4	QA5
Measuring capacity flexibility of a transportation system	Morlok and Chang, 2004	No	Partly	Partly	More than 5	Partly
Combining maturity with agility: lessons learnt from a case study	Tuan and Thang, 2013	Yes	Partly	Partly	More than 5	Yes
Measuring lean ports performance	Marlow and Paixão Casaca, 2003	No	Partly	No	More than 5	Yes
Agile project management: from self-managing teams to large-scale development	Dybå and Dingsøy, 2015	No	Partly	Partly	More than 5	Yes
Using conceptual models to explore business-ICT alignment in networked value constellations	Pijpers et al., 2012	Yes	Yes	No	More than 5	Yes
Assessing Business Agility: A Multi-Industry Study in The Netherlands in Business Agility and Information Technology Diffusion	van Oosterhout, Waarts and van Hillegersberg, 2005	Partly	Yes	No	More than 5	Yes
A Taxonomical Study of Agility Strategies and Supporting Supply Chain Management Practices	Wang, 2011	Yes	Yes	No	1-5	Yes
Agile manufacturing: the drivers, concepts and attributes	Yusuf, Sarhadi and Gunasekaran, 1999	No	Partly	Partly	More than 5	Yes
Lean and agile in small- and medium-sized	Gurahoo and Salisbury, 2018	Yes	Partly	No	1-5	Yes

Title	Authors, Year	QA1	QA2	QA3	QA4	QA5
enterprises: Complementary or incompatible?						
Developing Logistic Software Platforms: E- Market Place, a Case Study	Bernal et al., 2019	Yes	Yes	No	No	Partly
Digital transformation at logistics service providers: barriers, success factors and leading practices	Cichosz, Wallenburg and Knemeyer, 2020	Yes	Yes	No	1-5	Yes
How digital transformation can influence business model, Case study for transport industry	Genzorova, Corejova and Stalmasekova, 2019	Yes	Partly	No	More than 5	Yes
Critical Success Factors for the Development and Adoption of Mobile Applications in Logistics	Dunz, Werth and Breitner, 2020	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes
Agile Software Development: A Modeling and Simulation Showcase in Military Logistics	Longo and Iazzolino, 2016	Yes	Partly	No	1-5	Yes
Implementation of Scrum Retrospective in the Process of Improving Logistics Organization	Rola and Kuchta, 2020	Yes	Partly	No	1-5	Yes

A.5. Questionnaires Delphi study

In the following the questionnaires that were used for the three rounds of the Delphi study are presented. The original answers of the participants are available and can be handed out on request.

A.5.1. Questionnaire Delphi study – Round 1

The following parts of this section were part of the questionnaire of the first round of the Delphi study and sent to the experts.

Agility in traditional logistics companies and logistics start-ups

As part of my PhD, I am conducting a Delphi study on the use and benefits of agile methods in traditional logistics companies as well as in logistics start-ups. I am particularly interested in why these agile methods and practices are used and what challenges occur when applying these agile methods and practices.

I would be very pleased about your participation in the survey. Your participation is important for me and supports me in my research.

The survey will consist of several rounds and after each round you will receive the results together with the invitation for the next round. It is therefore easiest if you enter your e-mail address at the end of the survey.

Mandatory questions are marked with an (*).

Consent for participation in research interview:

- I voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.
- I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind.
- I understand that I can withdraw permission to use data from my completed questionnaire within two weeks after completion, in which case the material will be deleted.
- I have had the purpose and nature of the study explained to me in writing and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study.
- I understand that participation involves describing what agile methods and practices I use, which purpose I pursue using agile methods and practices and what challenges I face using them. I am aware that this Delphi studies consists of several rounds.
- I understand that I will not benefit monetarily from participating in this research.
- I understand that all information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.
- I understand that in any report on the results of this research my identity will remain anonymous. This will be done by changing my name, the name of my employer and disguising any details of my completed questionnaire which may reveal my identity or the identity of people I speak about.
- I understand that anonymised extracts from my answers may be quoted in the dissertation, conference presentations and published papers.
- I understand that the completed consent form and my filled-out questionnaires will be retained in secure servers or password-protected computers for ten years.

- I understand that under freedom of information legalisation I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above.
- I understand that I am free to contact any of the people involved in the research to seek further clarification and information.

1. Do you agree to participate in the Delphi study? *

- Yes, I agree to participate in the study
- No, I do not agree with the participation and do not want to participate in the study (*The questionnaire can now be closed. No information will be transmitted.*)

2. How many employees does the logistics company for which you work or where you are a consultant on a project assignment has in total? *

- ≤ 10 employees
- < 10 employees but ≤ 30 employees
- < 30 employees but ≤ 50 employees
- < 50 employees but ≤ 100 employees
- < 100 employees but ≤ 250 employees
- < 250 employees but ≤ 500 employees
- < 500 employees

3. How many years ago was the logistics company originally founded? *

- ≤ 1 year ago
- > 1 year but ≤ 3 years
- > 3 years but ≤ 5 years
- > 5 years but ≤ 10 years
- > 10 years

4. How many years have you been working for your logistics company? *

- ≤ 1 year
- > 1 years but ≤ 3 years
- > 3 years but ≤ 5 years
- > 5 years but ≤ 10 years
- > 10 years

5. How many years of work experience do you have in the logistics industry overall? *

- ≤ 1 year
- > 1 years but ≤ 3 years
- > 3 years but ≤ 5 years
- > 5 years but ≤ 10 years
- > 10 years

6. What is your current role in your logistics company? *

- Agile Coach / Scrum Master
- Developer

- Functional or technical architect
- Head of department
- Top management (CEO/CFO/CTO,...)
- Product Owner
- Project Manager
- Others

7. How long have you been working in your current role? *

- ≤ 1 year
- > 1 years but ≤ 3 years
- > 3 years but ≤ 5 years
- > 5 years but ≤ 10 years
- > 10 years

8. How do you work together in your team? *

Here and in the following, the term "team" is refers to the group of employees with whom you mainly work on a day-to-day basis.

- Classical approach (Waterfall model)
- Agile
- Hybrid form
- Others

9. How many colleagues work with you in the logistics company in the same team? (Including you) *

Here and in the following, the term "team" is refers to the group of employees with whom you mainly work on a day-to-day basis.

- Just me alone
- One more person and me
- > 2 people but ≤ 5 people
- > 5 people but ≤ 9 people
- > 9 people but ≤ 15 people
- > 15 people

10. How many years of experience do you have with agile methods like Scrum, Kanban, SAFe, LeSS, Extreme Programming, etc.? *

- No experience
- ≤ 1 year
- > 1 years but ≤ 3 years
- > 3 years but ≤ 5 years
- > 5 years but ≤ 10 years
- > 10 years

11. Which process models have you personally used so far (also in previous jobs)? *

You can find information on the process models in the links next to the response options.

Table 38: Answer options: process models used

	Frequently	From time to time	Rarely	Once	Never
Waterfall model http://tiny.cc/WaterfallModel					
V-model http://tiny.cc/VModel					
Lean Management http://tiny.cc/LeanMgmt					
Prince2 http://tiny.cc/Prince2Method					
Scrum http://tiny.cc/ScrumMethod					
Kanban http://tiny.cc/Kanban					
Large Scale Scum (LeSS) http://tiny.cc/Less					
Scaled Agile Framework (SAFe) http://tiny.cc/SafeMethod					
Extreme Programming (XP) http://tiny.cc/ExtremeProgramming					
Feature Driven Development (FDD) http://tiny.cc/FeatureDD					
Crystal http://tiny.cc/CrystalMethod					
Others					

12. Comments or additions to the previous question

You can use the comment field for example if you have selected "Others" above.

13. On a scale of 1-7, how extensive do you rate your expertise in agile methods and practices? *

1 = No know-how, 7 = I have very extensive know-how

14. In which form do you use agile methods in your team in the logistics company? *

1 = "In pure form", 5 = Maximum adaptation to the prevailing conditions, Intent of usage = Not yet used, but planned for the future, n/a = No statement possible or method not applied

Table 39: Answer options: level of adoption of agile methods

	"Pure form"	Minimally adopted	Slightly adopted	More strongly adopted	Maximally adapted	Intent of usage	n/a
Scrum http://tiny.cc/ScrumMethod							
Kanban http://tiny.cc/Kanban							
Large Scale Scum (LeSS) http://tiny.cc/Less							
Scaled Agile Framework (SAFe) http://tiny.cc/SafeMethod							
Lean startup http://tiny.cc/LeanStart							

	“Pure form”	Minimally adopted	Slightly adopted	More strongly adopted	Maximally adapted	Intent of usage	n/a
Extreme Programming (XP) http://tiny.cc/ExtremeProgramming							
Feature Driven Development (FDD) http://tiny.cc/FeatureDD							
Crystal http://tiny.cc/CrystalMethod							
Others							

15. Comments or additions to the previous question

*You can use the comment field for example if you have selected "Other methods" above.

16. How regularly do you use the following agile practices in your team in the logistics company?
(Part 1/3)

Note: Some answer options are only visible when scrolling to the right. 1 = Daily, 2 = Several times a month, 3 = Once a month, 4 = Several times a year, 5 = Never, Intent of usage = Not yet used, but planned for the future, n/a = No statement possible or practice not applied

Table 40: Answer options: frequency of use of agile methods (Part 1)

	Daily	Several times a month	Once a month	Several times a year	Never	Intent of usage	n/a
Agile Release Train http://tiny.cc/AgileReleaseTrain							
Update of the task board http://tiny.cc/TaskBoard							
Work in feature teams http://tiny.cc/FeatureTeams							
Delivery of the software http://tiny.cc/FrequentDelivery							
Builds of the software http://tiny.cc/Build							
Build-Measure-Learn cycles http://tiny.cc/BML							
Close exchange within the team http://tiny.cc/TeamCommunication							
Creation of a Minimum Viable Product http://tiny.cc/MinimumVP							

17. Comments or additions to the previous question

18. How regularly do you use the following agile practices in your team in the logistics company? (Part 2/3)

Note: Some answer options are only visible when scrolling to the right. 1 = Daily, 2 = Several times a month, 3 = Once a month, 4 = Several times a year, 5 = Never, Intent of usage = Not yet used, but planned for the future, n/a = No statement possible or practice not applied

Table 41: Answer options: frequency of use of agile methods (Part 2)

	Daily	Several times a month	Once a month	Several times a year	Never	Intent of usage	n/a
Feedback cycles with the customer http://tiny.cc/CustFeedback							
Inspect & Adapt Event http://tiny.cc/IaA							
Pair Programming http://tiny.cc/PIplanning							
Program Increment Planning http://tiny.cc/PIplanning							
Refactoring http://tiny.cc/Refactoring							
Refinement http://tiny.cc/Refinement							
Retrospectives http://tiny.cc/SprintRetro							
Review http://tiny.cc/SprintReview							

19. Comments or additions to the previous question

20. How regularly do you use the following agile practices in your team in the logistics company? (Part 3/3)

Note: Some answer options are only visible when scrolling to the right. 1 = Daily, 2 = Several times a month, 3 = Once a month, 4 = Several times a year, 5 = Never, Intent of usage = Not yet used, but planned for the future, n/a = No statement possible or practice not applied

Table 42: Answer options: frequency of use of agile methods (Part 3)

	Daily	Several times a month	Once a month	Several times a year	Never	Intent of usage	n/a
Sprint Planning http://tiny.cc/SprintPlanning							
System Demo							

http://tiny.cc/SystemDemo							
Daily Standup http://tiny.cc/Daily							
Test-driven Development http://tiny.cc/TestDD							
Monitoring of limit for Work in Progress http://tiny.cc/WIPLimit							
Merging the code back into the master/ baseline http://tiny.cc/Merge							
Other practices							

21. Comments or additions to the previous question

You can use the comment field for example if you have selected "Other practices" above.

22. If you work in a team: Who uses the agile methods and practices? *

Here and in the following, the term "team" is refers to the group of employees with whom you mainly work on a day-to-day basis.

- The whole team
- Parts of the team
- Just me
- Others

23. Who initiated the use of agile methods and practices in the logistics company? Multiple selection possible *

If you are not currently using agile methods and practices: Who could initiate the introduction of agile methods?

- Top Management
- Head of department
- Team lead
- External consultant
- Agile Coach
- Team colleagues
- Own initiative
- Others

24. Who decided what agile methods and practices to use? Multiple selection possible *

If you are not currently using agile methods and practices: Who would decide on that?

- Top Management
- Head of department
- Team lead
- External consultant

- Agile coach
- Together as a team
- Just me
- Others

25. For what reasons do you use agile methods and practices in your work environment or project deployment? * Please select up to four central reasons.

If you are not currently using agile methods and practices: Why would you like to use them?

- Reduction of time to market
- Responsiveness to changing priorities/ demands
- Increase in productivity
- Increased alignment between the business and IT departments
- Increase in product quality
- More accurate predictability of the delivery date of the product
- Increased project transparency
- Cost reduction
- Strengthening the team spirit
- Risk reduction
- Increase of product maintainability
- Improving the external image of the company
- Meeting quality standards
- Increase in employee satisfaction

26. Comments or additions to the previous question

27. What challenges arise when using agile methods and practices? Please select up to four central challenges. *

If you are not currently using agile methods and practices: What challenges might arise?

- Organisational culture contradicts agile values
- General resistance to change among employees
- Lack of management support
- Recruitment of adequate employees
- Lack of skills or knowledge in relation to agile methods
- Inconsistent processes and procedures between the (agile) teams
- Lack of availability of the product owner
- Dominance of classical development methods
- Use of a fragmented tooling
- Little cooperation in the agile teams
- Need to comply with legal requirements
- Imbalanced distribution of knowledge in the agile teams
- Outdated skills in the agile teams
- Difficulties in going small iterative steps
- Environment with heavy-weight documentation
- Distributed teams over several locations

- Too little communication in the agile teams
- Lack of customer commitment for e.g. functional feedback
- Unsuitable working environment
- Lack of technical know-how in the agile team
- Low knowledge transfer in the agile teams

28. Comments or additions to the previous question

Many thanks for your participation! We would be very pleased if you enter your e-mail address.

Then I can send you the results of the previous round and the questionnaire for the next round.

A.5.2. Questionnaire Delphi study – Round 2

The following parts of this section were part of the questionnaire of the second round of the Delphi study and sent to the experts.

Agility in traditional logistics companies and logistics start-ups

Thank you for participating in the first round of the Delphi study. In this second round, the results of the first round will be deepened.

I would be very pleased about your participation in the survey. Your participation is important for me and supports me in my research.

The survey will consist of several rounds and after each round you will receive the results together with the invitation for the next round. It is best if you give your e-mail address at the end of the survey.

Mandatory questions are marked with an (*).

1. According to which criteria were the agile methods selected as (future) methods in your team?
 Select up to two criteria.

Table 43: Answer options: selection criteria agile methods (Part 1)

	Own previous experience	Implementation costs	Recommendation of external consultants	Recommendation of colleagues	Image of the methods	Existing knowledge among the employees	Applicability for my requirements	Applicability for my number of employees	Recommendation of an agile coach	Company guidelines	Method unknown	Use not planned
Scrum http://tiny.cc/ScrumMethod												
Kanban http://tiny.cc/Kanban												
Scaled Agile Framework (SAFe) http://tiny.cc/SafeMethod												
Lean startup http://tiny.cc/LeanStart												
Extreme Programming (XP) http://tiny.cc/ExtremeProgramming												
Feature Driven Development (FDD) http://tiny.cc/FeatureDD												

2. Comments or additions to the previous question

3. According to which criteria were the agile methods selected as (future) methods in your team?
 Select up to two criteria.

Table 44: Answer options: selection criteria agile methods (Part 2)

	Own previous experience	Implementation costs	Recommendation of external consultants	Recommendation of colleagues	Image of the methods	Existing knowledge among the employees	Applicability for my requirements	Applicability for my number of employees	Recommendation of an agile coach	Company guidelines	Method unknown	Use not planned
Large Scale Scrum (LeSS) (http://tiny.cc/LeS)												
Lean startup (http://tiny.cc/LeanStart)												
Crystal (http://tiny.cc/CrystalMethod)												
Scrumban (http://tiny.cc/Scrumban)												

4. Comments or additions to the previous question

5. What is the most important practice that you use to respond to changing priorities/requirements from the customer? *

- Agile Release Train
- Build-Measure-Learn cycles
- Close exchange within the team
- Creation of a Minimum Viable Product
- Daily Standup
- Feedback cycles with the customer
- Inspect & Adapt Event
- Programme Increment Planning
- Refactoring
- Regular delivery of the software
- Review
- Sprint Planning
- System Demo
- Work in feature teams
- Other practice*

6. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Other practice" above.

7. To what extent does the practice you mentioned above increase responsiveness to changes in customer priorities? (1 = Not at all, 7 = Very much) *

8. What is the most important practice you use to respond to changing team priorities/requirements? *

- Agile Release Train
- Build-Measure-Learn cycles
- Close exchange within the team
- Creation of a Minimum Viable Product
- Daily Standup
- Feedback cycles with the customer
- Inspect & Adapt Event
- Programme Increment Planning
- Refactoring
- Regular delivery of the software
- Review
- Sprint Planning
- System Demo
- Work in feature teams
- Other practice*

9. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Other practice" above.

10. To what extent does the practice you mentioned above increase responsiveness to internal changes? (1 = Not at all, 7 = Very much) *

11. What is the most important practice you use to speed up product delivery? * Here and in the following the term "product" is understood to mean the sum of software increments.

- Agile Release Train
- Close exchange within the team
- Creation of a Minimum Viable Product
- Daily Standup
- Feedback cycles with the customer
- Inspect & Adapt Event
- Merging the code back into the master/baseline
- Monitoring the limit on work in progress
- Program Increment Planning
- Regular builds of the software
- Regular delivery of the software
- Review
- Sprint Planning
- Test-driven development
- Other practice*

12. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Other practice" above.

13. To what extent does the practice you mentioned above speed up product delivery? (1 = Not at all, 7 = Very strongly) *

14. What is the most important practice you use to improve communication between customers and your own IT? *

- Build-Measure-Learn cycles
- Close exchange within the team
- Creation of a Minimum Viable Product
- Feedback cycles with the customer
- Inspect & Adapt Event
- Program Increment Planning
- Retrospectives
- Review
- Sprint Planning
- System Demo
- Updating the Task-Board/ Kanban-Board
- Work in feature teams
- Regular builds of the software
- Regular delivery of the software
- Other practice*

15. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Other practice" above.

16. To what extent does the practice you mentioned above improve the communication between IT and customers? (1 = Not at all, 7 = Very strong)*

17. What is the most important practice you use to increase transparency about status and obstacles in the agile team? *

- Agile Release Train
- Build-Measure-Learn cycles
- Close exchange within the team
- Creation of a Minimum Viable Product
- Daily Standup
- Feedback cycles with the customer
- Inspect & Adapt Event
- Program Increment Planning
- Regular builds of the software
- Regular delivery of the software
- Review
- Sprint Planning
- System Demo
- Updating the Task-Board/ Kanban-Board
- Work in feature teams
- Other practice*

18. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Other practice" above.

19. To what extent does the practice you mentioned increase transparency in the team? (1 = Not at all, 7 = Very much) *

20. What is the most important practice you use to improve product quality? *

Here and in the following the term "product" is understood to mean the sum of software increments. Quality is measured by the freedom from errors of the code, fulfilment of (customer) requirements, maintainability and reusability of the code.

- Work in feature teams
- Build-Measure-Learn cycles
- Close exchange within the team
- Creation of a Minimum Viable Product
- Daily Standup
- Feedback cycles with the customer
- Inspect & Adapt Event
- Merging the code back into the master/baseline
- Pair Programming
- Program Increment Planning
- Refactoring
- Regular builds of the software
- Regular delivery of the software
- Retrospectives
- Review
- Sprint Planning
- System Demo
- Test-driven development
- Other practice*

21. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Other practice" above.

22. To what extent does the practice you mention increase product quality? (1 = Not at all, 7 = Very much) *

23. What is the most important practice you use to reduce risks of the project? *

- Agile Release Train
- Build-Measure-Learn cycles
- Close exchange within the team
- Creation of a Minimum Viable Product
- Daily Standup
- Feedback cycles with the customer
- Inspect & Adapt Event
- Program Increment Planning
- Regular builds of the software
- Regular delivery of the software
- Review
- Sprint Planning
- System Demo
- Test-driven development
- Work in feature teams
- Other practice*

24. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Other practice" above.

25. To what extent does the practice you mention reduce the risks? (1 = Not at all, 7 = Very strongly) *

26. What is the most important practice you use to increase the productivity of the agile team? *

Here productivity is measured in terms of the added value created for the product and the customer.

- Build-Measure-Learn cycles
- Close exchange within the team
- Creation of a Minimum Viable Product
- Daily Standup
- Feedback cycles with the customer
- Merging the code back into the master/baseline
- Monitoring the limit on work in progress
- Refactoring
- Refinement
- Regular delivery of the software
- Retrospectives
- Review
- Sprint Planning
- Test-driven development
- Updating the Task-Board/ Kanban-Board
- Work in feature teams
- Other practice*

27. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Other practice" above.

28. To what extent does the practice you mention increase productivity? (1 = Not at all, 7 = Very much) *

29. Has an agile transformation taken place in your company? *

- - Yes, my team has switched from a classic approach to the agile approach. *Move on to question 31*
- - No, we have used agile methods from the beginning. *Move on to question 36*
- - Yes, the entire IT department was transformed from a classic approach to the agile approach. *Move on to question 36*
- Others*

30. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Others" above.

31. Who has promoted agile transformation and the introduction of agile methods? *

Select all applicable answers.

- Dedicated, internal transformation team working only on the transformation
- Various internal people working on different projects and helped shape the transformation
- Supported by external consultants
- Others

32. Comments or additions to the previous question

33. How was the agile transformation planned? *

- Iterative: Only the first step was planned, the following steps were defined later
- Fixed roadmap: there was a multi-stage transformation plan from the outset
- Others

34. Comments or additions to the previous question

35. How was the introduction of agile methods carried out? *

Select all applicable answers.

- Start with a small pilot project
- Start with strategically important project
- Changeover from day X of the entire organisation
- Automation of the technical infrastructure
- Others

36. Which procedures are important when introducing agile methods? Please select up to three central procedures. *

Select all applicable answers.

- Early coaching of the Scrum Team
- Early focus on automation of (software development) processes
- Early involvement of employees
- Focus on the agile principles instead of the processes
- Following a defined transformation plan
- Only minimal adaptation of the agile methods to your own circumstances
- Putting together a dedicated transformation team
- Promotion of a new organisational culture
- Support of the transformation by the upper management
- Support for the transformation from external consultants
- Support from an agile coach
- Other

37. On a scale of 1 to 7, how strongly do the following factors influence the successful use of agile methods *

Table 45: Answer options: factors that influence the successful use of agile methods

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Organisational Culture							
Resistance among employees to change							
Imbalanced distribution of knowledge in the agile teams							
Lack of knowledge in relation to agile methods							
Availability of the product owner							

Many thanks for your participation! We would be very pleased if you enter your e-mail address.

Then I can send you the results of the previous round and the questionnaire for the next round.

A.5.3. Questionnaire Delphi study – Round 3

The following parts of this section were part of the questionnaire of the third round of the Delphi study and sent to the experts.

Thank you for participating in the second round of the Delphi study. In this third round the results so far shall be consolidated and discrepancies shall be questioned.

I would be very pleased if you would participate in the survey. Your participation is important for me and supports me in my research.

To enable me to send you the results, please provide your e-mail address at the end of the survey.

Mandatory questions are marked with an (*).

After having asked for the selection criteria for agile methods in the second round, the most frequent criteria will be evaluated once again with regard to their importance.

1. On a scale of 1- 7, how important are the following criteria in selecting agile methods? *

Table 46: Answer options: importance of selection criteria

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Own previous experience							
Applicability for my requirements							
Applicability for my number of employees							
Recommendation of external consultants							
Existing knowledge among the employees							
Company guidelines (Informal)							
Recommendation of colleagues							

2. Comments or additions to the previous question

The second round asked what practices are used to achieve benefits such as accelerated product delivery and transparency through the use of agile practices. For the following benefits (accelerated product delivery, etc.), the effectiveness of the practices used was sometimes rated as low. In the following we will discuss why this is the case.

3. Are you making the best possible use of practices to speed up product delivery?*

Here and in the following the term "product" is understood as the sum of software increments.

- Yes
- No
- Others

4. If "no" or "other", why are you not (yet) using the practices in the best possible way?

5. Do you plan to change the practice(s) you use to speed up product delivery in the future? *

„Theory" here and in the following means books and other publications on the recommended use of agile methods and practices.

Select all applicable answers.

- I plan to use (another) practice(s).
- I plan to use (another) practice(s) in addition.
- I use the practice(s) recommended from the theory and it fits our requirements.
- I am using the recommended practice(s) from the theory and it does not fit our requirements.
- I am using the right practice(s), but should stick more to theory.
- I am using the right practice(s), but should stick less to theory.
- Others*:

6. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Others" above.

7. Are you making the best possible use of practices to improve communication between customers and IT? *

- Yes
- No
- Others

8. If "no" or "other", why are you not (yet) using the practices in the best possible way?

9. Are you planning to change the practice(s) you use for communication between customers and IT in the future? *

“Theory” here and in the following means books and other publications on the recommended use of agile methods and practices.

Select all applicable answers.

- I plan to use (another) practice(s).
- I plan to use (another) practice(s) in addition.
- I use the practice(s) recommended from the theory and it fits our requirements.
- I am using the recommended practice(s) from the theory and it does not fit our requirements.
- I am using the right practice(s), but should stick more to theory.
- I am using the right practice(s), but should stick less to theory.
- Others*:

10. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Others" above

11. Do you make the best use of practices to increase transparency on status and impediments? *

- Yes
- No
- Others

12. If "no" or "other", why are you not (yet) using the practices in the best possible way?

13. In the future, do you plan to change the practice(s) you use for transparency on status and impediments? *

“Theory” here and in the following means books and other publications on the recommended use of agile methods and practices.

Select all applicable answers.

- I plan to use (another) practice(s).
- I plan to use (another) practice(s) in addition.
- I use the practice(s) recommended from the theory and it fits our requirements.
- I am using the recommended practice(s) from the theory and it does not fit our

requirements.

- I am using the right practice(s), but should stick more to theory.
- I am using the right practice(s), but should stick less to theory.
- Others*:

14. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Others" above.

15. Do you make the best possible use of practices to minimise project risk? *

- Yes
- No
- Others

16. If "no" or "other", why are you not (yet) using the practices in the best possible way?

17. In the future, do you plan to change the practice(s) you use to reduce project risk? *

“Theory” here and in the following means books and other publications on the recommended use of agile methods and practices

Select all applicable answers.

- I plan to use (another) practice(s).
- I plan to use (another) practice(s) in addition.
- I use the practice(s) recommended from the theory and it fits our requirements.
- I am using the recommended practice(s) from the theory and it does not fit our requirements.
- I am using the right practice(s), but should stick more to theory.
- I am using the right practice(s), but should stick less to theory.
- Others*:

18. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Others" above.

19. When using agile methods, how strictly should you generally follow the theory or adapt the methods to your own circumstances on a scale of 1 to 7? *

Origin of the question: The results of the first round show that agile methods are sometimes not used in their pure form. The results of the second round show that the effectiveness of the practices used is in some cases rather low. This question is intended to question the reason for this. Here and in the following, "theory" means books and other publications on the recommended use of agile methods and practices.

1=Maximally adopted, 7= Pure form of the theory

20. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Others" above.

Background to the following questions: In the first round, the following five points were identified as the greatest challenges in the use of agile methods:

- Unequal distribution of knowledge
- Organisational Culture
- Fear of change

- Lack of knowledge of agile methods
- Lack of availability of the product owner

The results of the second round show a wide dispersion in the impact of these five challenges on the successful use of agile methods.

In the following, we will therefore ask how the challenges are expressed in your case.

21. How does an uneven distribution of knowledge influence the use of agile methods? *

Select all applicable answers.

- Obstruction of team cooperation
- Bottlenecks in the distribution of tasks
- Deterioration of the team's mood
- Unequal contribution to team success by team members
- Obstruction of T-shaping (qualification in depth and breadth) of team members
- Other

22. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Others" above.

23. How does the organisational culture influence the use of agile methods? *

Select all applicable answers.

- Strict hierarchies block the agile approach
- Supervisors do not respect the independence of the teams
- Lack of personal responsibility blocks the agile teams
- Lack of error culture reduces openness and transparency
- The lack of an agile mindset means that the greatest possible added value cannot be generated
- Clients/ users do not respect the agile approach
- Other

24. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Others" above

25. How does the fear of change among employees influence the use of agile methods? *

Select all applicable answers.

- Agile teams cannot develop in the best possible way
- Agile teams cannot react flexibly enough
- Added value for the customer is not maximised
- Team members do not expand their knowledge sufficiently
- New teams make slow progress in switching to agile methods
- Others

26. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Others" above

27. How does incomplete knowledge about agile methods influence the use of agile methods?

*

Select all applicable answers.

- Incorrect use of agile methods
- Incomplete agile mindset means that the greatest possible added value cannot be generated
- Error culture is not lived and reduces transparency
- Too little communication within the agile teams
- The agile teams do not take enough responsibility
- Others

28. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Others" above

29. How does a lack of availability of the product owner (PO) influence the use of agile methods? *

Select all applicable answers.

- The PO has no time to answer the team's questions
- The agile team is blocked
- Lack of joint responsibility for the success of the product
- The agile team does not accept the prioritisation of the PO's backlog
- Others

30. Comments or additions to the previous question

* You can use the comment field, for example, if you have selected "Others" above.

Many thanks for your participation! We would be very pleased if you enter your e-mail address.

Then I can link the results of this round with your answers from the preliminary round and send you the results of the last round.

A.6. Report Delphi study

In the following, the three reports that were sent to the participants after each of the three rounds of the Delphi study are presented. Some figures and contents have already been presented in the PhD thesis but remain in the reports presented below to ensure the readability of the reports.

A.6.1. Report Delphi study – Round 1

As part of my PhD, I am conducting a Delphi study on the use and benefits of agile methods in traditional logistics companies as well as in logistics start-ups. In the following, you find the results from the first round of the Delphi study.

Who participated?

About half of the participants come from logistics start-ups and the other half from traditional logistics companies.

45% of the companies were founded within the last 10 years and are therefore classified as start-ups. In total, that were 14 out of 29 participants from logistics companies. More than 25% of all participating companies were founded within the last three years. On the other hand, about 55% of the companies were founded more than 10 years ago. The details can be found in the following diagram.

Figure 72: Age of the participating logistics companies in the Delphi study

The survey data also shows that participants from traditional logistics companies have on average been employed there for longer time and have on average more years of experience in the logistics industry than participants from logistics start-ups.

Half of the participating companies had more than 500 employees.

About 50% of the participants come from companies with more than 500 employees. In comparison, about 30% of the participants come from companies with less than 30 employees. The details can be seen in the following diagram. There is only one logistics company younger than 10 years that has more than 500 employees. Conversely, all companies older than 10 years have more than 500 employees.

Figure 73: Number of employees in the participating logistics companies in the Delphi study

The participants expressed their opinions from different perspectives.

In the first round of the Delphi study, mainly members of the top management and project leaders participated, but also many agile coaches, scrum masters and developers. Four of the five scrum master/ agile coaches are employed by traditional logistic companies. All seven participants from top management come from logistics start-ups whereas all six project managers come from traditional logistics companies.

Figure 74: Roles of the participants of the Delphi study

The participants have a broad knowledge of logistics.

Looking at the experience of the participants in the logistics industry, it is striking that 45% have more than 5 years of experience in the logistics industry. Another 45% have between one and five years of experience. Accordingly, the remaining 10% have less than one year of experience in the logistics industry. Comparing the overall experience in the logistics industry with the experience in the current role of the participants, it is noticeable that 65% of the

participants have less than three years of experience in the current role. Participants seem to cover different perspectives, as they appear to change roles and functions regularly.

N = 29

Figure 75: Years of experience in the logistics industry of the participants of the Delphi study

Almost all of the logistics companies surveyed use agile methods.

In the companies surveyed, only little work is done purely according to the Waterfall model, often the hybrid approach is followed or teams even work completely agile. Participants who work according to the "hybrid" approach work in six of twelve cases in teams with more than nine people. The other five teams have more than five people. Only one team has less than 5 people. In comparison, agile teams tend to be smaller and only have more than nine members in two out of 15 cases.

Figure 76: Overview of the method and way of teamwork

In eight of the 14 companies with less than 500 employees, the participants in the study stated that they work in an agile manner. In the companies with more than 500 employees, eight of the 15 participants in the study stated that they work in an agile manner. If we look at companies with less than 100 employees, as many as 7 out of 10 participants in the study said they worked agile.

Research question 1: What agile methods and practices are used in logistics start-ups and traditional logistics companies?

Scrum is the most used agile method in the surveyed logistics companies.

The agile method Scrum is used most by traditional logistics companies as well as by logistics start-ups. This is followed by Kanban, Lean startup, Extreme Programming (XP) and Feature

Driven Development (FDD). It is noticeable that start-ups use the older agile methods such as XP and FDD more often than traditional logistics companies. More than 80% of the participants state that they want to use additional agile methods - especially methods for scaling Scrum such as Scaled Agile Framework (SAFe) and Large Scale Scrum (LeSS). Logistics companies, especially the logistics start-ups, seem to plan their scaling of their agile teams.

These results can be compared with the results of the 13th State of Agile Report (VersionOne, 2019). The State of Agile Report is conducted by CollabNet VersionOne and collects responses from more than 1,000 participants worldwide from various industries and company sizes on the use of agile methods. Following the results of the State of Agile report, Scrum is also the most widely used methodology. However, this is followed by Scrumban and mixtures of an agile and a Waterfall approach. The methods Lean startup and XP are only mentioned there in 2% and 1% respectively as the methods used.

For scaling agile teams the State of Agile report stated that most companies use SAFe, Scrum of Scrum or LeSS among others (VersionOne, 2019).

In addition, the participants were asked how strongly they adapt the agile methods to the prevailing conditions. The results show that more experienced participants adapt the agile methods more strongly to their conditions than less experienced participants do.

Compared to that other publications state that especially when introducing agile methods, companies are more successful if they adhere strongly to the original guidelines of the agile methods (Moreira, 2013; Dingsoeyr, Falessi and Power, 2019). Most of the companies of these case studies adapt the agile methods use later after gaining more experience.

Figure 77: Overview of the agile methods used

The most common agile practice are daily standups

Overall the agile practice used the most are daily standups followed by a close exchange within the agile team and reviews and retrospectives. Looking at logistics start-ups in more detail, based on the results of the first round of the Delphi study, minimum viable products are especially important, as well as joint team planning through daily standups and sprint planning

sessions. For traditional logistics companies the use of task boards like Kanban boards, the close exchange within the team and the feedback from the customer are especially important.

Agile practices are in theory a subset of the complete agile method. The results of this Delphi study show that often single practices are used, but not the complete agile method. For example, in 100% of the cases daily standups are performed in logistics start-ups and traditional logistics companies. However, only 92% of logistics start-ups and 87% of traditional logistics companies use the associated agile method Scrum. The effect is even stronger with more technical agile practices such as refactoring and pair programming. These are used individually much more often than the complete agile method Extreme Programming.

Comparing this with the results of the 13th State of Agile Report, it is also evident that daily standups, sprint planning, retrospectives and the iterative collection of customer feedback are the most important practices (VersionOne, 2019). The logistics industry seems to behave similarly to other industries.

Figure 78: Overview of the agile practices used

Furthermore, the results show that participants who ranked their expertise with agile methods higher than other participants use agile practices more often. This could be because these participants find it easier to use agile methods because they face less uncertainty using the practices. In addition, these more experienced participants may be more aware that regular use of the practices increases the level of benefits. Other publications show that the regular use is essential to maximise the benefits gained from the use of agile methods and practices (McAvoy and Butler, 2010; Wang, Conboy and Pikkarainen, 2012).

The initiative for the use of agile methods originates from different directions

The original initiative for the use of agile methods and practices comes from a relatively even distribution from different sources. According to the participants of the Delphi study, the impulse for agile methods often comes from upper management, from team colleagues or own initiative, but in other cases from the team lead or key account management. When looking at the results, it must be kept in mind that when asking for the initiator of the introduction of agile methods, a multiple selection of answers was possible.

The participants who stated that top management took the initiative to use agile methods come from start-ups in 10 out of 14 cases. The information on the initiative of team colleagues, the team lead and the own initiative is given in about 50% of the cases of study participants from logistics start-ups and traditional logistics companies.

Figure 79: Origin of the initiative for the use of agile methods in logistics companies

Most of the time the team decides itself what agile methods to use

In 42% of all cases, the team itself decides what agile methods they want to use. In some cases, the top management, the head of department or the team leader decides. In half of the cases of logistics start-ups (seven out of 14 start-ups), the top management has a say in the selection of agile methods. In traditional companies, top management was involved in only one case. This could be due to the fact that start-ups are often smaller and the top management is closer to the agile teams in terms of hierarchy. When looking at the results, it must be considered that this question allowed a multiple selection of answers.

The fact that in most cases the team (co-)decides what agile methods are used shows that principles from the Agile Manifesto are followed (Beck et al., 2001). In the principles, these two principles underline the importance of the self-organised team:

- *“Build projects around motivated individuals. Give them the environment and support they need, and trust them to get the job done.*
- *At regular intervals, the team reflects on how to become more effective, then tunes and adjusts its behaviour accordingly.”*

Figure 80: Decision makers when choosing the agile method

Research question 2: What are the main benefits using agile methods and practices?

The main advantage of using agile methods is the ability to react to changes

The reasons why participants use agile methods are largely the same in logistics start-ups and traditional logistics companies. It is mainly about the responsiveness to changing priorities/demands, the acceleration of (product) delivery and more intensive coordination between IT and business departments.

Regardless of the size of the company, very similar benefits seem to be sought through the use of agile methods. If you compare this with the 13th State of agile Report, you will see that this does not only apply to the logistics industry. Also in other industries, the most important advantages of the use of agile methods are the ability to react to changing requirements, fast product/software delivery, increased quality and improved coordination between IT and the business (VersionOne, 2019).

Figure 81: Reasons for the use of agile methods and practices

The objectives of the use of agile methods can be grouped into five clusters. Sorted according to the frequency of the answers, the following clusters are concerned:

- Work organisation
- Possibility for customer feedback
- Technical optimisation of software development
- Scaling of the teams
- Optimisation of team cooperation

Research question 3: What are the main challenges using agile methods and practices?

The biggest challenge when using agile methods is the organisational culture

Overall, the challenges faced by logistics start-ups and traditional logistics companies in applying agile methods are quite similarly distributed. Looking more closely at traditional logistics companies, they tend to have more of a problem with organisational culture and a lack of readiness for change. Participants from logistics start-ups stated that their employees/colleagues have less of a problem with change than with the unbalanced distribution

of knowledge in the agile teams. Both types of companies see the partial lack of knowledge about agile methods as a challenge

Agile coaches and Scrum Masters mainly identify the organisational culture, the lack of knowledge about agile methods and the resistance to change as challenges. In comparison, the unbalanced distribution of knowledge within teams, the knowledge of employees about the application of agile methods, the lack of availability of product owners and the lack of customer engagement in terms of feedback are challenges that top management and department heads see in the application of agile methods

Figure 82: Challenges of start-ups and traditional logistics companies using agile methods and practices

A.6.2. Report Delphi study – Round 2

As part of my PhD, I am conducting a Delphi study on the use and benefits of agile methods in traditional logistics companies as well as in logistics start-ups. In the following, you find the results from the second round of the Delphi study.

In this second round of the Delphi study 23 participants took part. Of these, 14 participants work in traditional logistics companies and 9 participants in logistics start-ups.

Selection criteria for agile methods

When asked about the criteria used to select agile methods, it was possible to give several answers. For each method, the participants were able to select more than one selection criterion, which is why more than 23 answers were given for some criteria.

The most used criterion for selecting agile methods is the own previous experience. This criterion is used more often than the fit of the method to requirements, the applicability for the team size and the previous knowledge of the team members themselves.

All nine participants of the logistics start-ups stated that they chose agile methods based on their previous knowledge. In traditional logistics companies, ten of the 14 participants confirmed this. Of the four remaining participants from traditional logistics companies, three participants had the support of external consultants or an agile coach in selecting the method. The fact that prior knowledge as a whole is the most frequently chosen criterion is particularly interesting, since the literature so far tends to assume that the circumstances and goals of the team are the main selection criterion (Campanelli and Parreiras, 2015).

A participant of a logistics start-up stated that most of the time the way they work develops over time and afterwards they find out that they do e.g. Feature-Driven-Development.

Less often the decision on the agile methods is made based on the marketing of the agile methods and its implementation cost. In eight out of ten cases, the Scrum method is specified in the company guidelines.

Figure 83: Selection criteria for the use of agile methods

Figure 84: Division of selection criteria between traditional logistics companies and logistics start-ups

The upper chart shows the distribution of used selection criteria between traditional logistics companies and logistics start-ups. It can be seen that these two types of companies use very different selection criteria. Even though in both company types most decisions are made based on the own previous experience traditional logistics companies follow more often the advice from external consultants and colleagues and company guidelines. Logistics start-ups make decisions with a greater focus on individual needs and more often include the applicability to the team size. The different heights of the pillars are mainly due to the fact that 14 participants come from traditional logistics companies whereas only nine participants work in logistics start-ups.

Overview of the agile practices used to achieve specific benefits

Practices used to respond to changing priorities / requirements by the customer

Figure 85: Overview of practices used to react to changing priorities by the customer

Sprint planning and feedback cycles with the customer in general are most commonly used to respond to changing priorities triggered by external influences, such as changing customer requirements. One third all logistics start-ups use daily standups to respond to changing priorities, while none of the traditional logistics companies considers this the most important practice to respond to external change.

Clustering the response options such as sprint planning, short feedback cycles with the customer, build-measure-learn cycles, regular software delivery, creation of minimum viable products and reviews, it becomes apparent that 16 of the 23 participants respond to the changing needs of the customer using an iterative approach.

Table 47 shows how many participants selected which method and how helpful they rated the methods in order to respond to external change. Looking at the average shows how well the practice actually helps on average to respond to changing priorities. Build-measure-learn cycles, customer feedback cycles and reviews are rated on average the best way to respond to changing priorities.

In addition, the participants mentioned twice continuous integration and continuous deployment as possible and good practices to deal with changing external priorities.

Table 47: Agile practices used to react on changing priorities by the customer (Likert scale results)

Agile practices used	Number	Proficiency of the practices on a scale of 1-7 (Mean)
Sprint planning	5	5.4
Feedback cycles with the customer	5	6.0
Daily standup	3	5.7
Close exchange within the team	3	5.5
Review	2	6.0
Regular delivery of the software	2	4.0
Creation of a minimum viable product	1	6.0
Agile release train	1	4.0

Build-measure-learn-cycles	1	7.0
Total	23	5.5

Practices used to respond to changing internal team priorities

Figure 86: Overview of practices used to react to changing internal priorities

Daily standups and a close exchange with the agile team are most commonly used to respond to changing internal team priorities. This also reflects the guidelines and principles of the Agile Manifesto (Beck et al., 2001) saying that “the most efficient and effective method of conveying information to and within a development team is face-to-face conversation”. Even if daily standups and the close exchange does not necessarily take place face-to-face, it can be seen that communication is important in the basics of agile theory. One participant stated that the close exchange takes not only place within a team but also between the teams and at management level.

The study participants were also asked how helpful the respective method is in reacting to changing internal priorities. Close exchange within the team is rated the highest, eight participants stated to use it to react to changing internal priorities.

Table 48: Agile practices used to react to changing internal priorities (Likert scale results)

Agile practices used	Number	Proficiency of the practices on a scale of 1-7 (Mean)
Daily standup	9	5.6
Close exchange within the team	8	5.8
Build-measure-learn-cycles	2	5.5
Working in feature teams	1	5.0
Sprint planning	1	5.0
Regular delivery of the software	1	5.0
Feedback cycles with the customer	1	5.0
Total	23	5.4

Practices used to accelerate product delivery

Regular software delivery is most commonly used to accelerate product delivery. Regular (and automated) software delivery allows quick feedback from the customer and users. This approach is supported by two additional comments of the participants, who have also indicated to use continuous integration and continuous deployment.

Figure 87: Overview of practices used to accelerate product delivery

The following table also shows that the number of different practices used to speed up the delivery of products. Start-ups seem to focus more on automated build and deployment, as they consider this the most appropriate practice for accelerating product delivery. Traditional logistics companies (rather) focus on close, regular exchange within the team and with the customer. Daily standups and the agile release train are rated as most effective.

Table 49: Agile practices used to accelerate product delivery (Likert scale results)

Agile practices used	Number	Proficiency of the practices on a scale of 1-7 (Mean)
Regular delivery of the software	6	5.7
Creation of a minimum viable product	4	5.5
Sprint planning	3	4.0
Close exchange within the team	3	5.3
Feedback cycles with the customer	1	5.0
Daily standup	1	6.0
Review	1	5.0
Agile release train	1	6.0
Monitoring the limit of work in progress	1	5.0
Regular builds of the software	2	5.0
Total	23	5.3

Practices used to improve communication between the customer and the IT department

Reviews are most commonly used to improve communication between the customer and the IT department. Participants gave preference to face-to-face communication over communication via software tools. Furthermore, communication from the team to the customer is often not a challenge, but rather between the different teams that are responsible for the customer.

Figure 88: Overview of practices used to improve communication between the customer and the IT

If you look at the theoretical guidelines of the review, this is also in line with the theory. The Scrum guide describes that “attendees (of the review) include the Scrum team and key stakeholders” (Schwaber, 1997). This means that customers, users and other stakeholders can participate in the review if it is beneficial to the team. The review is particularly successful if a culture of constructive criticism and open communication exist. However, if you consider the assessment of the participants, reviews are not the most effective practice. System Demos and regular builds and delivery of the software are ranked higher.

Table 50: Agile practices used to improve communication between the customer and the IT (Likert scale results)

Agile practices used	Number	Proficiency of the practices on a scale of 1-7 (Mean)
Review	5	4.6
Close exchange within the team	5	4.8
Feedback cycles with the customer	4	5.5
Other practices	3	4.7
System demo	2	5.5
Regular delivery of the software	2	6.0
Creation of a minimum viable product	1	3.0
Regular builds of the software	1	6.0
Total	23	5.0

Practices used to increase transparency on status and impediments

Daily standups and an updated Kanban/task board are used most often to increase transparency on the status and impediments. Transparency is one of the three pillars of the scrum guide (Schwaber, 1997). The other two pillars are "Inspect" and "Adapt" for which transparency is a prerequisite. Open, constructive communication and cooperation, e.g. via the Kanban board or in daily standups, is proposed in the agile principles to increase transparency. Some logistics companies also celebrate open and early communication about successes and failures, encouraging employees to engage in an open and constructive exchange.

Figure 89: Overview of practices used to increase transparency on status and impediments

Daily standups, retrospectives, inspect & adapt events and the usage of build-measure-learn cycles have been ranked to be the most effective to increase transparency within the agile team.

Table 51: Agile practices used to increase transparency (Likert scale results)

Agile practices used	Number	Proficiency of the practices on a scale of 1-7 (Mean)
Update of the Kanban board	7	5.1
Daily standups	5	5.8
Close exchange within the team	3	4.3
Review	2	5.5
Build-measure-learn-cycles	2	6.0
Feedback cycles with the customer	1	5.0
Retrospectives	1	6.0
Inspect & adapt event	1	6.0
System demo	1	4.0
Total	23	5.3

Practices used to increase product quality

Test-driven development (TDD) is used most often to increase product quality. Other used practices are reviews, feedback cycles and pair programming. These methods all have in common that feedback is given to the developer in the shortest possible time. One participant stated that they use the approach "The reviewer is responsible for the code, not the developer". This led to an enormous increase in product quality in their logistics start-up.

Figure 90: Overview of practices used to increase product quality

Refinement, minimum viable products and pair programming have ranked highest and seem to be the most effective to increase product quality. In practice, TDD is often very helpful but also difficult for developers to use.

Table 52: Agile practices used to increase product quality (Likert scale results)

Agile practices used	Number	Proficiency of the practices on a scale of 1-7 (Mean)
Test-driven Development	5	5.0
Review	4	5.8
Feedback cycles with the customer	3	5.7
Pair Programming	3	6.3
Close exchange within the team	2	5.5
Regular builds of the software	2	5.0
Build-Measure-Learn-Cycles	1	6.0
Refinement	1	7.0
Creation of a minimum viable product	2	6.5
Total	23	5.6

Overall, the rankings for the selected practices are very high, averaging 5.6.

Practices used to decrease project risk

Feedback cycles, the creation of minimum viable products and reviews are used most often to reduce project risk. All three have the goal of providing feedback as quickly as possible, so that, if necessary, it is possible to react as quickly as possible to deviations, e.g. to meet customer requirements. Fast feedback in general is one of the core approaches to agile processes.

Figure 91: Overview of practices used to reduce project risk

Development of a product vision, sprint plannings and regular software delivery have been assessed to be the most effective to reduce project risk. The shorter the feedback cycles and

sprints are, the less time is lost if the increment created does not meet the customer's requirements.

Table 53: Agile practices used to decrease product risk (Likert scale results)

Agile practices used	Number	Proficiency of the practices on a scale of 1-7 (Mean)
Feedback cycles with the customer	6	5.0
Creation of a minimum viable product	3	5.3
Review	3	4.7
Sprint planning	2	5.5
Regular builds of the software	2	5.5
Development of a product vision	2	6.0
Inspect & adapt event	1	5.0
Working in feature teams	1	5.0
System demo	1	5.0
Regular delivery of the software	1	6.0
Build-measure-learn-cycles	1	5.0
Total	23	5.2

Practices used to increase productivity of the team

Retrospectives, daily standups and close exchange within the team are used most often to increase productivity of the team. Retrospectives strive for the continuous improvement of processes and cooperation. This approach can already be seen in the Kaizen approach that has its origins in the Japanese automotive industry. Close and frequent interaction in the team often ensures that the team members are more motivated. They want to contribute to the team's success and also present their progress in the daily standup.

Figure 92: Overview of practices used to increase productivity of the team

Close exchange within the team, monitoring the limit of work in progress, refinements and feedback cycles have been rated the most effective to increase transparency within the agile team.

Table 54: Agile practices used to increase productivity (Likert scale results)

Agile practices used	Number	Proficiency of the practices on a scale of 1-7 (Mean)
Retrospectives	6	5.2
Daily standup	4	5.5
Close exchange within the team	4	6.0
Monitoring the limit of work in progress	3	6.0
Sprint planning	2	5.5
Refinement	1	6.0
Feedback cycles with the customer	1	6.0
Creation of a minimum viable product	1	5.0
Others	1	1.0
Total	23	5.4

The participant who selected "Other practice" stated in the free text field that increasing the productivity of the team is outside their focus.

It is noticeable that although logistics start-ups tend to choose agile methods according to their applicability and fit, for all questions in this second section (2. Overview of the agile practices used to achieve specific benefits, see page 280), traditional logistics companies rank the suitability of the respective practice on average higher than logistics start-ups. For example, logistics companies on average rate the suitability of their chosen practices for increasing responsiveness to external priorities at 5.6. Logistics start-ups rate the suitability of the practices at only 5.3 on average. This is the case for all questions in Section two.

Table 55: Overview of rankings for the individual advantages that are aimed at with agile methods

Agile practices used	Traditional logistics companies	Logistics start-ups
Respond to changing priorities / requirements by the customer	5.6	5.3
Respond to changing internal priorities	5.8	4.9
Accelerate product delivery	5.4	5.1
Improve communication between the customer and the IT department	5.1	4.8
Increase transparency on status and impediments	5.4	5.1
Increase product quality	5.6	5.6
Reduce project risk	5.4	5.0
Increase productivity	5.6	5.1
Average	5.5	5.1

Overall, across all agile practices and objectives, agile coaches and scrum masters rated the effectiveness of the agile practices used quite high compared to other study participants. At this point, a future study could question the reason for this. Do the agile coaches and scrum masters

have a different view on the use of agile practices? Or does their support of the team ensure that appropriate practices are used effectively by the team?

Agile Transformation

Twelve participants were or are still part of an agile transformation. Respectively, eleven out of the 23 participants stated, that they used agile methods from the beginning. More than half of the participants from logistics start-ups stated that they had already used agile methods directly from the beginning. This may be because in this study, start-ups are defined as being younger than 10 years and that agile methods originated in the 1990s. In this aspect, it was easier for logistics start-ups than for traditional logistics companies to work agile right from the start. Additionally, it may also be that start-ups are under more time pressure, especially at the beginning, to establish themselves on the market in order to earn money. One principle of agile methods is the fast delivery of products to enable direct feedback. This approach could be of high relevance especially for start-ups at the beginning.

Figure 93: Overview of the number and status of agile transformations in logistics companies

Only the 12 participants who stated that they had experienced an agile transformation were asked the following questions about the process of the transformation. Of these twelve participants, nine come from traditional logistics companies, while three come from logistics start-ups.

Drivers of the agile organisation

Two of three participants from logistics start-ups said that their agile transformation has been driven by people who also take on other tasks. This fits in well with the approach that is generally known from start-ups. Responsibilities, which are often divided among individuals in larger companies, are bundled in start-ups into less employees due to a lower number of resources. In traditional logistics companies, a dedicated team is formed for agile transformation in 33% of cases. Only one participant from a traditional logistics company stated that they were supported by external consultants during the transformation.

Figure 94: Different types of teams promote the introduction of agile methods

Important guidelines for the agile transformation

Looking at the recommended guidelines and lessons learned from agile transformation, management support is most important in traditional logistics companies as well as in logistics start-ups. It is interesting to note that even though teams aim to work in a self-organised manner, especially after the agile transformation, full support of the management is still important for the transformation. It is not only important that the transformation is approved, but also that the necessary resources (time, coaches, trainings, new office space, etc.) are made available. Afterwards the results differ. For traditional logistics companies, a promotion of a new organisational culture and the early involvement of employees is particularly important. For logistics start-ups, the focus on agile principles instead of processes is important.

Figure 95: Recommendations for the agile transformation

Factors that influence the successful use of agile methods

In the second round another look at the challenges of using agile methods that were selected most in the first round was taken. Results show that the impact of the challenges was rated differently in the second round. Although only nine of the total of 23 answers come from logistics start-ups, the participants' assessments are more widespread than the answers of the participants from traditional logistics companies. It is interesting to note that in the first round of the Delphi study, participants from logistics start-ups stated that they have fewer problems with the organisational culture and resistance to change of their employees than traditional logistics companies. In this second round, however, they rated the impact of organisational culture and resistance to change highest. This could indicate that logistics start-ups pay close attention to how the mindset of the employees towards changes is and whether the new employees fit into the organisational culture of the start-up. Although 50% of the participants from logistics start-ups and 20% of the participants from traditional logistics companies said in the first round of the Delphi study that they had problems with an unequal distribution of knowledge. However, in this second round the influence of the challenge was in total rated lower than the other challenges in this second round of the Delphi study. This could mean that traditional logistics companies as well as start-ups themselves have larger problems with an uneven distribution of knowledge, but also generally consider the problem not so big for other companies.

Figure 96: Impact of selected challenges on the successful application of agile methods

According to the results of the second round, the lack of knowledge about agile methods seems to be more of a problem in traditional logistics companies. In the first round, 29% of participants from logistics start-ups and 33% of participants from traditional logistics companies said they had a problem related to the lack of knowledge using agile methods.

Considering the lack of availability of the product owner, participants from logistics start-ups seem to have a widely spread opinion about how important the product owner is for the successful use of agile methods. Participants from traditional logistics companies rate the relevance of product owners for the successful use of agile methods higher than and not as diversified as the participants from logistics start-ups. In the first Delphi round the availability of the product owner was rated as the third most important challenge by participants from both types of companies.

Looking at the answers of the participants to the challenges, it is noticeable that department heads and upper management evaluate challenges of the agile transformation with a lower risk than scrum masters, agile coaches and other participants with a high level of experience with agile methods. Possible explanations could be that department heads and upper management perceive challenges differently or even rate their risk lower.

A.6.3. Report Delphi study – Round 3

As part of my PhD, I am conducting a Delphi study on the use and benefits of agile methods in traditional logistics companies as well as in logistics start-ups. In the following, you find the results from the third round of the Delphi study.

In this third round of the Delphi study 22 participants took part. Of these, 13 participants work in traditional logistics companies and 9 participants in logistics start-ups.

Selection criteria for agile methods

When asked about the criteria used to select agile methods, participants were asked in this third round to assess the importance of the following seven selection criteria:

- Own prior experience
- Meet the needs
- Applicability to team size
- Advice of ext. consultants
- Prior knowledge of team
- Company guidelines
- Advice of colleagues

Results of the second round showed that these seven criteria were used the most often by the participants to select agile methods. In this third round, participants were asked to assess the importance of these criteria in the selection of agile methods.

Overall, criteria assessed the most important in this third round were *own previous experience*, *applicability of the method for your own requirements* and *team size*. This corresponds to the results of the second round. Less important criteria are the *advice of external consultants and colleagues* and the *previous knowledge in the team*. A large spread of responses can be seen in the criterion *company guidelines*.

Similar as in the second round, the most important criterion for start-ups in this third round is *own previous experience* with the agile methods. In traditional logistics companies, the most important criterion is the *applicability of the method to their own requirements*. In the second round, the criteria *company guidelines* and *own previous experience* were rated more important in traditional logistics companies. This could be due to the way questions were asked in the second and third round. In the second round, it was asked which criteria were used. In the third round, participants were asked to assess the importance of the selection criteria. It is possible that participants from traditional logistics companies find it important to select the agile method based on its *applicability to their requirements* in theory, but in real life, they have to follow

company guidelines. Another possibility is, that in real life, it might be easier and bears less risk to select agile methods based on their *own previous experience*.

A participant of a traditional logistics company stated that the approaches “Inspect” and “Adapt”, which are two of the Scrum pillars, determine his everyday life. With the selection of agile methods, these approaches allow the constant possibility of adjusting if the method chosen is not the right one.

Figure 97: Assessment of the selection criteria for the use of agile methods

When using agile methods, how strictly should you generally follow the theory or adapt the methods to your own circumstances?

Participants were asked to what extent, on a scale of *one* to *seven*, they adapt agile methods and practices to their own circumstances. *Seven* corresponds to following the pure form of the agile theory and *one* means maximum adaptation to one's own circumstances.

Figure 98: Overview on the assessment of participants on the adaption of agile methods

The answers of the 13 participants from traditional logistics companies and the nine participants from logistics start-ups result in the following statistical values.

Table 56: Overview of the statistical analysis of participants' replies in relation to the degree of adaptation of agile methods

	Min	Max	Average	Median	Mode
Traditional logistics companies (n = 13)	1	6	3.3	3	2
Logistics start-ups (n = 22)	1	6	3.1	2	2
Total (n = 22)	1	6	3.2	2	2

The bar chart shows that traditional logistics companies and logistics start-ups rate the question rather similarly. This also results in the nearly similar values of the statistical evaluation. However, the Figure 29 shows that the participants of traditional logistics companies tend to adapt agile methods a little more than logistics start-ups.

In the literature, some studies show that especially when introducing agile methods, companies are more successful if they adhere strongly to the original guidelines of the agile methods. In these cases, the agile approach will only be adapted later, when experience has been gained in using the agile methods (Moreira, 2013; Dingsoeyr, Falessi and Power, 2019).

In this study, many of the participants stated that they would adapt the agile methods. This could be due to the experience of the participants in this study. Only participants with great expertise in agile methods were surveyed and it is conceivable that they adapt agile methods directly because they have enough experience. Results of the first round of the Delphi study show, that especially participants who ranked their own experience with agile methods higher than other participants adapt agile methods more strongly to their conditions (see Results of first round, page 253).

What affects the successful use of agile methods?

In the last part of the third round, participants were asked to answer multiple choice questions to describe how the following challenges in the use of agile methods are manifested specifically:

- Unequal distribution of knowledge

- Strict organisational culture
- Fear of change
- Incomplete knowledge of agile methods
- Availability of the product owner

Unequal distribution of knowledge

The participants' replies are quite similarly spread over the different effects of unequal distribution of knowledge, regardless of whether they work in a traditional logistics company or a logistics start-up.

Figure 99: Overview of the effects of unequal distribution of knowledge in the team on the use of agile methods

In four traditional logistics companies, the lack of T-shaping, i.e. the improvement of the skills of the team members and their ability to work across disciplines, is a problem. No participant from a logistics start-up stated this to be a problem.

Strict organisational culture

With regard to organisational culture, the participants stated that in most cases strict hierarchies limit the agile approach. In traditional logistics companies, the two next most important effects of a strict organisational culture are the lack of personal responsibility and supervisors that disrespect the team's independent way of working. In logistics start-ups, on the other hand, the organisational culture has a particularly strong influence on the ability to talk openly about mistakes and on the agile mindset in general.

Figure 100: Overview of the effects of organisational culture on the use of agile methods

Fear of change

With regard to the fear of change, the participants have very different opinions. Participants from traditional logistics companies state that due to fear of change, teams are not able to develop in the best possible way, adopt the agile approach not quickly enough or don't react flexible enough. Participants from logistics start-ups state that the teams do not expand their knowledge enough and do not deliver the greatest possible value added for the customer.

Figure 101: Overview of the effects of fear of change on the use of agile methods

Clustering these results, it becomes clear that traditional logistics companies tend to have a problem with the fear of changes in agile transformation. On the other hand, employees in logistics start-ups cannot serve customers in the best possible way due to the fear of change.

Incomplete knowledge of agile methods

Figure 102: Effects of incomplete knowledge of agile methods on the use of agile methods

Given the incomplete knowledge of agile methods, traditional logistics companies and logistics start-ups again agree on the effects. Incomplete knowledge of agile methods prevents that the

greatest possible value added can be generated for the customer because the agile methods are not used correctly. In addition, the incorrect use of agile methods can limit the responsibility agile teams do take.

Availability of the product owner

Figure 103: Overview of the effects of the lack of the product owner on the use of agile methods

If the product owner is missing, the agile team is blocked and the team does not feel jointly responsible for the success of the product. In addition, the PO needs to be available to answer functional questions at short notice. Participants from traditional logistics companies and logistics start-ups agreed that these are the important consequences when the product owner is not available.

A.7. Questionnaire survey

In the following the questionnaire of the survey is presented. The original answers of the participants are available and can be handed out on request.

Load unfinished survey

0%

Language: English - English Change the language

Agility in logistics startups

Dear Participant,

Thank you for taking the time to participate in this scientific study.

The questionnaire takes **about 15-20 minutes** to complete. The survey consists of 4 pages and a **total of 24 questions**.

Here is some helpful advice on how to complete the questionnaire:

- Please, first read the notes, which are given at the beginning of the page.
- Before answering the questions, read the corresponding information.
- If you want to read information about the agile methods or practices, then you can use the attached links.

We are very interested in sending you the results of the survey. If you would like to receive them, enter your email address at the end of the survey. In doing so, you will automatically participate in a price draw of an Apple iPad Pro.

All answers will be kept strictly confidential and will not be passed on to third parties. The collection of data is for scientific purposes only.

Thank you very much for taking part in the survey as an expert!

There are 24 questions in this survey.

Next

Personal details and Information about the Company (Page 1/4)

Note:

Team = The project team in which you spend the most working time.

Agile methods structure agile principles and practices into a defined pattern of procedures. Examples of agile methods are Scrum, Kanban, Extreme Programming (XP).

Agile practices are based on agile values and principles and they are individual elements within an agile method. Examples of agile practices are Sprint Planning, Daily Scrum, Review, Pair Programming.

What is your current position in your logistics company?

Choose one of the following answers

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="radio"/> Agile Coach | <input type="radio"/> Product Manager |
| <input type="radio"/> Developer | <input type="radio"/> Project Manager |
| <input type="radio"/> Functional or Technical Architect | <input type="radio"/> Scrum Master |
| <input type="radio"/> Head of Department | <input type="radio"/> Top Management (CEO / CIO / CTO, ...) |
| <input type="radio"/> Product Owner | <input type="radio"/> Other: <input type="text"/> |

How many years of experience do you have with agile methods like Scrum, Kanban, SAFe, LeSS, Extreme Programming, etc.?

Choose one of the following answers

- No Experience
- ≤ 1 Year
- > 1 Year but ≤ 3 Years
- > 3 Years but ≤ 5 Years
- > 5 Years but ≤ 10 Years
- > 10 Years

How would you rate your expertise in agile methods and practices?

	1 (low)	2	3	4	5	6	7 (high)
Please, rate your expertise in agile methods and practices	<input type="radio"/>						

How do you work together in your team?

Choose one of the following answers

- Hybrid approach combines elements from the classical and agile approaches
- Classical Approach (Waterfall Model)
- Agile Approach
- Hybrid Approach
- Other:

How many people work in your team?

Choose one of the following answers

- Just me alone
- One more Person and me
- > 2 People but ≤ 5 People
- > 5 People but ≤ 9 People
- > 9 People but ≤ 15 People
- > 15 People

When was your logistics startup founded?

Choose one of the following answers

- ≤ 1 Year ago
- > 1 Year ago but ≤ 3 Years ago
- > 3 Years ago but ≤ 5 Years ago
- > 5 Years ago but ≤ 10 Years ago
- > 10 Years ago

How many employees has your logistics company in total?

Choose one of the following answers

- ≤ 10 Employees
- > 10 Employees but ≤ 30 Employees
- > 30 Employees but ≤ 50 Employees
- > 50 Employees but ≤ 100 Employees
- > 100 Employees but ≤ 250 Employees
- > 250 Employees but ≤ 500 Employees
- > 500 Employees

Previous

Next

Use of agile methods and practices (Page 2/4)

Note:

Team = The project team in which you spend the most working time.

Agile methods structure agile principles and practices into a defined pattern of procedures. Examples of agile methods are Scrum, Kanban, Extreme Programming (XP).

Agile practices are based on agile values and principles and they are individual elements within an agile method. Examples of agile practices are Sprint Planning, Daily Scrum, Review, Pair Programming.

Is your team more likely to use the whole agile method or selected practices?

Choose one of the following answers

- Using the **complete** agile method, for example Scrum or Kanban
- Using only **selected** agile practices, for example Sprint Planning or Pair-Programming
- Using **no** agile methods or agile practices
- Other:

In what form do you use agile methods in your team?

Information:

Planned = Not yet in use, but intended for the future

Unknown = No statement possible or practice not in use

For more information about the agile methods use the links below

* **Theoretical guidelines** are publications in which process contents of methods are defined. Theoretical guidelines for agile methods can be, for example, Scrum Guide or all science published papers.

Links for more information:

Scrum: <http://tiny.cc/ScrumMethod> ; **Kanban:** <http://tiny.cc/Kanban> ; **XP:** <http://tiny.cc/ExtremeProgramming> ; **Scrumban:** <https://tinyurl.com/y6ddun4f> ; **FDD:** <http://tiny.cc/FeatureDD> ; **Lean Startup:** <http://tiny.cc/LeanStart> ; **Crystal:** <http://tiny.cc/CrystalMethod> ; **SAFe:** <http://tiny.cc/SafeMethod> ; **LeSS:** <http://tiny.cc/Less>

	Following theoretical Guidelines*	Single Practices are adjusted	Several Practices are adjusted	Most Practices are adjusted	Fully adjusted to Team's Specifics	Planned	Unknown
Scrum	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Kanban	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Extreme Programming (XP)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Scrumban	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Feature Driven Development (FDD)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lean Startup	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Crystal	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Scaled Agile Framework (SAFe)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Large Scale Scrum (LeSS)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

How regularly do you use the following agile practices in your team? (part 1 of 2)

Information:

Planned = Not yet in use, but intended for the future

Unknown = No statement possible or practice not in use

For more information about the agile practices use the links below

Links for more information:

Daily Standup: <http://tiny.cc/Daily> ; **Update of the Task:** <http://tiny.cc/TaskBoard> ; **Close exchange within the Team:** <http://tiny.cc/TeamCommunication> ; **Feedback Cycles with the Customer:** <http://tiny.cc/CustFeedback> ; **Retrospectives:** <http://tiny.cc/SprintRetro> ; **Delivery of the Software:** <http://tiny.cc/FrequentDelivery> ; **Review:** <http://tiny.cc/SprintReview> ; **Sprint Planning:** <http://tiny.cc/SprintPlanning> ; **Creation of a Minimum Viable:** <http://tiny.cc/MinimumVP> ; **Product:** <http://tiny.cc/MinimumVP> ; **Refactoring:** <http://tiny.cc/Refactoring> ; **Builds of the Software:** <http://tiny.cc/Build> ; **System Demo:** <http://tiny.cc/SystemDemo>

	Daily	Multiple times a Month	Once a Month	Several times a Year	Never	Planned	Unknown
Daily Standup	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Update of the Task (Kanban Board)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Close exchange within the Team	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Feedback Cycles with the Customer	<input type="radio"/>						
Retrospectives	<input type="radio"/>						
Delivery of the Software	<input type="radio"/>						
Review	<input type="radio"/>						
Sprint Planning	<input type="radio"/>						
Creation of a Minimum Viable Product	<input type="radio"/>						
Refactoring	<input type="radio"/>						
Buils of the Software	<input type="radio"/>						
System Demo	<input type="radio"/>						

How regularly do you use the following agile practices in your team? (part 2 of 2)

Information:

Planned = Not yet in use, but intended for the future,

Unknown = No statement possible or practice not in use

For more information about the agile practices use the links below

[🔗 Links for more information:](#)

Work in Feature Teams: <http://tiny.cc/FeatureTeams> ; **Refinement:** <http://tiny.cc/Refinement> ; **Test-Driven Development:** <http://tiny.cc/TestDD> ; **Pair-Programming:** <http://tiny.cc/PairProgramming> ; **Merging the Code back into the Master/Baseline:** <http://tiny.cc/Merge> ; **Monitoring of Limit for Work in Progress:** <http://tiny.cc/WIPLimit> ; **Inspect & Adapt Event:** <http://tiny.cc/IaA> ; **Build-Measure-Learn Cycles:** <http://tiny.cc/BML> ; **Programm increment Planning:** <http://tiny.cc/PIplanning> ; **Agile Release Train:** <http://tiny.cc/AgileReleaseTrain>

	Daily	Multiple times a Month	Once a Month	Several times a Year	Never	Planned	Unknown
Work in Feature Teams	<input type="radio"/>						
Refinement	<input type="radio"/>						
Test-Driven Development	<input type="radio"/>						
Pair-Programming	<input type="radio"/>						
Merging the Code back into the Master/Baseline	<input type="radio"/>						
Monitoring of Limit for Work in Progress	<input type="radio"/>						
Inspect & Adapt Event	<input type="radio"/>						
Build-Measure-Learn Cycles	<input type="radio"/>						
Programm increment Planning	<input type="radio"/>						
Agile Release Train	<input type="radio"/>						
Method unknown	<input type="checkbox"/>						
Use not planned	<input type="checkbox"/>						

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Introduction and scaling of agility methods in your company (Page 3/4)

Note:

Team = The project team in which you spend the most working time.

Agile methods structure agile principles and practices into a defined pattern of procedures. Examples of agile methods are Scrum, Kanban, Extreme Programming (XP).

Agile practices are based on agile values and principles and they are individual elements within an agile method. Examples of agile practices are Sprint Planning, Daily Scrum, Review, Pair Programming.

Is the scaling of agile methods planned or in use, e.g. by methods such as LeSS and SAFe?

	No	Planned	In Use	Unknown
Large Scale Scrum (LeSS)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Scaled Agile Framework (SAFe)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Who took the **initiative** and introduced agile methods and practices in your team?

(Multiple answers possible)

If you are not currently using agile methods and practices, who would lead to the initiative?

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Agile Coach | <input type="checkbox"/> Senior Management |
| <input type="checkbox"/> External Consultants | <input type="checkbox"/> Team Leader |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Product Manager | <input type="checkbox"/> Together as a Team |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Head of Department | <input type="checkbox"/> Other: <input type="text"/> |
| <input type="checkbox"/> My decision | |

Who **decided** which agile methods and practices to use? (Multiple answers possible)

If you don't currently use agile methods and practices, who would decide?

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Agile Coach | <input type="checkbox"/> Senior Management |
| <input type="checkbox"/> External Consultants | <input type="checkbox"/> Team Leader |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Product Manager | <input type="checkbox"/> Together as a Team |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Head of Department | <input type="checkbox"/> Other: <input type="text"/> |
| <input type="checkbox"/> My decision | |

How can the introduction of agile methods be supported?
(Select up to three of the most important factors)

- Support for Transformation by Senior Management
- Following a defined Transformation Plan
- Compilation of a dedicated Transformation Team
- Supporting the Transformation with External Consultants
- Focus on Agile Principles instead of Processes
- Minimal Adaptation of Agile Methods to the Circumstances
- Early Focus on Automation of (Software Development) Processes
- Maximal Adaptation of Agile Methods to the Circumstances
- Early involvement of Employees
- Support from an Agile Coach
- Early coaching of the Agile Team
- Creating a new Organisational Culture

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Business objectives and challenges (Page 4/4)

You are almost done! This is the last page!

By introducing agile methods or agile practices in the team, we have...?

	Disagree	Rather Disagree	Draw	Rather Agree	Agree	No Answer
...increased customer satisfaction.	<input type="radio"/>					
...increased employee satisfaction.	<input type="radio"/>					
...increased business value.	<input type="radio"/>					
...increased on-time delivery.	<input type="radio"/>					
...increased transparency of risks.	<input type="radio"/>					
...improved project processes.	<input type="radio"/>					
...increased project transparency for the team and the customer.	<input type="radio"/>					
...increased flexibility of the product scope.	<input type="radio"/>					
...improved productivity in the team.	<input type="radio"/>					
...improved communication in the team.	<input type="radio"/>					
...improved communication between the team and the customer.	<input type="radio"/>					

Which agile methods do you use for the following challenges in your team?

How well suited are they? (Part 1/2)

Information: XP = Extreme Programming, FDD = Feature Driven, SAFe = Scaled Agile Framework

For more information about the agile methods use the links below

🔗 Links for more information:

Scrum: <http://tiny.cc/ScrumMethod> ; **Kanban:** <http://tiny.cc/Kanban> ; **XP:** <http://tiny.cc/ExtremeProgramming> ; **Scrumban:** <https://tinyurl.com/y6ddun4f>
FDD: <http://tiny.cc/FeatureDD> ; **Lean Startup:** <http://tiny.cc/LeanStart> ; **Crystal:** <http://tiny.cc/CrystalMethod> ; **SAFe:** <http://tiny.cc/SafeMethod> ; **LeSS:** <http://tiny.cc/Less>

	Select suitable agile Method									How well is the selected method suited?					
	Scrum	Kanban	XP	FDD	Lean Startup	Crystal-method	Scrum-ban	SAFe	No Method	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	No Answer
Response to changing External Priorities/Requirements	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Response to changing Internal Priorities	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Accelerate Product Delivery	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Improve Communication between the Customers and the IT Department	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Increase Transparency on Status and Impediments	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Increase Product Quality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Which agile methods do you use for the following challenges in your team?

How well suited are they?

(Part 2/2)

Information: XP = Extreme Programming, FDD = Feature Driven, SAFe = Scaled Agile Framework

For more information about the agile methods use the links below

🔗 **Links for more information:**

Scrum: <http://tiny.cc/ScrumMethod> ; **Kanban:** <http://tiny.cc/Kanban> ; **XP:** <http://tiny.cc/ExtremeProgramming> **Scrumban:** <https://tinyurl.com/y6ddun4f>
FDD: <http://tiny.cc/FeatureDD> ; **Lean Startup:** <http://tiny.cc/LeanStart> ; **Crystal:** <http://tiny.cc/CrystalMethod> **SAFe:** <http://tiny.cc/SafeMethod> ; **LeSS:** <http://tiny.cc/Less>

	Select suitable agile Method										How well is the selected method suited?					
	Scrum	Kanban	XP	FDD	Lean Startup	Crystal-method	Scrum-ban	SAFe	Other	No Method	Very low	Low	Medium	High	Very high	No Answer
Optimization of Work Organization	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Technical Optimization of Software Development	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Scaling of the Team	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Optimization of Team Collaboration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reduce Costs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Increase Productivity of Work Processes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reduce Project Risk	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

How strong were the challenges in your team during the introduction of agile methods or agile practices?

Information:

1 (weak) = The challenge in the team was very low.

7 (strong) = The challenge in the team was very high.

	No Challenge	1 (weak)	2	3	4	5	6	7 (strong)
Unequal Distribution of Knowledge	<input type="radio"/>							
Strict Organizational Culture	<input type="radio"/>							
Fear of Change	<input type="radio"/>							
Incomplete Knowledge of Agile Methods	<input type="radio"/>							
(Not) Availability of the Product Owner	<input type="radio"/>							

Thank you for participating in the survey!

Please enter your email address if you want the results of the survey and/or take part in the price draw.

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[Submit](#)

A.8. Tested data categories of the survey data

Besides the age of the start-ups, other types of clustering would also have been possible. The following table shows which data clusters were also tested for significant differences. T/S" corresponds to a significant difference and "T/N" to a test without significance. Since the details regarding the age of the start-ups are presented in the section on the survey results, no comments were included for the age cluster (see Section 7.3. – Results of the survey, page 133).

Table 57: Overview of tested data clusters

Questioned aspects	Data clusters						Comments
	Origin of start-ups	Size of start-ups	Role of participants	Asset based vs. Asset-light	Initiator of agile methods	Selector of agile methods	
Is your team more likely to use the whole agile method or selected practices?	T/N	T/N	T/N	T/N	T/N	T/N	None
In what form do you use agile methods in your team?	T/S	T/N	T/N	T/N	T/N	T/N	Kanban is used more often in Germany. For many participants, the country allocation was not possible as not all participants left their e-mail address in the survey.
How regularly do you use the followings agile practices in your team?	T/N	T/N	T/S	T/N	T/N	T/N	Agile coaches and scrum masters use agile practices more often and follow the guidelines more closely.
Is the scaling of methods planned or in user e.g. by methods such as LeSS and SAFe?	T/N	T/N	T/S	T/N	T/N	T/N	Agile coaches state more frequently than participants with other roles that scaling methods such as SAFe and LeSS are used.

Questioned aspects	Data clusters						Comments
	Origin of start-ups	Size of start-ups	Role of participants	Asset based vs. Asset-light	Initiator of agile methods	Selector of agile methods	
How can the introduction of agile methods be supported?	T/N	T/S	T/N	T/N	T/N	T/N	Start-ups with between 100 and 250 employees and start-ups with 500 or more employees use especially many support measures when introducing agile methods.
By introducing agile methods we have realised...[the following benefits]?	T/N	T/N	T/S	T/N	T/N	T/N	Agile coaches and scrum masters rate the realisation of benefits through the use of agile methods higher than top managers or department heads do.
Which agile methods do you use for the following challenges in your team?	T/N	T/N	T/N	T/N	T/N	T/N	Start-ups with between 100 and 250 employees and start-ups with 500 or more employees encounter a particularly large number of challenges when using the agile methods.
How strong were the challenges in your team during the introduction of agile methods or agile practices?	T/N	T/N	T/S	T/N	T/N	T/N	None

T/S = Tested and significant differences found, T/N = Tested and no significant differences found